

**APPLICATION OF JOHN LOCKE'S SOCIAL CONTRACT
IN RESOLVING INCESSANT CONFLICT BETWEEN
FEDERAL GOVERNMENT OF NIGERIA (FGN)
AND ACADEMIC STAFF UNION OF
UNIVERSITIES (ASUU)**

BY

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**DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATIONAL FOUNDATIONS
FACULTY OF EDUCATION
UNIVERSITY OF NIGERIA, NSUKKA**

MARCH, 2024

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**A Ph.D THESIS PRESENTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATIONAL
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IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF
DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY (Ph.D) IN PHILOSOPHY OF EDUCATION**

SUPERVISOR: REV FR. PROF. G. C. ABIOGU

MARCH, 2024

APPROVAL PAGE

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DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to my beloved wife, Mrs. Njoku Thelma for her prayers and moral support all through the period of this research.

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study was to investigate the extent to which Locke's social contract theory can resolve the incessant conflict between the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) and the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU). The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Four research questions and four null hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study comprised 4,354 subjects (15 directors of federal ministry of education, Abuja, 12 directors of federal ministry of labour, Abuja and 4,327 academic staff of federal universities in South-East). A sample of 448 respondents comprising 15 directors of FME and 433 lecturers drawn from three federal universities through a simple random sampling technique was used for the study. A structured questionnaire titled: Locke's Social Contract and Conflict Resolution Questionnaire (LSCCRQ) and interview schedule developed by the researcher from the reviewed literature were used for data collection. Three lecturers from the Faculty of Education University of Nigeria, Nsukka validated the instruments. The reliability of the instruments was determined using Crombach Alpha. The direct delivery and retrieval method was employed in distributing the instrument with the aid of 3 research assistants. The four research questions were answered using mean (\bar{x}) and Standard deviation (SD) while t-test statistics was used to test the four null hypotheses posed at 0.05 level of significance and the interview schedule data was analyzed using thematic analysis method. An overview of the results showed that mutual obligation as envisaged by John Locke can be used to resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU to a very high extent while the people's right of consent, people's right to property ownership and the people's right of revolution can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN to a high extent. The result of the t-test analysis of hypothesis found that the difference between the respondents on the extent mutual obligation can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU is not statistically significant. By implication the null hypothesis is not rejected. Whereas there is a statistically significant difference in the responses of the respondents on the extent to which People's right of consent, people's right to property ownership and the people's right of revolution can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU, by implication the corresponding null hypotheses are rejected. Based on the results of the study, the researcher concluded that Locke's social contract theory is to a high extent an applicable approach in resolving the incessant conflict between the FGN and ASUU. Thus, in formulating and implementation of policies or strategies for the resolution of FGN-ASUU conflicts in Nigerian universities irrespective of the geographical zones of the university, John Locke's idea of social contract should be considered and adopted as a model or guiding principle. Consequently, the study recommends among other things that both ASUU and FGN should at all cost avoid renegeing on their agreements reached in the course of resolving their conflicts to avoid all forms of hostility and intolerance between them.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Globally, education is regarded as an effective tool for individual and national development. Unfortunately, the incessant conflict between the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) and Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) which has always resulted to industrial strike actions by ASUU has posed a serious impediment to the realization of the university education goals in Nigeria. It has therefore, become almost impossible for the Nigerian university educational system to fulfill its expectations of human capital development for national economic advancement. Negotiation attempts to resolve this conflict in the past has led ASUU and the government to enter into several documented mutual agreements. However, the conflict has remained largely unresolved probably because the government has repeatedly reneged on the terms of the agreements or could it be that an effective conflict resolution strategy is yet to be applied in the matter? This question is pertinent considering the rate at which the conflict has continued to resurface time after time. The cumulative consequence of this conflict on the university education system is best left to imagination.

The university education system for this work can be defined as the highest arm of education under the tertiary education level in Nigeria. The tertiary education level is the highest level among the three levels of education in the country namely: Basic education, Secondary education and Tertiary education. The Nigerian educational system is currently organized on the 9-3-4 system of education which implies, 9 years of basic education, 3 years of senior secondary and 4 years of tertiary/ University education (Njoku, Njoku, Ugo-Israel and Umealor, 2017). The university education offers graduate and post graduate degrees in different fields of study and in different areas of specialization. There are about 174 universities registered by the National University Commissions (NUC), of which there are 43 federal universities, 52 state owned universities and 79 Private universities (NUC, 2020). The Nigerian government allowed private bodies to organize and

provide private university education to augment the government owned universities in order to ensure efficient university education in the country. Otonko (2012) and Okerulo (2010) defined the university as Ivory Tower and center for excellence where knowledge, a 'public good', ideas and ideals are disseminated and acquired; future leaders are developed and high level technical human capacity that ensures economic growth and development are forged through lecturing/ teaching, learning, research, internship and practicum. According to the Nigerian Policy on education document of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN), the main function of the Nigerian university education is the provision of much needed manpower to fast-track the socio-economic development of the nation while the specific goals include: To contribute to national development through high level relevant manpower production; Development and inculcation of proper values for the survival of the individual and the society; Development of the intellectual capability of the individuals to appreciate their local and external environments; To ensure the acquisition of physical and mental skills to enable individuals to be self-reliant and useful to the society; To promote and encourage scholarship and community service; forging and cementing national unity and to promote national and international interaction and understanding (FRN, 2013). These laudable goals expected of the universities illustrate the lofty expectations placed on the university education by the Nigerian government. Lofty as they may seem, these goals are attainable if the university system is properly managed.

The Nigerian university system is managed by two structures as stressed by Adeniyi (2015): the internal structure and the external structure. The internal management structure comprises of the Visitor who is usually the Head of State or the Head of Government that established the university (The President in case of Federal universities and the Governors in case of State universities); the Vice Chancellor (VC), who is the head of the university; the Governing Council, headed by the Chairman (Pro-Chancellor) responsible for goal setting, policy formulation, staff development, general discipline, budget approval and liaison activities with the government for the university; the Senate (headed by the VC with the Registrar as the Secretary) and finally, the university committees.

The external structure speaks of the government management of the university through the ministries of education and the National University Commission (NUC). Whereas the state ministry of education oversees the state universities, the Federal Ministry of Education (FME) oversees the federal universities. The FME is the government body authorized to carry out the functions of formulating national policy on education, collecting and collating data for purposes of educational planning and financing as well as harmonizing quality of education throughout the country (Olawale, 2020). FME carries out these functions through its departments headed by directors who are also members of the staff of the ministry. NUC is a Commission that coordinates and regulates university management on behalf of the federal government of Nigeria.

The Ministry of Labour and Employment is another auspice of the government that plays a prominent role in the course of managing university education especially, in the area of staff union versus government Labour disputes. That is because, the ministry is generally concerned with employee-employers relationship as it is saddled with the responsibility of formulating policies on trade union organizations as well as handles trade disputes and complaints, assist in worker's education and keeps records on trade unions and their activities. It is in keeping to these responsibilities that brought the ministry to the front line as a representative of the federal government in their negotiations with ASUU in the course of their conflict resolutions. The federal Minister of Labour and Employment, Sen. Chris Ngige, has therefore been a major mouth piece of the government in her dispute with ASUU so much so that his grandstanding disposition in defiance defense of the government on the matter has made the federal government versus ASUU dispute seem like Ngige versus ASUU dispute in recent times. Based on the above, when the actions of federal government of Nigeria is mentioned in this work, it invariably implies the action of the Federal Ministry of Education and the Federal Minister of Labour and Employment and vice versa.

The federal government of Nigeria (FGN) is the apex government body out of the three arms of government in the country. Administratively, Nigeria is organized in six geopolitical zones (North-East, North-West, North-Central, South-East, South-West and South-South) and three tiers of

government, the Local Government Area, the state government and the Federal government. As provided by the Nigerian constitution, each of these tiers of government has their peculiar functions known as residual functions but some issues are collectively handled by the three tiers known as the concurrent functions (Egerue, 2019). Prominent among such concurrent functions is education. The Nigerian constitution permits each tier of government to focus its responsibilities mainly on a particular level of education. Hence, tertiary education is the main focus of Federal Government. In other words, Federal government is saddled with the responsibility of overseeing the government owned universities. The state governments are in charge of secondary education and the local governments take care of the basic education (International Organisation for Migration (IOM), 2014). According to IOM (2014), the Federal Government is also expected to support the state and local governments in counterpart funding as well as formulate educational policies through the Federal Ministry of Education to ensure quality control of all educational sectors and for effective management and provision of quality education in the country. For this research hence, the federal government of Nigeria (FGN) can be defined as the highest arm of the Nigerian government saddled with the responsibility of overseeing and regulating the general government administrations and educational system especially, the university educational system.

Academic staff union of universities (ASUU) is an umbrella that unites all teaching staff of the universities in Nigeria. For this work, ASUU is defined as a national trade union created for the purpose of fighting for the interest and welfare of academic staff of universities in Nigeria. It is an off shoot of the Nigerian Association of University Teachers (NAUT) which was an association of teaching staff of universities in Nigeria formed in 1965. The association was rebranded to Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) in 1978 under the Trade Unions Decree No. 22 of 1978. ASUU was created to continue the propagation and championing of the welfare of Nigerian lecturers. Its members are all academic staff of the universities comprising of lecturers from graduate assistant cadre to professorial cadre. This set of staff according to Okebukola (2010) plays a tripartite role of teaching, research and administration (in the cases of heads of department, faculty deans, provost of

schools, program coordinators, and so on). In other words, ASUU plays very essential role in the university system. Abiogu and Ugwuja (2007) asserted that the most important factor in education is the teacher, not technique, method or curriculum because the teacher translates all the other factors into meaningful learning experiences for the students.

The striving of ASUU to bring the government to understand and respect the importance of ASUU in university education and her firm stand against undemocratic policies of the government has made her relationship with the federal Government more of acrimonious and antagonistic. More so, due to her constitutional responsibility of managing university education, the federal government according to IOM (2014) sees the university and its staff, including ASUU as an organ of the state's bureaucracy which should be totally submissive to the interest of the government. The expression of this ideology by the government in her decisions and policies has never gone down well with ASUU. This is because, as observed by Albert (2015), ASUU sees the university as an autonomous entity, a status that ought to be respected by the government. Hence, ASUU poses as the mouth piece for the university community striving to curtail the administrative excesses of the government over the university affairs. These conflicting interests and ideologies have created an ugly circumstance of power tussle between the two parties and that has made them sworn enemies rather than partners in progress which they ought to be. This is probably the reason why it has been difficult for the two parties to resolve their conflicts.

Although, conflict is inevitable in every human society or organization, due to human insatiability, plurality of views and conflicting interests especially in employee-employer or government-labor relationships, quick resolution of the conflict is imperative for the progress of the organization. Segun (2013) defines conflict as clash, contention, confrontation, a battle, struggle or quarrel. While Hocker and Wilmont (2011) defined it as a felt struggle between two or more interdependent individuals over perceived and incompatible differences in beliefs, values, and goals, or differences in desires for esteem and control. For the sake of this work, conflict can be defined as the disagreement between two or more parties (in this case, between federal government of Nigeria

and ASUU) over certain issues (mostly University autonomy and academic freedom, funding and staff conditions of services).

The FGN-ASUU conflict has remained unresolved and incessant, probably because the federal government of Nigeria is yet to find and apply the right approach to permanently resolve their ideological differences all these years. This is obvious considering their inability to resolve the issues pertaining to university autonomy, academic freedom, poor funding of the universities and poor staff conditions of services of university workers which all along have constituted the major bone of contention between ASUU and FGN. According to Bello and Isah (2016) ASUU in their memoranda and communiqués in the past has always identified poor state of the universities, erosion of University autonomy and academic freedom, poor conditions of services of university staff and inadequate funding of Universities as major causes of its conflict with the government. Igbogidi (2014) has earlier reported that ASUU has through communiqués and press releases condemned the increasing interference of some auspices of the federal government such as NUC, the Federal Ministry of Education, office of the President and the Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board (JAMB) in the internal affairs of the Universities. In corroboration, Odoziobodo (2015) recalled that ASUU has severally embarked on nation-wide strikes to among other things, push for academic freedom and university autonomy because ASUU members believe that university autonomy and academic freedom are indispensable for the advancement, transmission and application of knowledge, hence their vocal and firm demand for autonomy and academic freedom.

The government on its own side has through its various representatives such as the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Labour and Employment reiterated its right to control all affairs of the universities since it pays university staff salaries, provides infrastructure and funds most activities of the universities. In his research, Asiyai (2013) reported that the ongoing government arbitrary interference in university affairs started as far back as 1975 when the then government usurped the powers of university council to dismiss staff. More so, staff unions of university have been arbitrarily proscribed and unbanned at various times; several Vice Chancellors have been sacked just for

refusing government imposed decisions; many lecturers have been unjustly dismissed, retired and even jailed over a mere accusation of teaching what they were not employed to teach; forty-nine lecturers of the University of Ilorin were dismissed just for participating in an ASUU nation-wide strike in 2001.

ASUU in 2020 embarked on strike prior to the worldwide COVID19 Pandemic provoked lockdown. The reason for the strike was the federal government imposition of the Integrated Personnel and Payroll Information System (IPPIS) on universities and all the federal government owned institutions (The Tide, 2020). ASUU saw this centralized payroll system as an infringement on the autonomy of the university and hence rejected it and rather insisted on the use of the University Transparency and Accountability Solution (UTAS). To that effect, ASUU called for a two weeks warning strike but the federal government refused to shift ground. Consequently, on the 23rd of March, 2020, ASUU declared an indefinite nationwide strike that lasted for nine months. Again, ASUU went on strike on the 14th February, 2022 because of the failure of the government to remove the IPPIS and failure to keep to other terms of agreement they reached with ASUU to call off the 2020 strike. Instead of fulfilling these agreements so as to resolve the strike, the Minister of Labour and Employment, Sen. Ngige on behalf of the government rather declared no-work, no-pay on the striking ASUU which made the strike to linger for seven months. As though that was not devastating enough, the minister went on to register two new university academic staff unions known as the Congress of Nigerian University Academics (CONUA) and National Association of Medical and Dental Academics (NAMDA). This was done to force ASUU to call off their strike instead of engaging them in a reasonable negotiation.

Pertaining to poor funding of the universities, studies have shown that the Nigerian universities are bedeviled by poor funding due to a general low budgetary allocation to education. For instance, IOM (2014) lamented that Nigeria has over the years failed abysmally to meet the United Nations' prescribed 26% budgetary allocation to education for developing nations. Similarly, Dimunah (2017) reported that Nigeria ranks lowest in budgetary allocation to education among other

African nations. This insufficient university funding is said to be responsible for lots of deficiencies and rot in the universities. Halidu (2015) has earlier established that underfunding of Nigerian universities has led to deteriorating educational infrastructures, shortage or total lack of physical facilities, resources such as textbooks, teaching materials, laboratory and library equipment, overcrowded classrooms and other problems associated with it. In addition to these problems, Igbinedion and Torupere (2019) averred that university underfunding is responsible for decreased motivation to work among university staff, the problem of brain drain, strikes, threats of strike and collapse of the general standard of university education in the country.

The report on the findings of Mahmood Yakubu led Committee on Needs Assessment of Nigerian Public Universities among other findings indicated poor funding of the university education. The report according to the Nation (2021) revealed that public universities are grossly underfunded and hence, seriously lacking in human and material resources. Ever since this report, ASUU has severally gone on strike over government's inability to ameliorate the problem of poor funding of university education. Government's response to this according to Odiagbe (2012) has always been that educational funding is not more important than that of any other sector of the country hence, recommends that universities should seek alternative sources of finance in order not to lean too much on government because the government is bedeviled by lack of funds too.

The inability of government to fund the universities does not seem to ASUU as really stemming from lack of funds in the government coffers rather, they believe it to stem from general lack of the will to develop public education and from misplacement of priorities. For instance, Awuzie (2009) stated that the problem with the Federal Government is not lack of funds, rather a clear case of misplacement of priority. This is so considering the way government officials squander the national treasury on frivolities. Mbaji (2017) confirms that there is lack of serious commitment by the government towards matters concerning the development and sustenance of university education. Albert (2015) asserted that while public universities are denied adequate funding, Nigerian political leaders are rather diverting the national funds to their private universities and if not

confronted now, Nigerians might be forced to turn to these elite private universities where they are charged very high tuition and fees that average Nigerians cannot afford. This same attitude by the government officials is what destroyed the lower educational levels (primary and secondary schools). The government abandoned this level of Nigerian educational system after subduing the Nigerian Union of Teachers (NUT) which is the trade union at this lower level of the Nigerian educational system. As a result, most parents now send their children to private-owned primary and secondary schools owned by the same elite class that starved the government-owned schools to death of funds. Only children from the poorest families now go to public primary and secondary schools. This situation is what ASUU is fighting tooth and nail to avoid, hence the endless conflict with the government (Iyayi, 2013).

The poor working conditions of Nigerian university academic staff is another issue of contention between ASUU and FGN. Okebukola (2010) reported that Nigerian university staff are suffering from serious poor conditions of services which include: low salary that most times delay in coming, delayed or denial of due promotion, unwarranted/unjust termination of appointments, victimization of staff, poor standard of living especially pertaining accommodation, transportation and health management, poor retirement benefits structure, over labored work force and tyrannical leadership approach of most Vice Chancellors and so on.

The issue of erosion of university autonomy, poor funding of universities and poor conditions of services of university staff could have been resolved to a large extent had the government implemented the recommendations of the Needs Assessment Committee. The committee recommended that an estimated amount of N1.3 trillion naira be injected to revitalize Nigerian public universities. In December 2013, the government agreed to release the fund to be paid in six installments, within the period of six years starting in 2013 with two hundred billion naira and two hundred and twenty billion naira in each of the remaining 5 years. After paying the first installment in 2013, the government reneged on the payment of the subsequent years. Moreover, the first installment that it release was wrongly done because instead of paying this money directly into the

coffers of ASUU, federal government rather paid it into NUC account and went further to use TETFund to construct and established 12 new universities instead of using the money for the revitalization of the old ones as recommended by the committee (Odoziobodo, 2015). This singular action infuriated ASUU members and put them in a conflict disposition against the government. Till date, these causes of conflict between ASUU and Federal government have continued to resonate. In other words, the ASUU-FGN conflict has not been resolved. There is therefore an urgent need for a more effective conflict resolution strategy to resolve the conflict permanently.

Conflict resolution may mean different things to different authors. Some prefer to manage a conflict while others may prefer a total termination of the conflict. For instance Kazimoto (2013) defined conflict resolution as the process of implementing strategies to limit the destructive effects of a conflict and increase its productive outcomes. To Adams (2019), conflict resolution involves moves initiated to put an end to a conflict. A cursory look at the two definitions will reveal that while the first definition has the conflict management outlook, the second definition takes the conflict termination viewpoint. Conflict resolution for this work can be defined as any attempt aimed at management or total termination of a conflict to minimize its negative impacts on the organizational objectives.

There are various kinds of conflict resolution strategies as recommended by different authors and bodies such as the Trade Unions Act of 1973 and the Trade Dispute Act of 1976. These conflict resolution strategies include: dialogue, mediation, conciliation, arbitration, adjudication and negotiation.

Dialogue is the first point of call in all the resolution strategies. It is a formal discussion in which the conflicting parties engage together in a bid to sort out their differences and come to terms. The ideas of most philosophers and theorists of different times in human history revolved around issues of conflict and conflict resolution. In others words, the concept of conflict resolution occupies an important place in the deliberations of both ancient and modern philosophers whose views have shaped discussions and understanding of the causes of conflicts and suitable conflict resolution

methods. For instance, Karl Marx (1848) is of the view that the class based economic structure of the society or social inequalities driven by capitalism and the class struggle associated with it is the primary cause of conflicts. To resolve conflicts according to the Marxist theorists, capitalism and every other agent of social inequality must be abolished. To Alan Fox (1966), Allan Flanders (1970) and Hugh Clegg (1975) in their pluralistic theory of trade conflict, conflict is caused by lack of formal system of collective bargaining, conciliation and arbitration as the means of establishing rules of engagements for the separate and competing interest groups. The best conflict resolution strategy therefore according to the pluralistic theorists is to uphold collective bargaining, conciliation and arbitration in making rules of engagement by the parties concerned.

The social contract theorists are another set of scholars that are vocal in their discussion of causes of conflict and conflict resolution strategies. Prominent among the social contract theorists are Epicurus, Machiavelli, Hugo Grotius, Baruch Spinoza, Samuel Pufendorf and most notably, Thomas Hobbes, John Locke, Jean-Jacques Rousseau, Immanuel Kant and John Rawls. These theorists believe that conflict arises when the rules or terms of an agreement is broken by any of the parties involved in the agreement. In other words, when a party fails to meet up with their obligations or infringes on the rights of another party, conflict will occur. Therefore agreement must be established in consideration of rights and obligations of parties involved in the agreement as a way to resolve a conflict and to forestall possible future conflicts among the parties, also each of the parties must endeavor to stick to the terms of agreement. The philosopher widely considered very elaborate in his discourse on conflict and conflict resolution in the civil society is John Locke (1632 -1704). John Locke's ideas of social contract took a more modern democratic approach in resolving conflicts.

The main tenets of the Locke's social contract are: Mutual Obligation between the people and the government, People's Right of Consent, People's Right to own Property and People's Right of Revolution against erring Government. On Mutual obligation between the people and the government, Locke posits that prior to the creation of the civil society, man lived in a state of nature. According to him, the state of nature is pre government and pre civil society, hence law and order

was absent. The need for law and order prompted men to move into the social contract. Locke posits two contracts, namely: Pactum Union is, which is the agreement to form a society and Pactum Subjection is which is agreement to form a government. By such pact/contract, the people and the government/ authorities incur mutual obligations to make the civil society more comfortable than the state of nature. It is the obligation of the people to submit to and obey the government and it is the obligation of the government to protect the people's right to life and of property ownership. To sustain the welfare of the people, Locke suggested that, both the government and the individuals must keep to their obligations. Thus a contract becomes void if either side reneges on its terms.

On the people's right of consent, Locke advocates for a type of government which must exist and govern by the people's consent. Locke averred that to form a civil society or to ordain a leader, the people must willingly consent to it. Hence, to govern a man, his consent must be sorted after. Anyone who uses force over another or tries to impose his decision on another arbitrarily puts himself into a state of war or conflict with another. This is because the victim of the forceful rule will fight to resist it. The consent doctrine of the Locke's social contract also entails that the government is expected to seek the opinion of the people in decision and policy making. When it becomes difficult for the government to reach the entire people one after the other to obtain their consents in decision making, the people's representatives such as union leaders become an easy channel for the government to draw the consent of the people concerned.

On the people's right to own property, Locke, posited that the right to own property in its wider sense refers to right to life, liberty, material belongings and dignity of labor. Everyman has the right to dispose of himself and his possessions as they may deem best. This right is inalienable because according to Locke it is a natural right, it is not created by society therefore, it can ipso facto not be limited by the society, except to the extent that it is necessary to give them effective protection through dispute resolution in cases of unlawful encroachment or unlawful possession. Also, it can only be limited by the obligation to respect the same right in others. The human property/possession includes human labor which may be physical labor or mental labor. Locke referred to it as right to

self-ownership. Locke claimed that labor puts a distinction between property possessed by the individual and the property shared by all men in common. To use another man's labor, the man must be duly consulted and compensated for it in form of wages, salaries, allowances and other favorable conditions of labor. Uncompensated labor may tantamount to slavery and violates the property rights of the man and may result to conflict. Locke notes that property rights are the center of most conflicts in the human society. Work place conflicts between employers and employees, employees and fellow employees or employers and the government or business competitors are all hinged on property and labor rights. Most times, workers embark on industrial strike action when they feel their conditions of services are not favorable. To avoid such conflicts, government and private employers alike, must pay their workers as and when due as well as ensure favorable working conditions of the workers.

On the people's right of revolution against erring government, Locke's social contract theory believes that sovereign power is derived from the people and the political authority is held in the form of a trust. In other words, power belongs to the people. The people are therefore naturally empowered to retrieve power from an erring government. By this, Locke not only opposed the divine rights of kings advocated by the Church of England, but also opposed the doctrine of absolute sovereignty advocated by his predecessor, Thomas Hobbes. According to Locke, the ruler is just another man who like all other men is prone to faults and making mistakes. Consequently, decision making is not to be left to the government alone because they can make mistakes or allow their human selfishness and emotions to becloud their sense of judgment and as such, make wrong decisions that can be detrimental to the public. Decisions therefore are reached through deliberations rather than the arbitrariness of the rulers otherwise the civil society will become unbearable for man. To John Locke, the reign of a government ought not to be more unbearable than the state of nature. Should this be the case, people would merely revert back to the state of nature by liquidating the government. That is to say If the sovereign repeatedly abuses his power or consistently fail on the

duty of guaranteeing the security of life, property and the liberty of the people, the people should oppose or rebel against him without fear of punishment or any form of victimization.

In extension of this tenet to work place situation, employees reserve the power to rebel against the employer by downing their tools to express their disenchantment against the employer who had failed in the duty of providing favorable conditions of services. Rebellion or industrial strike action is therefore a means of forcing constituted authority to live up to its responsibility/obligation in compliance with the dictates of a contract. It will be wrong therefore, for any authority, whether government or employer to criminalize rebellion or strike which resulted from the failure of the government or employer to live up to expectation. Rather, there should be a round table dialogue between the authority and the aggrieved parties to resolve the conflict as muscle flexing will only worsen the situation. Furthermore, whatever agreement reached during the deliberation must be kept by all parties involved, irrespective of their status to avoid a future reoccurrence of the conflict.

Locke's social contract is considered democratic because a government is established and operates on the people's consent, will and desire. Locke's Social contract is also said to have been one of the most important paradigms of Western philosophical and legal theory in helping to shape man's understanding of justice and social structures that promote peace (Adolph, 2020). Considering the postulations of the locks social contract theory, the researcher wonders if there are ways this theory can resolve the FGN-ASUU conflict.

The need to resolve the FGN-ASUU conflict has become more urgent than ever giving its devastating effects on the Nigerian university education. A study by Oyetakin, Alabi, and kayode, (2012) reveals that the conflict between federal government of Nigeria and ASUU have crippled academic activities of universities on several occasions and this has continued to disrupt the school calendar and academic excellence and fast paving way for mediocrity and academic backwardness. According to the study, there is hardly a full academic session that the crises did not result in loss of study periods, delayed students' graduation and economic wastage for students, parents and the country as a whole. Moreover, the strike periods leaves the university infrastructures and amenities

unattended to which results to decay of these structures. Most times, the university structures are vandalized and learning materials carted away by hoodlums. This situation exacerbates the gross lack of amenities, infrastructures, learning materials and teaching aids as reported by the Mahmood Yakubu led Committee on Needs Assessment of Nigerian Public Universities (The Nation, 2021). According to the report, all the universities visited by the committee lacks basic infrastructures and learning materials; laboratories and workshops equipment. As well consumables are either absent, inadequate or outdated; Kerosene stoves are being used as Bunsen burners in some university laboratories; some engineering workshops operate under zinc sheds and trees, and many science-based faculties are running what is referred to as “Dry Lab,” due to lack of reagents and tools to conduct real experiments. There is high shortage of hostel accommodations hence, the few available ones have overcrowded and congested rooms, overstretched lavatory and laundry facilities and its resultant poor sanitation. Furthermore, about 163 of the 701 physical uncompleted projects recorded by the committee had been abandoned. The report also shows serious lack in human resources - the universities are grossly understaffed, rely heavily on part-time and visiting lecturers, hence lecturers are over labored, a situation that decreases their efficiency. A report by Education For All (2014) shows that Nigeria has one of the worst lecturer-to-student ratios in the world, with the National Open University, the University of Abuja and Lagos State University having ratios of 1:363, 1:122 and 1:114, respectively. Also, the reports of the Needs Assessment Committee in 2013 as reported by The Nation (2021) found that the students-teachers ratio was 1:400 on the average as against the 1:40 recommended by NUC.

This statistics confirms the overworking condition of Nigerian lecturers especially when compared to university staff in other parts of the world. All these put together with lack of serious efforts by government to remedy the situation have put the Nigerian university in a serious jeopardy. Abiogu (2009) lamented that the functionality aspect of the Nigerian educational system has gone to the dogs and the survival of its *educands* and the larger society is on the brink of disaster. The cumulative consequence of all these is that Nigerian universities can no longer produce quality

graduates who can compete favorably in the global markets as they graduate with mere certificates without the requisite knowledge and skills that can impact on the economy. Corroborating the complaint, Anonaba (2015) asserted that most graduates in Nigeria are half-baked and unemployable in a formal service. This situation has dragged the dignity of Nigerian education to the mud. This ugly consequence was brought to the fore in 2005 when the first global university ranking was done by International Association of Universities (IAU). The ranking indicated that no Nigerian University was found among the list of best/first 1000 Universities in the world. The trend continued yearly till in 2019 when University of Ibadan took the 901st position. However, in the 2020 list, university of Ibadan lost the position and hence no Nigerian university made the list of global first 1000 universities.

At the continental level, a similar ranking for African nations in 2021 by Olario Pro (2021) showed that only seven Nigerian Universities out of the 174 universities registered by NUC were found on the list of first 100 Universities in Africa and none of the them is among the first thirty. The ranking of previous years also reveal a steady downward ranking of Nigerian universities year after year. Whereas other African countries have always strived to rise above their previous years' rankings, Nigeria, the once acclaimed giant of Africa and intellectual laboratory of Africa is lagging behind. Little wonder why then Nigerian universities are hardly considered by foreign students as a place of study and Nigerian youths are leaving the country in large numbers to other countries for studies, for greener pastures and for safety. The national image on Nigeria is seriously smeared by this situation as it demonstrates bad leadership and poor development on the country making the movement of the country towards global relevance delusional and unrealistic.

With particular reference to the South-East area of Nigeria, education in this area is regarded as the major means for upward social mobility. This accounts for the large number of universities in the area. People in the area are university undergraduates, graduates, civil servants or university staff who depends on government salaries for economic security. Based on this, any situation that adversely affects education will have a direct and proportionate effect on the lives of majority of the

people economically, socially, mentally and otherwise. In other words, the persistent conflict between ASUU and FGN with its resultant ASUU strikes has dealt a heavy blow on the people of this area due to their large dependence on education. During such strikes, youths come home from different parts of Nigeria where they are schooling, they become idle and mostly pose a serious burden to the parents couple with the fact that most parents in the area whose income comes from university activities are cut off from their source of livelihood.

As though the FGN-ASUU conflict has not done enough damage yet, the federal government led by Dr. Chris Ngige, the minister of labour in March, 2022 secured a court order by which a ‘no-work-no-pay’ condition was declared on ASUU during their last strike action. Based on this order, academic staff of universities was not paid salaries for a period of seven months that the strike lasted. This singular act led to lots of family crises among lecturers who depend solely on their salaries for livelihood. Many suffered starvation and some even died due to inability to afford medical treatments. This condition also heightened the problem of brain drain as large number of the academic staff of universities left the country in search of employment in other countries of the world. Furthermore, the minister of labour in a bid to break ASUU formally registered two new university unions, the Congress of Nigerian University Academics (CONUA) and National Association of Medical and Dental Academics (NAMDA).

This grandstanding approach by the government in their conflict with ASUU has rather made the end to the incessant conflict improbable since the problem is rather getting worst. All efforts to resolve the conflict in the past had but a short term effect as the conflict resurfaces after a little while. This has necessitated the need for application of more effective conflict resolution strategies to urgently bring the conflict to an end. It is against this background therefore, that the researcher’s interest was aroused to investigate the extent to which John Locke’s social contract can be applied in resolving the conflict between Federal government of Nigeria and ASUU.

Statement of the Problem

For over five decades now, the persistent conflicts between the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) and Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) characterized by regular ASUU strike have been a threat to the realization of the university education goals in Nigeria. ASUU has severally downed working tools over the government's infringement on academic freedom and university autonomy, poor funding of the university education and poor staff conditions of services. The most recent cases are the 2020 ASUU strike that lasted for nine months over the introduction of the Treasury Single Account and by the imposition of the Integrated Personnel and Payroll Information System (IPPIS) on universities staff and another strike that took place between February 14th and October 14, 2022 over the failure of the government to fulfill their agreements with ASUU which they entered into in the course of resolving their previous disputes. Rather than seek for amicable way of resolving the matter, the government rather declared 'no-work-no-pay'. ASUU members were not paid salaries for a period of seven months that the strike lasted. This led to lots of family crises among lecturers who depend solely on their salaries for livelihood. Many suffered starvation and some even died due to inability to afford medical treatment. This problem also heightened the problem of brain drain as large number of the academic staff of universities left the country in search of livelihood in other countries of the world.

Studies showed that Nigeria has over the years failed abysmally to meet the United Nations' prescribed 26% budgetary allocation to education for developing nations and ranks far below other countries on this area. This has resulted to lack of fund to finance educational activities in the universities, shortage and decay of infrastructures, lack of learning materials, teaching aids and social amenities within the universities. Furthermore, the conflict also hinges on calls by ASUU for a change of their conditions of services characterized by low and delayed salary, delayed or denial of due promotion, unjust termination of appointments, victimization of staff, over labor and general poor standard of living of universities academic staff. The cumulative consequences of this conflict are evident in the areas of regular strike action by ASUU, irregular academic calendar, loss of study

periods, decreased motivation to work among university staff; brain drain, face-off between management and staff, riots, threats of strike and general fall in standard of university education in the country. Reports have shown that over 80 months have been lost to university staff strikes between 1993 and 2022. Because of this, Nigeria university system can hardly produce quality graduates who can compete favorably in the global markets as they graduate with mere certificates without requisite skills and knowledge that could impact on the economy.

Furthermore, Nigerian Universities have continued to rank very low in both African and the global university annual ranking. Consequently, Nigerian universities are hardly considered by foreign students as a place of study rather, Nigerians are running to other countries far and near to study. The resultant effect of the whole saga on the economy of Nigeria is better left to the imagination. Although, every part of Nigeria has its fair share of this problem but the South-East seems more hit. This problem could as well escalate out of proportion if the ASUU-FGN conflict is not urgently resolved. Thus, the need to investigate the extent Locke's social contract can be applied in resolving the conflict.

However, the ways by which John Locke's Social Contract can resolve the conflict between ASUU and FGN is not yet certain due to paucity of research work in this area. Considering this gap in knowledge, the problem of this research work put in form of a question is: In what ways can John Locke's social contract resolve the conflict between the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) and the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU)?

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the extent to which Locke's social contract theory can resolve the incessant conflict between the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) and the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU). Specifically, the study determined:

1. The extent to which mutual obligation can resolve the conflict between FGN and ASUU.
2. The extent to which people's right of consent can resolve the conflict between FGN and ASUU.
3. The extent people's right to property ownership can resolve the conflict between FGN and ASUU.

4. The extent to which people's right of revolution can resolve the conflict between FGN and ASUU.

Significance of the Study

The study has both theoretical and practical significances. Theoretically, the study is significant as the findings brought to the fore the functionality of the postulations of John Locke's social contract theory on which the study anchored. The theory believe that conflict arise when the rules of an agreement is broken by any of the parties involved in the agreement. In other words, when a party fails to meet up with their obligations or infringes on the rights of another party, conflict ensues. The tenets of this theory entail that in a society, the government and the people incur mutual obligation to make the society more bearable than the state of nature. Hence, the government must be democratic or have limited sovereignty as it must be established and rule by the people's consent. It also entails that the people have some inalienable rights especially, right to life and property which include right to labor. In other words a laborer deserves his pay and good conditions of services. Finally, the people reserve the right to rebel and dethrone any government that reneges on its obligations. In relation to labor matters, the employer, be it the government or private body must always enter into written agreement with the employees to establish rules of engagement which all must adhere to in other to avoid conflicts. The relationship between this theory and the current study is that the theory helped in explaining the reason for the FGN and ASUU conflict and possible ways to resolve it.

On the practical relevance, the findings of the study are of immense benefit to the government, Academic Staff Union of Universities, university management, students and future researchers. Firstly, the findings of this study should be published in the national gazette or referenced in the FME research publications, also workshops or seminars can be organized using the findings of this study to show or demonstrate to the federal government of Nigeria through the ministry of education and ministry of labour and employment, educational administrators and other policy makers, the extent to which John Locke's theoretical principles of mutual obligation, people's

right of consent, people's right of property ownership and the people's right of revolution can resolve the Federal government versus ASUU conflict especially in handling matters bothering on university autonomy, academic freedom, condition of services of university academic staff and funding of universities, in resolving other conflicts that may occur in the universities and to forestall future reoccurrence of such conflicts.

The findings of this study are of immense benefit to ASUU in the sense that when published in the media and internet with its emphases on the issues of contention between the Union and the government, when the government eventually implement the recommendations proceeding from this study and fulfill their part of their agreement with ASUU, the worries of the union members will be taken care of leading to improved conditions of services for them, undisturbed university autonomy and academic freedom and effective funding of the universities.

When published and placed in the universities virtual and physical library, the benefit of the findings of this study to university management are in the area of the internal policy making and budget planning. The information and recommendations from the study are guiding principles to can help them formulate best policies as well as implement them in line with the principles of social contract so that conflicts will be drastically minimized and peace and progress instituted between the university management and the staff unions.

The findings of this study are also beneficial to university students. This is because the study proffered guides to resolving the conflict between FGN and ASUU which has severally led to closing down the schools and delaying students from graduation. When the conflict is resolved as a result of the publication of the findings and recommendations of this study, the era of strikes will be over and stable academic calendar will be guaranteed, students will enjoy peaceful atmosphere in learning and graduate as at when due having acquired the requisite skills and knowledge.

The findings of the research study are also beneficial to future researchers. When the results of this study are made public through seminars, workshop and library materials in both hard and soft

copies, it will contribute to the knowledge bank serving as guide and reference material for future researchers carrying out research on related issues.

Scope of the Study

Geographically, the scope of the study covered the Federal Ministry of Education Abuja, Federal Ministry of Labour and Employment and all the Federal universities in South East Nigeria. Content wise, the study focused on the application of Locke's social contract theory (LSCT) in the resolution of the incessant conflict between the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) and the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) and specifically on the extent to which mutual obligation can resolve the conflict between FGN and ASUU, on the extent to which people's right of consent can resolve the conflict between FGN and ASUU, the extent to which people's right of property ownership can resolve the conflict between FGN and ASUU and the extent to which people's right of revolution can resolve the conflict between FGN and ASUU.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent can mutual obligation resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU?
2. To what extent can people's right of consent resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU?
3. To what extent can people's right to own property resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU?
4. To what extent can people's right of revolution resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU?

Hypotheses

To further guide the study, four null hypotheses were generated and each was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent to which mutual obligation can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent to which people's right of consent can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU.

Ho₃: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent to which people's right to property can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU.

Ho₄: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent to which people's right of revolution can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

This chapter reviews related literature under the following headings: conceptual framework, theoretical framework, empirical studies and summary of literature reviewed.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Concept of:

University Education

Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN)

Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU)

Conflict

Conflict Resolution

John Locke's Social Contract

Theoretical Framework

John Locke Social Contract Theory (1890).

The Pluralistic Theory of Industrial Conflict (1970)

Marxist Theory of Industrial Conflict (1848)

Empirical Studies

Studies on:

Mutual obligation and conflict resolution

Right of consent and conflict resolution

Right of property ownership and conflict resolution

Right of revolution and conflict resolution

Summary of Literature Review

Conceptual Framework

Concept of University Education

The Nigerian university system falls under the tertiary education while the tertiary education is the third arm of the Nigerian educational system. The Nigerian educational system is organized under the 9-3-4 system which implies, 9 years of basic education, 3 years of senior secondary and 4 years of tertiary/ University education (Njoku, Njoku, Ugo-israel and Umealor, 2017). The tertiary education is therefore the highest level or final step of education in Nigeria. Tertiary education comprises of Universities, Colleges of Education, Polytechnics, Institutes of Technology, Science, Arts, or Sports, and Seminary schools (FRN 2013). The focus of this section of the study however is on the University education.

The university has been recognized as an Ivory Tower and center for excellence where knowledge, a 'public good', ideas and ideals are disseminated and acquired; future leaders are developed and high level technical human capacity that ensures economic growth and development are made through lecturing/ teaching, learning, research, internship, and practicum (Otonko, 2012 and Okerulo, 2010). The Nigerian university education system offers two levels of university degrees, namely: graduate and Post Graduate Degrees in different fields of studies and in different areas of specialization. Graduate degrees comprises of a four-year, five-year or six-year Bachelor's degree program. The number of years a graduate degree takes is determined by the course area. For instance, Social Sciences and Humanity related courses take minimum of four years, Engineering, Technology related courses, Pharmacy and Law lasts for at least five years with two semesters per session/year where as Medicine, Veterinary and Human anatomy degrees take 6 years (UNESCO, 2012). Level 2 Degree/ Post Graduate Degree includes Master's Degrees which takes about two years and Doctoral Degrees which comes after the completion of a Master's degree takes two to three years. Admission into the University for Undergraduate Studies requires a minimum of senior secondary School examination Certificate or General Certificate of Education (GCE) Ordinary Level with minimum of 6 Credits including English Language and Mathematics at a maximum of two sittings. This also includes a Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB) Entrance Examination score of 180 and above (IOM, 2014).

Historically, the first attempt on university education in Nigeria is traceable to the Elliot Commission of 1943, whose recommendations led to the creation of University College Ibadan (UCI) in 1948. Nevertheless, UCI was not a full-fledged university as it was an affiliate of the University of London. Based on this and other bottlenecks associated with the collage, Nigerian elites clamored for a full-fledged “African” university. Consequently, in a 1954 Economic Mission to Europe led by Azikiwe, the Premier of the Eastern Region the main recommendation of the mission was that a university should be established in the Eastern region of Nigeria. This led to the establishment of University of Nigeria, Nsukka on October 5, 1960 (Otonko 2012). According to Alabekee (2013), the Federal Government of Nigeria in April 1959 set up the Ashby’s Commission led by Sir Eric Ashby of Cambridge University, U.K. to ascertain the higher education needs of the country for the next two decades. The Ashby’s Commission gave their recommendations which included that a university be established in Lagos, the then capital territory and in each of the three regions of the country (North, East and West) and that the universities must have a national outlook with the students drawn from different regions of the country and that the universities must be autonomous, independent and free in the conduct of their affairs among other recommendations. It was based on these recommendations that three universities were created in 1962. They are, the Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria for the Northern Region, University of Ife (now Obafemi Awolowo University) for the Western Region, University of Lagos for the Capital territory. The Eastern Region had already got its University of Nigeria, Nsukka in 1960. These four universities together with the University College Ibadan which was accorded university status in 1963 and named as University of Ibadan (UI) and the University of Benin, Benin-city established in 1970 are regarded as the first-generation Universities (Ejiogu and Sule, 2012).

Consequent on the increasing number of students who needed University education in Nigeria, and the growing needs for scientific and technological developments, eight (8) more universities were established between 1970 and 1980. They are: University of Calabar, University of Ilorin, University of Jos, University of Maiduguri, University of Port Harcourt, Federal University of

Technology Owerri (FUTO), Ado Bayero University Kano and Usman Danfodio University Sokoto. These are referred to as the second generation universities. Between 1981 and 1999, ten (10) additional Universities were established to address the special areas of technological and agricultural demands. They are: the Federal Universities of Technology Yola, Akure and Minna; Federal Universities of Agriculture Abeokuta, Markurdi; University of Abuja, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi, University of Uyo, Micheal Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike and Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka. these are the third generation universities. The fourth generation universities are those established from year 2000 till date. These exclude their contemporary state universities, Nigerian open University and private universities in the country. In Nigeria today there are about 174 universities registered by NUC, of which 43 are federal universities, 52 state owned universities and 79 Private universities (NUC, 2020).

Administratively, the management of university in Nigeria is in two structures: the internal structure and the external structure. The internal management structure comprises of the Visitor who is usually the Head of State or the Head of Government that established the university (The President in case of Federal universities and the Governors in case of State universities); the Vice Chancellor (VC), who is the head of the university; the Governing Council, headed by the Chairman (Pro-Chancellor) responsible for goal setting, policy formulation, staff development, general discipline, budget approval and liaison activities with the government for the university; the Senate (headed by the VC with the Registrar as the Secretary) and finally, the university committees. (Adeniyi (2015)). The external structure speaks of the government management of the university through the Federal Ministry of Education (FME). The FME is the government body authorized to carry out the functions of formulating educational policies, collecting and collating data for purposes of educational planning and financing as well as harmonizing quality of education throughout the country (Olawale, 2020). FME carries out these functions through its fifteen (15) departments headed by directors who are also members of the staff of the ministry. FME also has parastatals through which it carries out its functions. Prominent among the parastatals is the National Universities Commission (NUC).

According to a report by Quality Assurance Agency (QAA) for higher education in Nigeria, NUC is responsible for the regulation and harmonization of university management in the country; ensuring the orderly advancement of university education; maintaining its high standard and to ensure its adequate funding. The NUC functions also include: accreditation and approval of courses and programs, maintenance of minimum academic standards, monitoring of universities, establishing guidelines for setting up of universities, monitoring of private universities and issuing appropriate sanctions to erring universities (QAA, 2019).

The major objectives of university education in Nigeria according to the Nigerian Policy on education document, is the provision of much needed manpower to fast-track the socio-economic development of the nation while the specific goals include: to contribute to national development through high level relevant manpower production; the development and inculcation of proper values for the survival of the individual and the society; to develop the intellectual capability of the individuals to appreciate their local and external environments; to ensure the acquisition of physical and mental skills to enable individuals to be self-reliant and useful to the society; to promote and encourage scholarship and community service; forging and cementing national unity and to promote national and international interaction and understanding (FRN, 2013). In a nutshell, Afolayan (2015) averred that the overall goal of Nigerian university education is to produce a community of citizens that are highly skilled and well prepared for the world of Work, Sustainable national development and global expertise competitiveness.

The history of Nigerian university education cannot be complete without mentioning the fact that the system has suffered a lot of setback which has made it difficult for Nigerian universities to carry out their expected functions nor to attain their set out goals. A study by Jaja (2013) revealed the rot in the higher education in Nigeria, especially the university system. According to the author, the university education in Nigeria is in a deep mess, wounded on every side and gasping for breath. This is as a result of regular crises and unhealthy conflicts of various dimensions and magnitude such as frequent strike actions by university staff, students riot, decaying infrastructures, insufficient

learning facilities due to surging population of students, lack of motivation to work, brain drain syndrome and so on. Most of these problems stem from chronic underfunding of the universities, neglect of the university staff and disregard for university autonomy by the Nigerian government. This situation has to a large extent eroded the standard of university education in the country. Efforts by the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) to ameliorate the situation have always resulted to conflict between ASUU and Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN).

Federal Government of Nigeria

The federal government of Nigeria (FGN) is the apex government body as well as the arm of the Nigerian government saddled with the responsibility of overseeing the government owned universities. Nigeria is an independent democratic West African country which shares boundaries with Benin Republic in the West, Chad and Cameroon in the East and Niger Republic in the North. According to IOM (2014) Nigeria comprises of over 350 distinct nationalities, tribes/ ethnic groups, languages and religions with Igbo, Hausa and Yoruba as the dominant tribes while Christianity and Islam are the dominant religions. These diversities have given rise to cultural complexities that have considerably influenced the people's behavior especially in their approach to education, conflict resolutions, government policies and administrations.

Administratively, Nigeria is organized in six geopolitical zones (North-East, North-West, North-Central, South-East, South-West and South-South) and three tiers of government, the Local Government Area, the state government and the Federal government as the apex government. Each of these tiers of government has their peculiar functions known as residual functions but some issues are collectively handled by the three tiers known as the concurrent functions (Egerue, 2019). Prominent among such issues collectively handled by the three tiers of government is education. Nevertheless, the Federal Government is authorized to control all the educational sectors, formulate policies and ensure quality control through the Federal Ministry of Education. The constitution also permits each tier of government to focus its responsibilities mainly on a particular sector of education. Hence, tertiary education is the main focus of Federal Government, the states are in

charge of secondary education and the local governments take care of primary and pre-primary education. In addition, the Federal Government is expected to support the state and local governments in counterpart funding for effective management and provision of quality education in the country (IOM, 2014).

The federal government of Nigeria carries out its educational duties through various ministries and parastatals. Prominent among these are the federal ministry of education (FME) and the federal ministry of labor and employment (FMLE). This is because these two ministries play important role in the provision and management of educational activities in the country. The two ministries are always involved in most committees on educational matters including labour disputes in the educational sector. The FME is the government body authorized to carry out the functions of formulating national policy on education, collecting and collating data for purposes of educational planning and financing as well as harmonizing quality of education throughout the country (Olawale, 2020). FME carries out these functions through its departments headed by directors who are also members of the staff of the ministry. One of such departments is the National University Commission (NUC), NUC is a Commission that coordinates and regulates university management on behalf of the federal government of Nigeria.

The ministry of Labour and employment plays a prominent role in the course of managing university education especially, in the area of staff union versus government labour disputes. The ministry is concerned with employee - employer's relationship with the Minister of Labour and Employment as its overall head and assisted by the Permanent Secretary. The minister is appointed by the President, while the Permanent Secretary is a career civil servant. Currently, the Federal Minister of Labour and Employment is Senator Dr. Chris Nwabueze Ngige and Festus Egwarewa Keyamo SAN as the Minister of State for Labour and Employment. The main arms of the Ministry of Labour are: Employment and Wages department, Inspectorate department and the Trade Union Services and Industrial Relations department. These departments formulate policies on trade union organizations as well as handle disputes and complaints, assist in worker's education and keeps

records on trade unions and their activities. That is because, the ministry is generally saddled with the responsibility of formulating policies on trade union organizations as well as handles trade disputes and complaints, assist in worker's education and keeps records on trade unions and their activities. More so, Firstly, it is of common knowledge that the Minister of Labour and Productivity by virtue of section 147 (1) (2) (3) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (As amended) is a member of the Federal Executive Council, by section 148 thereof, the duties the Minister is expected to performed are as assigned to him by the President. In the discharge of his functions, the interest of the government is the paramount consideration.

It is in keeping to these responsibilities that brought the ministry to the front line as a representative of the federal government in their negotiations with ASUU in the course of their conflict resolutions. The federal Minister of Labour and Employment, Sen. Chris Ngige, has therefore been a major mouth piece of the government in her dispute with ASUU so much so that his grandstanding disposition in defiance defense of the government on the matter has made the federal government versus ASUU dispute seem like Ngige versus ASUU dispute in recent times.

During the 2022 ASUU strike action that lasted for about eight months, it was Dr Chris Ngige, the minister of labour who in March, 2022 on behalf of the federal government secured a court order by which a 'no-work-no-pay' condition was declared on ASUU members in a bid to force them back to work. Based on this order, academic staff of universities was not paid salaries for a period of eight months that the strike lasted. This singular art led to lots of family crises among lecturers who depend solely on their salaries for livelihood. Many suffered starvation and some even died due to inability to afford medical treatments. This condition also heightened the problem of brain drain as large number of the academic staff of universities left the country in search of employment in other countries of the world. Furthermore, the minister of labour in a bid to break ASUU formally registered two new university unions, the Congress of Nigerian University Academics (CONUA) and National Association of Medical and Dental Academics (NAMDA). Furthermore, most conciliatory and negotiation teams set up in the course of ASUU versus FGN

conflict were constituted and headed by either the Minister of Education or the Minister of Labour and employment. They are also signatories to all the memoranda and written agreements the government entered into with ASUU yet Section 3 (1) and (3) of the Trade Disputes Act empowers the Minister to determine the extent to which a collective agreement will become binding and therefore justiciable between the parties thereof. This is the reason why the minister of labour and employment will always rise in defense of the government when the government reneges on the agreements, For instance, the Minister of Labour and Employment, Chris Ngige once made a statement the Federal Government does not have the funds to meet its obligations in the agreement signed with the unions because the country is broke (Ogunbodede, 2022).

The exercise of these powers and functions has several implications. As an agent of the government, how possible is it for the minister in the exercise of this powers or performance of his functions to be neutral where the government is a party bearing in mind that ‘he who pays the piper dictate the tunes? Is it right for one to be the arbiter in his own matter? This has always been a matter of concern to ASUU in their collective bargaining with the government.

Concept of Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU)

The Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) is a national trade union created in 1978 to succeed the defunct National Association of University Teachers (NAUT). It is a unifying umbrella for academic staff of universities in Nigeria. It has its branches in almost all universities in Nigeria, Federal, state and some private universities except in the military and some private universities (Suleiman, 2016). ASUU was basically established for the purpose of fighting for the interest and welfare of academic staff of universities in Nigeria and for the growth and development of the university education. Adeyeye (2021) described ASUU as a trade Union comprising of both temporal and permanent academic staff of universities in Nigeria seeking not only the socio-political and economic/welfare interest of its members within the framework of promoting the cause of university education in Nigeria, but the entire good of Nigerians and Nigeria at large. The main objective of ASUU therefore, is the promotion and protection of the welfare of her members.

According to Etadon (2018), the principal objectives of ASUU as specified in the Rule '2' of the 1978 constitution of ASUU as amended in 1984 include: to organize all academic staff who are qualified for membership, regulation of the relationship that exists or may arise between Academic Staff and Employers or among members; to establish and maintain a just and proper conditions of service for its members, establishment and maintenance of a high standard of Academic performance and professional practices; encouragement of the participation of its members in the affairs of the University system and of the Nation at large; provision of benefits and other assistance to its members, protection and advancement of the socio-economic and cultural interests of the nation and to pursue such other objectives that are lawful and are in consistence with the spirit and practice of trade unionism. Etadon (2018) further averred that the government of the union as stipulated by Rule 5(ix) is vested on four main entities namely, National Delegate Conference (NDC); National Executive Council (NEC); Zonal Committees and Local Branches/ chapters.

The administrative head of ASUU is the National President. However, the National Delegate Conference is the highest authority/ decision making body of ASUU followed by NEC. The NDC was initially held annually, but since 1984 it has been a biannual conference. However, the Conference may be held any other time as the NEC may decide or by a resolution of majority of the chapters. The conference is composed of the NEC and four delegates from each chapter of the union. The NEC comprises of the entire national executives, the immediate past national President and chapter delegates consisting of at least the chairman and the secretary of each university chapter. The NEC meets at least once in six months on dates and venues decided by the Council. However, an extra-ordinary meeting of the Council may be summoned at the request of at least eight members of the council. The council is presided over by the President or by the Vice-President in his absence. The National executives of the Union include the President, the Vice-President, the Treasurer, the General Secretary, the Internal Auditor and Financial Secretary. They are also called the Principal Officers of the Union and they are all elected except the General Secretary who is appointed by the NEC. The administration of the Union in-between National Delegates' Conference is vested on the

NEC. All principal officers of the Union with the exception of the General Secretary are elected to serve for a term of two years at a time, provided no person holds the same elected position for more than three consecutive terms (Rule 10).

Local branches/ chapters are the union organization in each of the member universities. The Local Branches are vested with the function of seeing to the proper organization of the Union at the grass roots, to represent and to follow the directives of the National delegates Conference and the National Executive Council of the Union in the conduct of its affairs. A Branch Executive Committee comprises of the Chairman, the Vice-Chairman, the Secretary, the Treasurer, the immediate past Chairman and five other members elected by the chapter meeting. A chapter is required to hold at least three general meetings every year. The chapter Executive is required to provide leadership at the local level and run the affairs of the Union in-between the General meetings (Rule 9). The Union's organization is assisted by the services of three trustees who are elected at a National Delegates conference. All the properties of the Union are vested in the Trustees jointly on trust for the Union (Rule 12).

Under Rule 17 of the constitution, the issue of strike is covered. According to the Constitution, members of the Union are not to take part in a strike or in any way withhold their services from their employers without the express approval of the National Executive Council. Consequently a strike or any other type of industrial action not authorized by the National Executive Council is deemed unofficial. However, in deciding whether or not to authorize any form of industrial action, the National Executive Council is guided by the advice of the Branches and the provisions of the law. The main sources of union funds are entrance fees, subscriptions, levies and proceeds of economic and social activities. The funds of the union are allocated on the basis of 40% and 60% to the local Branches and National body respectively. All fees including deductions from salaries under check-off system are paid in the first instance to the local Branches which in turn remit 60% of such to the National Union (Rule 16). Every chapter is made up of the members and the principal officers. The principal officers collect the monthly dues which is a percentage deducted

from the salaries of the members and remitted to the account of the chapter from which the chapter remits sixty percent (60%) to the ASUU national account and 40% is kept back for the running of the chapter. This administrative set up ensures transparent operation of the union finances as such the members are not left in the dark.

ASUU members are all academic staff of the university. Academic Staff of universities according to Okebukola (2010) are lecturers from graduate assistant cadre to professorial cadre. This set of staff play a tripartite role of teaching, research and administration (in the cases of heads of department, faculty deans, provost of schools, program coordinators, and so on). In other words, they play very essential role in the daily running of the universities. The overriding importance of these teaching staff of the university is well captured by Abiogu and Ugwuja (2007) in their assertion that the most important factor in education is the teacher, not technique, method or curriculum because the teacher translates all the other factors into meaningful learning experiences for the students. Hence, it would not be wrong to say that the academic staff of universities under the umbrella of ASUU deserves a place of honor in the national scheme of affairs. For this work, the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) is hence defined as a national trade union created for the purpose of fighting for the interest and welfare of academic staff of universities in Nigeria with all academic staff of the Nigerian universities as its members.

The activities of ASUU as a union are guided by a set of principles. The guiding principles of the union as outlined by Adeyeye (2021) are: integrity, transparency and accountability; Professionalism, objectivity and hard work; courage, sacrifice and total commitment; internal democracy, teamwork and group solidarity including Patriotism, anti-imperialism and working class solidarity. The dogged commitment of ASUU to these principles and the union's objectives has brought about serious acrimony and antagonism between the union and the federal Government. Since its creation, ASUU has been extensively vocal in their demands for improvement on the staff working condition of her members, proper funding of the universities for efficiency and maximum output as well as for the full academic freedom and autonomy of the universities. When their

demands are ignored by the government, ASUU usually use the instrument of strike to persuade the government to rise up to expectations. This strategy employed by ASUU has always been frowned at by the government. For instance, Olusegun (2014) reported that the first ASUU strike was embarked upon in 1988 during the military regime of General Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida in order to drive home their demand for fair wages and university autonomy. In response to the strike, president Babangida proscribed the union on 7th August 1988 and all its property was confiscated by the military. It was later unbanned in 1990. However, owing to another strike in 1992 the union was once again banned on the 23 August 1992. Over time, the adverse effects of this loggerhead between ASUU and the government began to tell on the university system in the form of falling standard of education. In a bid to resolve the conflict, the FGN invited ASUU to a round table discussion where an agreement was reached on 3rd September 1992 that touched several of the union's demands. Regrettably, the refusal of the federal government to fulfill the terms of the agreement has deepened and sustained the conflict between ASUU and FGN to date.

The Concept of Conflict

There is no general consensus on how to define the term conflict. However, Segun (2013) sees conflict to mean clash, contention, confrontation, a battle, struggle or quarrel. While Hocker and Wilmont (2011) defined it as a felt struggle between two or more interdependent parties over perceived and incompatible differences in beliefs, values, and goals, or over differences in desires for esteem and control. For the sake of this work, conflict can be defined as the disagreement between two or more parties (in this case, between ASUU and FGN) over certain issues (mostly University autonomy, university funding and staff conditions of services).

Conflict has remained an inevitable circumstance prevalent in any human society or organization, especially in employee-employer or government-labor relationships. Despite all efforts by any organization to avoid conflicts, it is still bound to occur because of the diverse and conflicting interests inherent in the organizations. However, organizations, systems or institutions that are made up of antagonistic interest groups are more volatile and susceptible to conflicts. The inevitability of

conflicts in human organizations has been emphasized by various authors. Segun (2013) averred that to work in an organization is to be in conflict and to take advantage of joint work requires conflict management. Segun (2013) further asserted that in every industrial and industrializing society, three major actors with their diverse interests exist. They are the employer, the employee (labour/trade union) and the government and interactions of these parties often lead to conflict due to their conflicting interests. The extent of the conflict and its effect on the organization is determined by the ability of the employer and employees to have a proper dialogue and reach certain agreements concerning the terms and conditions of employment; the extent to which the parties are willing and able to keep to the agreement and the extent to which the parties can compromise on their interests. This means that how a conflict is resolved will determine its impacts whether negative or positive. Hence, a conflict can impact positively or negatively based on its resolution. According to Shonk (2023), conflict may be destructive as it can hinder the attainment of organization's objective, it can as well lead to reasonable progress depending on how it is resolved. In other words, the extent of damage caused by a conflict is a function of the resolution technique applied by the parties involved. Shonk (2023) further averred that a properly resolved conflict does not only lead to innovation and change, but also makes change more acceptable and more desirable while unresolved conflict is destructive to any organization. The Nigerian university institutions have been badly battered as a result of the unresolved conflicts between ASUU and the Federal government of Nigeria.

The bases of the ASUU-FGN conflict are mostly issues on government decrees, policies and measures, most especially those ones that tends to erode university autonomy and academic freedom, sustain poor funding of the universities; institute poor conditions of staff services and the refusal of the government to fulfill its gentleman agreements with ASUU. In his analysis of the root causes of ASUU-FGN conflict, Bello and Isah (2016) averred that ASUU in their memorandum to the Presidential Commission on the Salary and Conditions of Service of University Staff known as the Cookey Commission of 1981 identified the following as major causes of its conflict with the government: (a) poor state of the universities, (b) erosion of University autonomy and academic

freedom, (c) poor conditions of service of university staff and (d) inadequate funding of Universities. Bello and Isah (2016) further stated that these issues were also reiterated in ASUU's memorandum to the Akambi Panel in 1986 as their major reasons for embarking on various strike actions. These issues are so poorly resolved that they have remained the bone of contention between the government and ASUU till date.

What is it about academic freedom and university autonomy and why are they serious bone of contention between ASUU and the FGN? Academic freedom simply means the freedom of academic staff to express their views on current issues prevalent in the society without any fear of victimization. University autonomy on the other hand has severally been defined as protection of the universities from interference by government officials in the day to day running of the institution especially on the issues related to the selection of students, the appointment and removal of academic staff including the vice-chancellors, the selection of heads of departments, faculty deans and program directors, the determination of content of university education and the control of the degree standard as well as the determination of size and the rate of growth of the institution (Babalola, Ayeni, Adedeji, Suleiman and Arikewuyo, (2016); Babalola and Emunemu, 2014) Academic freedom and university autonomy in Nigeria are legal standards and not mere frivolous claims. The National Policy on Education sections 8 (63) declares that the internal organization and administration of each university shall be its own responsibility. The internal organization and administration areas of academic freedom for the universities include: the selection of their students, except where the law prescribes otherwise; appointment of their staff; choosing what to teach; selection of the area of research; determination of the content of courses. It further stipulates that Government shall continue to respect this freedom as long as these areas are in consonance with national goals and objectives (FRN, 2013). In addition to this declaration, Fernando (2013) asserted that the September 1988 World University Service (WUS) in her 60th assembly approved the Lima Declaration on Academic Freedom and Autonomy of Institutions of Higher Education which exempts universities and other higher institutions from government regulations and control.

Based on the above assertions, each university is expected to have its own bylaws and regulations by which its activities are governed. Anonaba (2015) asserted that ASUU has insisted that university autonomy and academic freedom are indispensable for the advancement, transmission and application of knowledge and this informed their vocal and firm demand for autonomy and academic freedom. The government has however, always infringed upon the university autonomy and academic freedom, so to say by continuously imposing regulations on conditions of service and bureaucratic rules over the internal affairs of the universities. Igbogidi (2014) asserted that ASUU has through communiqués and press releases condemned the increasing interference of NUC, the Federal Ministry of Education, the cabinet office, the office of the President and JAMB, in the internal affairs of the Universities. In their response, the government has insisted on its right to control all affairs of the universities since they fund university staff salaries, infrastructure and most activities of the universities. Anonaba (2015) recorded that as far back as the year 1980, the then president of Nigeria, Alhaji Shehu Shagari at the University of Lagos convocation jettisoned academic freedom and university autonomy when he stated that the academicians who are paid out of public funds have no right of autonomy or freedom. In other words universities can only enjoy autonomy and the desired freedom when they attain financial independence.

The abuse of the University autonomy was intensified with the creation of the National Universities Commission (NUC) in 1962 amended in 1974 through Decree No. 1 of 1974. With the introduction of NUC, the government usurped the powers of the university Senate to assess the academic merit of the university lecturers and the content of the university programs, the power to dictate what to teach and the number of students to be admitted into the universities. Olaleye and Oyewole (2016) averred that since its creation, NUC has been responsible for quality assurance in the Nigerian universities through program regulations and establishment of minimum standards for universities. In corroboration Utile (2021) recounted that the appointment of the Vice-chancellors had hitherto been the sole responsibility of the Governing Councils of Universities but with the Decree No. 23, of 1975 when the Federal Government took over the regional universities, the power

to appoint and remove Vice-chancellors was transferred to the Head of State giving the president and the state governors the final say in federal universities and state universities respectively and ever since, the appointment of the vice-chancellor has become a political affair. Utile (2021) also asserted that it was the Decree 16 of 1985 and its amendment in 1988 that dismantled what was left of university autonomy by expanding the functions of NUC in Section 10 of the Decree by vesting on the commission the power to lay minimum standards for all universities and other institutions of higher learning in the federation and the accreditation of their degrees and academic awards. Hence, for any Nigerian university to commence an academic program or establish an academic unit, it must obtain the written approval of NUC. The role played by NUC in the university affairs is hence, a violation of university autonomy and academic freedom.

The establishment of Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB) by Decree No 20 of 1978 is another government action that eroded the university autonomy. JAMB is a body saddled with the function of conducting entrance examinations into the Nigerian universities. This body has since taken over the duty of the universities to select their students. Etega, Etega and Aforika (2020) stated that prior to the creation of JAMB, each university in Nigeria autonomously conducted their admission examination. The creation of JAMB brought about serious conflict in the university system until the federal government succumbed to the pressures by the Committee of Vice-Chancellors of Nigerian Universities and introduced the policy of Post-JAMB screening policy in 2005 through the then Minister of Education, Mrs. Chinwe Obaji. By this policy, tertiary institutions are mandated to screen candidates who scored 200 and above in JAMB. Only those that passed the screening test can be offered admission. Etega, Etega and Aforika (2020) observed that the post-UTME restored a little degree of the right of universities to select the students they admit. Nevertheless, Utile (2021) believed that with JAMB and the quota system of admission still in operation, university autonomy is not guaranteed.

Stressing further the circumstances of violation of the university autonomy and academic freedom by the government, Utile (2021) pointed out areas of government undue interference in

internal university affairs to include: arbitrary proscription of ASUU, unjust dismissal of Vice Chancellors and other university staff, unjust detention and retirement of lecturers, imposition of decisions on university staff, undue interference in the process of electing heads of department, faculty deans, program directors etc. Recently and prior to the worldwide COVID19 Pandemic provoked lockdown, ASSU on the 24th of March, 2020 embarked on a nationwide strike which lasted for nine months. Part of the reason for the strike was because of federal government imposition of the Integrated Personnel and Payroll Information System (IPPIS) on universities and all the federal government owned institutions (The Tide, 2020). ASUU saw this centralized payroll system as an infringement on the autonomy of the university and hence rejected it. In their response to this, the federal government contended that it has the express right to control all affairs of the universities since it funds university staff salaries, infrastructure and most activities of the universities. As a result, the issue of University autonomy and academic freedom has remained an unresolved source of conflict between ASUU and federal government.

The Issues pertaining to poor funding is a general problem affecting the entire education subsector. This stems from the poor attention paid to education. Abiogu and Enemuoh (2007) asserted that Nigerian leadership treats education sector as no man's land, where every old woman plants mushroom anyhow. The university system however is the worst hit in this neglect. Studies have shown that fund allocation to the federal and state universities in Nigeria is grossly inadequate and regressive (Okai & Elekwa, 2012). Poor funding of universities can be described as a situation in which financial allocation or money made available for the expenditure needs of the universities are insufficient or readily unavailable resulting from ineffective sources of revenue for the universities. Bamiro (2012) averred that there are three (3) main streams or sources of fund for university education in Nigeria. The first stream consists of government allocations, Education Trust Fund (ETF) and funds from other government agencies; the second stream is students' fees and levies while the third stream comprises of consultancy services, gifts and donations from philanthropists, grants in aids from rich countries, incomes from the university's business investments, endowments,

and any other financial source. In addition, the government has made it mandatory for all federal universities to generate 10% of their total yearly funds internally to augment whatever fund allocated to them (Bamiro, 2012). In order to meet up with this mandate, Nigerian universities engage in commercial ventures such as transportation, agriculture, manufacturing and processing, hotel services, ICT and cybercafé services, restaurants and so on (Bamiro, 2012).

Despite these sources and streams of income available to Nigerian universities, the universities still suffer lack of basic needs due to poor funding. The reasons are not farfetched. The Nigerian budgetary allocation to education per annum has nothing to write home about. IOM (2014) lamented that Nigeria has over the years failed abysmally to meet the United Nations' prescribed 26% budgetary allocation to education for developing nations. According to Ugar (2018) and Gambo and Fasanmi (2019), the Nigerian percentage budgetary allocation to education in 2008 was 13.0%, in 2009, it was reduced to 7.25%. It was further reduced to 4.85% in 2010. From 2011, there was a little increase to 6.16%, 8.20% in 2012, 8.55% in 2013 and 9.94% in 2014. There was another sharp fall in the allocation in 2015 to the tune of 7.74%, and a further fall in 2016 to 6.10%, 7.38% in 2017 and 7.03% in 2018. This record validate the fact that the Nigerian budgetary allocation to education has been irregular, very meager and persistently fall below the 26% prescribed by the United Nations for developing countries. A study by Dimunah (2017) revealed that Nigeria ranks lowest in this aspect among other African nations. According to the report, Nigeria with an average of 8.4% ranks least among 20 African countries in their annual budgetary allocation to education while Ghana, Cote d'Ivoire and Uganda ranked 1st, 2nd and 3rd with 31.0 %, 30.0% and 27.0% allocation respectively. This report corroborated an earlier study by UNESCO (2012) which revealed that while Nigeria spends a paltry average of 1.1% of its GDP/GNP on education, other countries like Ghana spend 3.6%, Kenya 6.2%, and Zimbabwe 9.5%. Little wonder why then Nigerians are migrating to these countries for education and staying back for greener pastures after studies. By so doing Nigeria loses her quality academia and manpower to such countries, a condition referred to as brain drain.

More so, it has been observed that universities are finding it difficult to access the ETF due to strict criteria for accessing such funds. Hence, over 200 billion naira is lying fallow in the coffers of ETF (Adesulu, 2014; Idoko, 2017). This means that the money is there but not utilized. Furthermore, money from school fees and students' levies is not enough because tuition fees in the federal universities are either nonexistent or very low even lower than that of some private nursery schools in Nigeria (Igbinedion & Torupere, 2019). This trend has lasted for so long because any attempt by the university to raise tuition fees has always led to violent rioting by the students. The other sources of fund are either not regular in coming or scarcely available and so undependable. Private individuals find it difficult to partake in funding of the universities, an attitude emanation from the ideology of the civil society that knowledge is a public good and therefore, provision of education and scholarship is the responsibility of the government (Udoh, 2012). By implication, funding of universities is government duty. Obviously, this mentality seems erroneous as it has not helped the society, the evidence of which lies on the fact that Nigerian universities are suffering from gross underfunding, a situation with a lot of adverse consequences on educational development in the country.

It has been established that underfunding of Nigerian universities has led to deteriorating, shortage or total lack of physical facilities, resources such as textbooks, teaching and learning materials, laboratory and library equipment, overcrowded classrooms and other problems associated with it. Also university underfunding is responsible for decreased motivation to work, brain drain, face-off between management and staff, strikes and threats of strike and total collapse of the general standard of university education in the country (Faniran and Akintayo, 2012; Halidu, 2015). Definitely, this situation is a disaster for the university staff and students as well as for the parents and the country at large. In his study, Halidu (2015) projected the effects of poor funding of the universities to include limited laboratory/practical classes, field trips, attendance of academic conferences, shortage of chemicals and basic laboratory equipments, freezing of new appointments, virtual embargo on study fellowships, research grants, among others, too narrow strategic profiles

and core areas, loss of variety in research and teaching, loss of autonomy due to third party funding, just to mention but a few. Arikewuyo (2010) lamented that one of the major effects of poor funding of the universities is conflict among the major stakeholders stating that the issues of funding and its associating lack of facilities have been the cause of frictions between ASUU and the government in almost all instances. In a bid to end this friction, the FGN in an agreement with ASUU promised to allocate a minimum of 26 percent of the annual budgets to education in respect to the United Nation's prescription. However, the government has ever since failed to keep to the agreement (Arikewuyo, 2010). This has sustained the conflict between federal government of Nigeria and the **Academic Staff Union of Universities.**

The issue of poor conditions of university staff services is another issue of contention between ASUU and FGN. According to ASUU (2017), the conditions of services in Nigerian universities have very little or nothing to be desired Abubakar, Muhammad and Abdulsalam (2019) averred that prior to the military intervention in the Nigerian polity in 1966, the university staff was among the highest paid worker in Nigeria and hence, occupied a relatively high position over most of their counterparts in other offices in the civil service. As at 1960s, a university professor earned £3,000 per annum which is higher than that of a Federal Minister's salary of £2,700 and a Permanent Secretary paid between £2,500 and £2,940. During this time, an assistant lecturer was paid £950, while his counterparts in the federal civil service were offered £720. Furthermore, the salaries of Assistant Lecturers was higher than both a Sub-Lieutenant and Lieutenant; a Lecturer II more than a Lieutenant Colonel, a Reader/Associate Professor more than a Colonel and Brigadier.

At their emergence into Nigerian politics in 1966, the military quickly reviewed the civil service salary structures and conditions of services which were, of course done in a way to favor the military and at the expense of other sectors especially the university sub-sector. An Army Captain was now being paid more than the university Lecturer I, a Lieutenant-Colonel more than Senior Lecturer, a Colonel more than a Reader/Associate Professor; an army Brigadier, whose salary in 1966 had been lower than that of a Reader/Associate Professor, now earned more than even a full

Professor. The salaries of both the Lieutenant General and full General rose far above that of a Vice Chancellor (Abubakar, Muhammad & Abdulsalam, 2019). This marked the genesis of the fall of academia from the envious height of the social class ladder and became a source of conflict between the university staff unions and the government. Abubakar, Muhammad and Abdulsalam (2019) further revealed that industrial strike actions undertaken by ASUU in 1988 and afterwards are rooted on struggle for class survival. For instance, one major demand of the union in 1988 was the restoration of the 20% differential in the University Salary Structure (USS) initially enjoyed by university staff but was eroded by the military administrations.

The industrial strike actions by ASUU over poor conditions of services of their members yielded very little. This is because, rather than restoring the university staff salary to statuesque, the university staff conditions of service has over the years, experienced further downward trend. As a result, the conditions of services of Nigerian universities staff has very little or nothing to be desired. This poor condition of services has been evident in the areas of low salary which most times still delays in coming, delayed or denial of due promotions, unwarranted/ unjust termination of staff appointments, victimization of staff, poor standard of living especially pertaining accommodation, transportation and health management, poor retirement benefits structure and so on (Okebukola, 2010). It is a difficult thing for any man to function effectively under unsatisfying working conditions even a machine cannot do that. It is a mark of tyranny to make a man to work under such conditions. In a democratic society like Nigeria especially among the well-read and elites, any form of autocratic administration is vehemently resisted because such violates fundamental human rights, justice, industrial peace and harmony and leads to rebellion and conflict against such undemocratic regime.

Furthermore, Nigerian university workforce seems to be over labored. FME (2016) revealed that there was a total of 18, 328 academic staff to teach 433,871 students. This is far above the NUC prescription for university academic staffing which shows that a total of 33,951 lecturers are supposed to be employed given that number of students. Based on this, There is an academic staff

shortfall of 15,718 (46%) in Nigerian universities in year 2016. In a more recent report Nigeria has one of the worst lecturer-to-student ratios in the world, with the National Open University, the University of Abuja and Lagos State University having ratios of 1:363, 1:122 and 1:114, respectively (EFA, 2019). This statistics confirms the overworking condition of Nigerian lecturers especially when compared to university staffs in other parts of the world. For instance, the staff-to-student ratio in Harvard University is 1:4; Massachusetts Institute of Technology has 1:9 ratio while the University of Cambridge has 1:3 (IOM, 2014). The resultant effects of these poor working conditions are endless conflicts. This is because attempts by the academic staff union of universities to bring in the government to ameliorate these problems have always brought them to lock horns with the federal government.

Nigerian government of various regimes has applied different measures towards the resolution of the federal government versus ASUU conflicts. These attempts include the use of force (such as proscription of the union, harassment of its members and so on) as well as the setting up of various panels of enquiries and reconciliatory committees. These use of arbitrary force yielded no positive result, the government resorted to dialogue by which it entered into a written agreement with ASUU in June 30, 2009. Okebukola (2010) reiterated government's acknowledgement in the agreement that Federal Government of Nigeria and ASUU needed a comprehensive agreement to address the decay and rot in the system and the issue of the brain drain, twin factors that had noticeably began to rob the Nigerian Universities of their former glory as centers of excellence and of high rating amongst the community of Universities in the world. Awuzie (2009) averred that in the agreement, the government stated its commitment and procedures to meet the demands of ASUU pertaining university autonomy and academic freedom, adequate funding and better conditions of services. Awuzie (2009) further noted that if properly implemented, the Agreement would change the face and character of the Nigerian universities and would reasonably resolve the perennial conflict between ASUU and federal government. This opinion stems from the fact that all the issues that stand as the basis of the conflict were taken care of in the agreement. However, it is quite

disheartening to note that the cause of conflict in the recent past has been the failure of the Federal Government to fulfill her own part of the agreement. Out of the nine issues agreed upon, FGN has been able to implement only two, which are: - upward review of the retirement age of Professors from 65 to 70 years and reinstatement of unjustly dissolved university councils. Other issues bothering on university autonomy, academic freedom, funding and staff condition of services are totally neglected thereby deepening and sustaining the conflict between ASUU and federal government of Nigeria.

Concept of Conflict Resolution

Conflict resolution may mean different things to different authors. Some prefer to manage a conflict while others may prefer a total termination of the conflict. For instance Kazimoto (2013) defined conflict resolution as the process of implementing strategies to limit the destructive effects of a conflict and increase its productive outcomes. To Adams (2019), conflict resolution involves moves initiated to put an end to a conflict. A cursory look at the two definitions will reveal that while the first definition has the conflict management outlook, the second definition takes the conflict termination viewpoint. Termination of conflict here connotes the idea that the conflicting parties are mutually satisfied with the resolution but obviously and according to Segun (2013), hardly can conflicts actually be resolved to the mutual contentment of the conflicting parties except on the ground of compromise where each of the parties let go of some of their conflicting interests for the sake of peace. In another view, Shonk (2023) refer conflict resolution to the resolution of underlying disagreements in interest in order to create room for mutual acceptance of each party's existence. This definition puts into consideration the cause of conflict which is incompatible interests or disregard for the existence of the other party's interests. In an earlier publication and similar opinion Kelman (2010) defined conflict resolution as any process that yields an agreement that reconciles the interests of conflicting parties to the extent that their respective power positions enable them to prevail. In other words, the terms of their agreement are heavily determined by the power they can bring to bear in the negotiations. This implies that, for different parties to coexist peacefully, there

must be contract or agreement that specifies the terms or conditions of coexistence. As soon as the contract is breached by any of the parties, conflict may arise. Conflict resolution can also be referred to as dispute resolution, dispute management or conflict management. Conflict resolution for this work can be defined as any attempt aimed at management or total termination of a conflict to minimize its negative impacts on the organizational objectives.

It has been stated earlier that conflict is inevitable wherever there is human interaction and contact and that conflicts can be destructive or productive depending on how they are resolved. Conflict resolution therefore is necessitated by the fact that conflicts should not be left unresolved if the goals of an organization must be attained. There are various kinds of conflict resolution strategies involving industrial disputes as recommended by different authors and bodies such as the Trade Unions Act of 1973 and the Trade Dispute Act of 1976. These are laws enacted in Nigeria that make provisions for conflict resolution regarding labor relations in the workplace or trade dispute. Under Section 51 of the Trade Unions Act (1973), Trade dispute is defined as any dispute between employers and workers or between workers and workers or workers unions and employers which is connected with employment or non-employment or conditions of work of any person or in a place of work. There are also alternative conflict resolution strategies which are outside legal litigations. Generally, conflict resolution strategies include: dialogue, mediation, conciliation, arbitration, adjudication and negotiation.

Dialogue is the first point of call in all the resolution strategies. It is a formal discussion in which the conflicting parties engage together in a bid to sort out their differences and come to terms. The beauty of dialogue is that it frees the mind of grudges and bitterness and makes it easy to bury the hatchet and settle the conflict. In other words, it sheds light on the root cause of the conflict and possible ways of resolving it. When dialogue and other alternative conflict resolution strategies fail to resolve an industrial dispute, the parties may take the matter to the national industrial court which has the final say in any conflict resolution process involving labor matters in the country. According to Coker (2011), this court serves as the final arbiter in industrial dispute. Virtually all the above

conflict resolution strategies have in one time or the other been employed by the federal government and ASUU in a bid to give their dispute a permanent resolution. According to Ikegbu and Ushie (2017) collective bargaining and joint consultation involving dialogues, negotiation, mediation and arbitration have been the mostly used conflict resolution strategy in the conflict between the Federal Government of Nigeria and ASUU but all to no avail.

The concept of conflict resolution occupies an important place in the deliberations of both ancient and modern philosophers whose views have shaped discussions and understanding of the causes of conflicts and conflict resolution methods. For instance, Karl Marx (1848) is of the view that the class based economic structure of the society or social inequalities driven by capitalism and the class struggle associated with it is the primary cause of conflicts. To resolve conflicts according to the Marxist theorists, capitalism and every other agent of social inequality must be abolished. To Alan Fox (1966), Allan Flanders (1970) and Hugh Clegg (1975) in their pluralistic theory of trade conflict, conflict is caused by lack of formal system of collective bargaining, conciliation and arbitration as the means of establishing rules of engagements for the separate and competing interest groups. The best conflict resolution strategy therefore according to the pluralistic theorists is to uphold collective bargaining, conciliation and arbitration in making rules of engagement by the parties concerned. The social contract theorists are another set of scholars that are vocal in their discussion of causes of conflict and conflict resolution strategies. The idea of social contract originated from the works of these theorists. Prominent among the social contract theorists are Epicurus, Machiavelli, Hugo Grotius, Baruch Spinoza, Samuel Pufendorf and most notably, Thomas Hobbes, John Locke, Jean-Jacques Rousseau, Immanuel Kant and John Rawls. Although not all these scholars used the term social contract, some of them rather used such terms as covenants, pacts or compacts. However, they all opted towards the same fundamental endeavor to explain the origins of mutual obligations, rights and civil society but in diverse approaches. There are different versions of the social contract theory as there are various social contract theorists. The philosopher widely considered very elaborate in his discourse on social contract as a conflict resolution strategy in the civil society is John Locke (1632 -

1704). In other words, John Locke's ideas of social contract took a more modern democratic approach in resolving conflicts. Hence, the focus of this research is on the social contract theory according to John Locke.

About John Locke

John Locke (1632 -1704) was a British philosopher, an Oxford academic, a physician and a medical researcher. According to Lowe (2018) Locke was the greatest and most influential English philosopher, whose thought became the foundation both for the Classical Empiricism and for Liberal Democracy. He was born to Mr. John and Agnes Keene Locke in August 29, 1632 at Wrington, Somersetshire London, a city 12 miles away from Bristol and grew up in the nearby town of Pensford around 1647. He existed during one of the most remarkable periods in political and intellectual history of Great Britain in which conflicts between the Crown and the Parliament which overlapped with religious conflicts amongst Catholics, Protestants and Anglicans that metamorphosed into civil war in the 1640s. His father, a lawyer, served as a captain in the cavalry of the parliamentarians (Stuart, 2015).

At age 14, Lock was enrolled study in the prestigious Westminster School in London where he was exposed to studies in Latin, Greek, Hebrew, Arabic, mathematics, and geography. At age 20 he moved to Christ Church, Oxford in 1652 where he bagged his Bachelor of Arts (B.A.) in February 1656 and later his Master of Arts (M.A.) in June 1658 and also obtained his bachelor of medicine in February 1675. At that time, Westminster school was the most important English school. Likewise, Christ Church was the most important Oxford College. It was his friend, Richard Lower that introduced Locke into medicine and experimental philosophy which earned him membership into the Royal Society where he met and worked with such noted scientists and thinkers as Thomas Willis, Robert Boyle, Robert Hooke and many others. In addition to his services as a physician, Locke was the Secretary to the Lords Proprietor of Carolina and one time Secretary of the Board of Trade and Plantations hence, the official in charge of collecting information about trade and colonies for the British government. His appointments to these positions were as a result of his family background

and his flair for politics which brought him into contact with the leading Whig Politician, Lord Ashley by whose influence Locke secured successions of official appointments with the political and scientific circles of London. His closeness to the government shaped his perception of the government as being authoritarian, hence in his writings, he opposed authoritarianism and absolute/unlimited sovereignty at individual and institutional level (government or the church). This opposition to authoritarianism and absolute/ unlimited sovereignty earned him the title of “Father of Liberalism”. Sequel to his stand against absolute sovereignty, he was suspected of involving in the Rye House Plot In 1683, which was a plot to assassinate King Charles II of England and his brother, James, the Duke of York. Hence, Locke fled to the Netherlands where he was on exile from 1683 till 1689 when he returned to England.

Locke is regarded as one of the most influential Enlightenment thinkers because his writings influenced many British and Scottish Enlightenment thinkers including the likes of Voltaire and Rousseau as well as the American revolutionaries. His contributions to classical republicanism and liberal theory are reflected in the United States Declaration of Independence. Locke is also popular for his Philosophy of Mind - theory of *Tabula Rasa* in which he opined that at birth, the human’s mind is like a *tabula rasa*, that is a ‘clean/ empty slate’ on which no knowledge can be found but with time and experiences, knowledge is gathered to fill the empty slate. That is to say that he believes that man is born without innate capabilities but acquires it over time through learning and experiences.

Locke wrote quite a number of works that cut across various facets of epistemology, this include: *Two Treatises of Government*, *Letters Concerning Toleration*, *Essay concerning Human Understanding*, the *Reasonableness of Christianity*, *Essays on the Law of Nature* and *Some Thoughts Concerning Education* (Locke, 2015). His book, *The Two Treatises of Government* is divided into two portions, *The First Treatise* and *The Second Treatise*. In *The First Treatise*, Locke took his time to refute Sir Robert Filmer’s write up called *Patriarcha* in which Robert Filmer argued that civil society and political power was founded on a divinely sanctioned patriarchalism, in other words,

political authority originates from religious source referred to as the Divine Right of Kings and so absolute and unlimited. This was a prevalent belief and theory in the seventeenth-century England. Locke contradicted this theory by saying that political power comes from the people and belongs to the people, hence it should be limited to the peoples interest and aspirations. *The Second Treatise* also titled *An Essay Concerning the True Original Extent and End of Civil Government* focuses on the theory of civil society based on natural rights and social contract theory. Locke is thus a major contributor in the propagation and development of the social contract theory. He died on October 28 in the year 1704 and was buried in the churchyard of the village of Laver, East of Hallow in Essex, England where he had lived in the household of Sir Francis Masham 1691 till his death. Locke was never married nor had children.

John Locke's Social Contract

John Lock's social contract theory is presented in the work, *Second Treatise of Government* in the year 1890. In discussions concerning social contract, Locke treated issues like: the state of nature, types of human rights, reasons for abandoning the state of nature to create civil societies, type of government and government obligations. In summary, the main tenets of the Locke's social contract are:

- 1) Mutual obligation between the people and the government,
- 2) The people's right of consent,
- 3) The people's right to own property
- 4) The people's right of revolution against erring government.

On Mutual obligation between the people and the government, Locke posits that prior to the creation of the civil society, man lived in a state of nature. According to him, the state of nature is pre government and pre civil society, a state in which all men were naturally in and to him, that is, a state of perfect freedom where all men were free to order their own actions, and dispose of their possessions and persons as they think fit within the bounds of the law of nature, without asking leave or depending upon the will of any other man (Locke,1690). However, the major challenge of the

state of nature according to Locke is the absence of centralized and well coordinated law enforcement agents and absence of impartial judge. All men were both judges and law enforcers in their own cases, a situation that made the state of war or conflict inevitable. As a result, the fundamental of man which are rights to life, liberty, health and possessions are not guaranteed in the state of nature. This necessitated the need to abandon the state of nature to create a civil society. To achieve this, men moved into the social contract. Locke posits two contracts, namely: Pactum Unionis, which is the agreement to form a society and Pactum Subjectionis which is agreement to form a government. The former pact binds men together into a body politic (civil society/ Union), whereas the latter is made between the people (as a society/ Union) and the government. The main reasons for abandoning the state of nature to create civil societies therefore is for the protection and preservation of the rights to life, liberty and possessions of the people. He further posits that the state of nature should not be more bearable than the civil society and should this be the case, people would merely revert back to the state of nature. Therefore, both the people and the authorities have a mutual obligation to make the civil society more comfortable than the state of nature.

The above entails that in a civil society, obligation is incurred by both the leaders and the led as a result of membership of a civil society. It is the obligation of the people to submit to and obey the government and it is the obligation of the government to protect the people's right to life and of property ownership. To sustain the welfare of the people, Locke suggested that, both the government and the individuals must keep to their obligations and avoid renegeing on their terms of agreement. Sequel to this, the importance of keeping agreement for an effective social contract cannot be over emphasized. When the rights of the people are denied them or the people's liberty are restricted or their security is threatened, the government has failed and hence renegeed on the terms of the agreement and thus releases the people from their obligations and loyalty. In that case, the people will react against the government to show their disappointment. The failure of the government according to Locke, empowers the people to revolt and rebel against the government. This is so because, as stipulated by Locke, a contract becomes void if either side renegees on its terms. If the

government is able to keep her agreement with the people, the people will have no reason to rebel against it. In extension to labor or work place administration, workers go on strike when the employers fail to keep to the agreed terms and conditions of service.

On the people's right of consent, Locke advocates for constitutionally limited government or limited sovereignty which must exist by the peoples consent. Locke averred that to form a civil society or to ordain a leader, the people must willingly consent to it. Hence, to govern a man, his consent must be sorted after. Similarly, to enjoy another man's property or estate, his consent must be obtained and so on. As averred by Locke, men being by nature, all free, equal and independent, no one can be put out of his Estate, and subjected to the Political Power of another, without his own consent (Locke 1890). Anyone who uses force over another or tries to impose his decision on another arbitrarily puts himself into a state of war or conflict with another. This is because the victim of the forceful rule will fight to resist it. There are two types of consent as put forward by John Locke, namely - explicit consent and Implicit/ tacit consent. Explicit consent is when someone says "I do" or "I agree" in writing or verbally to a government while implicit or tacit consent is supposedly and reasonably inferred or deduced from a person's behavior that the person do actually consent. According to Locke (1890), an individual gives his tacit consent to obey the laws of a government just by owning property that is under the government's jurisdiction or barely travelling freely on the Highway. It means that every man, that hath any possessions, or enjoyment, of any part of the dominions of any government, doth thereby give his tacit consent. Tacit consent, then, depends on the subject's acceptance of the protections and services of the government. While explicit consent is consent by action, implicit or tacit consent is consent by inaction. Whether by tacit consent or explicit consent, the consent doctrine of the Locke's social contract entails that the government at all times and in every situation are expected to seek the opinion of the people in decision and policy making. Government officials must hence, avoid imposition of decisions and policies on the people as that will mean erosion of the people's rights. Although it will be a difficult task for the government to reach the entire people one after the other to obtain their consents in

decision making, the availability of unions and the union leaders provides an easy channel for the government to draw the consent of the people concerned.

On the people's right to own property, Locke, posited that the right to own property in its wider sense refers to right to life, dignity of labor, liberty and material belongings. Everyman has the right to dispose of himself and his possessions as they may deem best. This right is inalienable because according to Locke it is a natural right, it is not created by society therefore, it can ipso facto not be limited by the society, except to the extent that is necessary to give them effective protection through dispute resolution in cases of unlawful encroachment or unlawful possession. Also, it can only be limited by the obligation to respect the same right in others. In other words, the human right to own property cannot be limited except with the consent of its possessors. The human property/possession includes human labor which may be physical labor or mental labor. Locke referred to it as right to self ownership. Locke claimed that labor puts a distinction between property possessed by the individual and the property shared by all men in common. Labor is the unquestionable property of the laborer. To use another man's labor, the man must be duly compensated for it in form of wages, salaries, allowances and other favorable conditions of labor. Uncompensated labor may tantamount to slavery. Locke opined, to subject a man to slavery or for a man to submit himself to slavery violates the property rights of the man.

By nature, labor is intrinsically unpleasant. It is undertaken only in expectation of the dividend of the value one creates by it. It would be unjust therefore to thwart that expectation. As a matter of fact, any attempt to thwart the dividend expectation of a laborer always result to a conflict. In particular, Locke notes that property rights are the center of most controversies in the human society. Work place conflicts between employers and employees, employees and fellow employees or employers and the government or business competitors are all hinged on property and labor rights. It is the duty of the government and employers to avoid poor conditions of services to avoid such conflicts and to resolve them when they arise. Locke in his social contract theory averred that it is mainly for the protection of property that men enter into agreements or contracts to form a

government. The failure of a government to protect the people's right of property empowers the people to rebel against the government. This is evident in labor related matters. Most times, workers embark on industrial strike action when they feel their conditions of services are not favorable. To avoid such conflicts, government and private employers alike, must pay their workers as and when due. Other benefits and allowances accruable to the workers must be given to them.

On the people's right of revolution against erring government, Locke's social contract theory advocated for limited sovereignty unlike Hobbes' version of the social contract theory. It is a limited sovereignty in the sense that its power is derived from the people and the authority is held in the form of a trust. In other words, power belongs to the people. Apart from that, sovereignty is also limited by natural laws and property rights and empowers the people to retain a right to revolt. Therefore, the people have the right to overthrow the government, which goes against the will of the people or against the natural laws. In other words, if whosoever in authority exceeds the power given him by the law or the people, such a government has acted arbitrarily and tyrannically and hence may be opposed by the people and forfeit its powers just as any other man who by force invades the right of another. By this, Locke not only opposed the divine rights of kings advocated by the Church of England, but also opposed the doctrine of absolute sovereignty advocated by his predecessor, Thomas Hobbes. According to Locke, the ruler is just another man who, like all other men is prone to faults and making mistakes. Consequently, decision making is not to be left to the government alone because they can make mistakes or allowed their human selfishness and emotions to becloud their sense of judgment and as such, make wrong decisions that can be detrimental to the public. Decisions therefore are reached through deliberations rather than the arbitrariness of the rulers otherwise the civil society will become unbearable for man. To John Locke, the state of nature is a much more peaceful state of existence, and thus the reign of a government ought not to be more unbearable than the state of nature. Should this be the case, people would merely revert back to the state of nature by liquidating the government. Thus, the sovereign's powers must be limited to the pursuit of the greater good of all. That is to say If the sovereign repeatedly abuses his power or

consistently fail on the duty of guaranteeing the security of life, property and the liberty of the people, the people should oppose or rebel against him without fear of punishment or any form of victimization.

In extension to work place situation, employees reserve the power to rebel against the employer by downing their tools to express their disenchantment against the employer who had failed in the duty of providing favorable conditions of services. Adewole (2014) agreed with Locke by stating that the phenomenon of political rebellion and cases of industrial strike actions resulted from frustration among citizens and workers in a political/ industrialized society. The author further averred that rebellion or industrial strike is an attempt at contract vitiation by citizens who are conscious of their political rights within the context of social contract. This means that industrial strike action and rebellion in most cases are attempts by citizens to assert their right which cannot be wished easily away. Rebellion or industrial strike action is therefore a means of forcing constituted authority to live up to its responsibility/ obligation in compliance with the dictates of a contract. This is always the case especially when the citizens or workers have exhausted all legal avenues but to no avail or when law and other institutional framework are inefficacious; then there will be no other option than for the people to mobilize for pro-active action through organized revolts; civil disobedience, downing of working tools or other allied-actions to redressing the anomaly. It will be wrong therefore, for any authority, whether government or employer to criminalize rebellion or strike which resulted from the failure of the government or employer to live up to expectation. Rather, there should be a round table discussion between the authority and the aggrieved parties to resolve the conflict as muscle flexing will only worsen the situation. Furthermore, whatever agreement reached during the deliberation, all parties involved, irrespective of their status and gender must stick to the agreement to avoid a future reoccurrence of the conflict.

Theoretical Framework

Three theories were considered relevant to this study; they are John Locke social contract theory, the pluralistic theory of industrial conflict and Marxist theory of industrial conflict. However this study will be anchored on John Locke social contract theory.

John Locke Social Contract Theory (1890)

John Locke's social contract theory is presented in the work, *Second Treatise of Government* in the year 1890. The main tenets of the Locke's social contract are Mutual obligation between the people and the government, the people's right of consent, the people's right to own property and the people's right of revolution against erring government. Locke posits that prior to the creation of the civil society man lived in a state of nature which is pre government and pre civil society devoid of law and order. The need for law and order prompted men to move into the social contract. Locke posits two contracts, namely: *Pactum Unionis*, which is the agreement to form a society and *Pactum Subjectionis* which is agreement to form a government. By these pacts/contract, the people and the government/ authorities both incurred a mutual obligation to make the civil society more comfortable than the state of nature. It is the obligation of the people to submit to and obey the government and it is the obligation of the government to protect the people's right to life and of property ownership. To sustain the welfare of the people, Locke suggested that, both the government and the individuals must keep to their obligations. This is so because, as stipulated by Locke, a contract becomes void if either side reneges on its terms.

Locke advocates for a type of government which must exist and govern by the peoples consent. Locke averred that to form a civil society or to ordain a leader, the people must willingly consent to it. Similarly, to enjoy another man's property or estate, his consent must be obtained and so on. Anyone who uses force over another or tries to impose his decision on another arbitrarily puts himself into a state of war or conflict with the other. This is because the victim of the forceful rule will fight to resist it. The consent doctrine of the Locke's social contract entails that the government at all times and in every situation is expected to seek the opinion of the people in decision and policy

making. the government can reach the entire people to obtain their consents in decision making their representatives such as union leaders.

Locke also posited that the right to own property in its wider sense refers to right to life, dignity of labor, liberty and material belongings. Everyman has the right to dispose of himself and his possessions as they may deem best. This right is inalienable because according to Locke it is a natural right, it is not created by society therefore, it can ipso facto not be limited by the society, except to the extent that it is necessary to give them effective protection through dispute resolution in cases of unlawful encroachment or unlawful possession. The human property/ possession include human labor which may be physical labor or mental labor. Locke referred to it as right to self ownership. Locke claimed that labor puts a distinction between property possessed by the individual and the property shared by all men in common. To use another man's labor, the man must be duly consulted and compensated for it in form of wages, salaries, allowances and other favorable conditions of labor. By nature, labor is intrinsically unpleasant. It is undertaken only in expectation of the dividend of the value one creates by it. It would be unjust therefore to thwart that expectation. As a matter of fact, any attempt to thwart the dividend expectation of a laborer always result to a conflict. Uncompensated labor may tantamount to slavery. Locke opined that to subject a man to slavery or for a man to submit himself to slavery violates the property rights of the man. In particular, Locke notes that property rights are the center of most conflicts in the human society. Work place conflicts between employers and employees, employees and fellow employees or employers and the government or business competitors are all hinged on property and labor rights. Most times, workers embark on industrial strike action when they feel their conditions of services are not favorable. To avoid such conflicts, government and private employers alike, must pay their workers as and when due.

Locke's social contract theory advocates for limited sovereignty or power derived from the people and held in the form of a trust. In other words, power belongs to the people. The people are therefore naturally empowered to retrieve power from an erring government. By this, Locke not only

opposed the divine rights of kings advocated by the Church of England, but also opposed the doctrine of absolute sovereignty advocated by his predecessor, Thomas Hobbes. According to Locke, the ruler is just another man who like all other men is prone to faults and making mistakes. Consequently, decision making is not to be left to the government alone because they can make mistakes or allow their human selfishness and emotions to becloud their sense of judgment and as such, make wrong decisions that can be detrimental to the public. Decisions therefore should be reached through deliberations rather than the arbitrariness of the rulers otherwise the civil society will become unbearable for man. To John Locke, the reign of a government ought not to be more unbearable than the state of nature. Should this be the case, people should merely revert back to the state of nature by liquidating the government. That is to say If the sovereign repeatedly abuses his power or consistently fail on the duty of guaranteeing the security of life, property and the liberty of the people, the people should oppose or rebel against him without fear of punishment or any form of victimization.

Locke's social contract theory is relevant to this study because its tenets revealed the possible ways by which contracts can be applied in conflict resolution and possible future avoidance of conflicts. It means that if social contract is properly applied, it might be able to resolve the conflict between ASUU and FGN.

The Pluralistic Theory of Industrial Conflict (1970)

The pluralist theory of industrial conflict also called the Oxford Approach or the Conflict Theory originated from the works of some British industrial relation academics such as Alan Fox (1966), Allan Flanders (1970) and Hugh Clegg (1975). However, Allan Flanders is recognized as the chief proponent of this theory. The major believe of this theory is that conflict is a rational and inevitable phenomenon in any industrial relationship hence, there is always the need for a formal system of collective bargaining, conciliation and arbitration as the means of establishing rules of engagement, terms of contract and resolving conflicts. The pluralist theory can be represented by the equation: $r = f(b)$ or $r = f(c)$ where r = rules governing industrial relations; b = collective bargaining;

c = conflict resolution through collective bargaining. This is to say that in the pluralistic theory, rules of industrial relation and conflict resolution is a function of collective bargaining.

Another major belief of the theory is that business/ industrial organizations is coalitions of related but separate and competing interest groups such as the management or the employer, the workers or employees and the government or regulatory body. According to Flanders, conflict between and among these interest groups is inevitable and necessary for innovation and growth of the organization. The inevitability of conflict here stems from the fact that there are opposing interests and the legitimacy of employers' interests, decisions, impositions and control is not automatically or expressly accepted by the employees. Where the interest of the employer contradicts those of the employees, such interests are vehemently opposed by the employees and conflict ensues. To strike a balance on the conflicting interests, negotiation and bargaining become necessary and for the sake of collective bargaining, the workers unite themselves in trade/ workers unions. In other words, it is the need for collective bargaining that gave rise to unionism in industrial relations. For the purpose of collective bargaining employees join workers' unions and employers join employers' union. Unions thus balance the decision making power between the employers and employees. Consequently, trade unions are viewed by the pluralist as legitimate representatives of interests groups. Stability in industrial relations is therefore, the product of concessions and compromises between management and trade unions. Hence trade unions should be accepted and respected by workers, employers, the government and the general public, as a necessary instrument for industrial harmony.

The pluralists argue that the government is an important interest group in the industrial relations. They believe that although collective bargaining is the best method of industrial conflict resolution, state intervention is still necessary to protect not only the interest of both the employers and the employees but the overall interest of the society. It is the duty of the government therefore to mediate between the employers and the trade unions when they could not easily reach a compromise or agreement through collective bargaining. They also believe that in an industrial organization,

conflict is inevitable and necessary for the growth and development of the organization. This is so because according to Flanders, the process of conflict resolution through collective bargaining avails the conflicting parties the opportunity to bring their grievances to a dialoging table where these grievances are exposed and resolved. When this happens, each party is happy and when workers are happy, their performances will increase leading to increased productivity. Moreover, each of the parties will be careful not to go contrary to resolutions and agreements to avoid conflicts. One can hence rightly state that the pluralistic theory focuses on the equilibrium between capitalists and the laborers rather than the domination of one over the other. It is a paradigm shift from the master-slave nature of the unitary theory era to a more democratic relationship in the industrial system. Pluralism changed the primary function of management from controlling, instructing or demanding to coordinating, communicating and persuading.

To ensure industrial harmony, managers should understand and respect the diversity of group interests, objectives and motivations as well as the need for team work. This is because when workers, managers or the government at any point expresses disregard for the rules of their contract/relationship or disrespect the interest of others, workplace relations would simply break down resulting to industrial strike and other outcomes that can hinder reasonable progress.

The pluralist theory of industrial conflict is relevant to the ongoing research in the sense that the theory centers on the root causes of labor-management-government conflicts in an industrial system and how the conflicts can be resolved through collective/ democratic bargaining. It also features Labor union as a legitimate organ of the industrial system necessary for harmony in the system. In connection to the educational industry, the university management, the labor unions (ASUU, etc) and the federal government constitutes the opposing interest groups who must mutually respect the interests of one another. Although the government represents a dual interest, first as the employer and secondly, the regulatory body, it is expected that it should respect ASUU as a legitimate representative of university academic staff. The government is therefore under obligation to bring ASUU to a dialogue table, persuade them into concessions, compromises and consensus and

whatever agreement reached in the course of their dialogue must be honored by both parties rather than government posing as the master and using arbitrary force to subjugate ASUU. By so doing, the perennial conflict between ASUU and federal government will be resolved and the Nigerian educational industry will be better for it.

Marxist Theory of Industrial Conflict (1848)

Marxist theory of Industrial Conflict otherwise known as Radical Approach originated from the ideas and works of Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels (1848) and Karl Marx (1867) in other words, the theory was drawn from two different publications involving Karl Marx. Marxist theory was first publicly presented in 1848 by Karl Marx along with Friedrich Engels in a pamphlet titled *The Communist Manifesto* which emphasized the theory of class conflict and revolution. However, In 1867 Karl Marx published his *Marxian economics* which focused on the criticisms of capitalism in a book, titled *Das Kapital*. The main postulation of this theory is that conflict between employers and employees is a product of capitalism and therefore, inevitable and perennial. Invariably, the political and social inequalities or class based economic structure of the society characterized by perpetual class struggle is the primary cause of industrial conflicts. This struggle is caused by inequalities in the distribution of wealth, power, authority and the ownership of the means of production between the two main classes of people in the capitalist economy – the “Haves” and the “Have Nots”, like the bourgeois and the proletariats.

The bourgeois are the rich who own and control the factors or means of production. They are the owners of business enterprises; they also control the political power while the proletariats consist of the poor and laborers who have nothing to offer other than their labors and services. The interests and aspirations of the bourgeois and the proletariats are divergent and in constant conflict. This is because, while the bourgeois tend to maximize profits by paying less for labor, the proletariats tend to maximize wages/salaries. Each of them uses every means trying to achieve their objectives and because the gain of the bourgeois is the loss of the proletariats and vice versa, the two are always antagonistic to each other, hence the persistent conflict.

However, because the bourgeois are in control of political powers, they use it to achieve their aims over the proletariats. The capitalists hence, perpetually cut down on the wages of workers and in extreme cases cut down on their numbers too. The rich thus grows wealthier at the expense of the poor, who lives at his mercy and is implicitly embittered by the development and will always be in search for a way out. Based on this, Marxists regard state intervention in industrial disputes via legislation, police and the creation of industrial tribunals and court as a means of supporting and sustaining management's interest and dominance rather than creating a balance between the competing classes. More so, initiatives alleged to ensure cordial industrial relations such as, collective bargaining, employee participation, co-operative work culture and so on are regarded by Marxists as nothing more than a hoax, sophisticated management techniques designed to reinforce control, subjugation and continued exploitation of workers.

Furthermore, the Marxists view trade unions both as labor reaction to exploitation by capital as well as a weapon to bring about a revolutionary social change. They argued that the primary concern of trade unions is improving the position of workers from the lower to the upper class within the economic and social class system whereas, concerns with wage-related disputes are secondary. The Marxists believe also that the inherent inequalities and exploitative economic relations between these upper and lower classes will lead to a revolution in which the working class will ultimately revolt against the capitalists, take over the control and ownership of the means of production and abolish the inequalities associated with capitalism and as such, replace capitalism in its entirety with collective ownership of factors of production, firstly under socialism and then under communism. By so doing, social classes and class struggle would no longer exist and that will mark the permanent resolution of industrial conflicts.

The Marxist theory of Industrial Conflict is relevant to this research study as it gives a reasonable explanation of the possible cause of the perpetual conflict between the Nigerian university academic staff under the umbrella of ASUU and the Federal government of Nigeria. In this case, the federal government constitutes the bourgeois class while the Nigerian university

academic staff is the proletariat class. The endless conflict between these two stems from class struggle and conflict of interest. While ASUU wants autonomy and freedom as well as better working conditions for her members in order to improve their positions from the lower to the upper class within the economic and social class system, federal government feels that such demands if granted will cause her to lose control over the university staff and that is a luxury it cannot afford. Although the Marxists' idea of revolution as the only means of industrial conflict resolution has been widely criticized and countered, regular strike by ASUU which is a form of rebellion has always been a means of dragging the government to dialogues. ASUU president once said that strike is the only language the Nigerian government understands. This is not supposed to be so. If the government can humble itself and shun exploitative tendencies and her master-slave disposition in her relationship with ASUU, dialogue with ASUU as equal partners and stick to their agreement, the conflict between them could be resolve and peace and progress restored in the university and to the nation at large.

Review of Empirical Studies

This section reviewed empirical studies carried out in areas related to the present study. It also examined how relevant and how related they are to the present study.

Study on Mutual Obligation and Conflict Resolution

Carsten (2021) carried out a study captioned Egocentrism and Naïve Realism: impact on the process of negotiation and mutual agreement in Nigeria local government system: a study of Enugu state. The aim of the study was to investigate how selfish bargaining and grandstanding approach affect the process of negotiation and mutual agreement in managing and resolving labor conflict in the local Government system in Nigeria with particular reference to Enugu State. Seven research questions and four hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Descriptive Research method was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of all the workers in Enugu State Local Government System totaling 10100 workers. Out of this population, a sample of 401 workers was selected using the Yamani sampling Formula. Questionnaire, oral interview and personal

observation were used as instrument for data collection. The data collected was analyzed using correlation coefficient (r) test, standard deviation and chi-square.

The findings of the study revealed that both government and staff union negotiators usually proceed in an egocentric or selfish manner and behave as “naïve realists” in the sense that they assume that the issues under contest is exactly as they see it, that other rational perceivers will therefore share their perceptions and that those who fail to see the matter as they see it are either lacking information or are biased. This behavior makes it very difficult for the conflicting parties to reach any mutual contract/ agreement. This makes conflict management or resolution between the parties difficult or impossible. This is therefore the reason why conflicts are persistent or reoccurring in government owned institutions. This according to the study is also the reason Management scarcely bargains with staff in resolving conflict situations. Management does not always explain its reasons for taking a particular position in resolving conflicts. The study further revealed that other factors that heightened labor conflict include: poor funding of the Local government system, low participation of employees in taking key decisions, especially on matters affecting them directly. To eschew or resolve industrial conflicts therefore, the negotiation parties must avoid selfishness but to try to see the issues from the other party’s perspective, make some sacrifices and some compromises to reach mutual agreement.

The reviewed research is related to the current study in the area of conflict between employers and employees or work place conflicts. In other words, both studies are concerned with causes and resolution of conflicts between workers and their employers and both adopted the descriptive survey research design. Also both employed questionnaire and interview for data collection. However, a gap exists in the reviewed study in the areas of scope, population and method of data analysis. The study under review covers causes and management of industrial conflict between Local Government Area workers and the management staff; used Local Government Authority staff in Enugu State as the population and correlation coefficient (r) test, standard deviation and chi-square as methods of data analysis. The current study filled the above gap by

focusing on Locke's social contract theory for conflict resolution between the academic staff union of universities and the federal government of Nigeria using directors of FME, Abuja and lecturers in Federal Universities in South-East Nigeria as the population and Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test statistic as the method of data analysis.

Adeyeye (2021) undertook a study on Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) and Federal Government (FG) conflict in Nigeria: Empirical evaluation of the root causes, character and management of ASUU strikes. The objective of the study was to identify and analyze the roots and character of ASUU-FGN conflict and to analyze why the settlement of ASUU-FGN discord was intractable. Three research questions and four null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of the study consisted of 10,000 subjects drawn from two groups. The first group comprises all academic staff in Nigerian Universities represented by the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU). The second group is made up of Ministers, Director Generals, members of University Councils, top National Universities Commissions officials, University Vice-Chancellors, among others whose official actions and policies determine in one way or the other, the way the Universities are administered. The sample of the study is 300 subjects which is 3% of the population selected using multi-stage stratified sampling technique. Documents, questionnaire and interview were used for data collection. Mean deviation and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions while the t-test statistics was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

The findings of the study revealed that the bone of contention between ASUU and the government has always based on erosion of university autonomy and academic freedom, underfunding of universities, poor remuneration and conditions of service of university staff and poor physical conditions of work coupled with radicalism and confrontational disposition of ASUU. Secondly, the settlement between ASUU and the government has been intractable because government use intimidation in attempt to subdue ASUU rather than engaging them in proper dialogue and when the governments reluctantly resort to dialogue, the same government will renege

on the agreements. The reviewed study and the current study are related since they both center on conflict between ASUU and the federal government and both adopted the same method of data analysis. However, while the reviewed study focuses on the roots and character of ASUU strikes and the reason the settlement of ASUU-Federal Government conflicts was intractable, the current study focused on Locke's social contract theory with the view to determine its application in resolving the conflict between ASUU and Federal Government of Nigeria. The gap created by the reviewed study which the current study filled is how to resolve the ASUU-Federal government conflict.

Ehoro and Konya (2020) carried out a research on collective bargaining, mutual agreement and industrial harmony in Rivers State-owned tertiary institutions. It aimed at investigating the relationship between collective bargaining/ mutual agreement and industrial harmony in Rivers State-owned tertiary institutions. The study adopted the cross-sectional survey in its investigation of the variables. Two hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consisted of 1,796 academic staff of 4 Rivers State owned tertiary institutions. The sample size of 327 was drawn using Taro Yamane sample size formula. A researcher developed questionnaire titled "collective bargaining, mutual agreement and industrial harmony questionnaire" (CBMAIHQ) was used for data collection. The hypotheses were tested using the Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Statistics at a 95% confidence interval and a 0.05 level of significance.

The findings of the study revealed that there is significant relationship between collective bargaining / mutual agreement and industrial harmony in Rivers State owned tertiary institutions hence, if the management of tertiary institutions should show more commitment and respect for collective bargaining and mutual agreement it will go a very long way fostering industrial harmony in the educational sector. The study under review and the ongoing research study are related since they are both concerned with relationship and industrial harmony between academic staff of tertiary institutions and the management body. However, the study under review created a gap in the area of scope of the study, both content and geographic scopes as well as in the areas of the sampling method, method of data collection and data analysis in the sense that the study focused on the

relationship between collective bargaining/ mutual agreement and industrial harmony with academic staff of 4 Rivers State- owned tertiary institutions as population of the study, using Taro Yamane sampling formula, used only questionnaire for data collection and Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Statistics for data analysis. The current study filled the gap by focusing on John Locke's social contract theory with the view to determine its application in resolving the conflicts between ASUU and Federal Government of Nigeria with directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of federal universities in south east Nigeria as the population, used simple random sampling technique, employed interview in addition to questionnaire for data collection and mean, standard deviation and t-test statistic for data analysis.

Ojo (2020) carried out a research on the theme, collective bargaining process and implementation of agreements: An appraisal of Federal Government and Academic Staff Union of Universities industrial disputes. The main aim of the study was to historically review the extent to which collective bargaining process has influenced the implementation of agreements reached in resolving industrial disputes particularly between the Federal Government of Nigeria and Academic Staff Union of Nigerian Universities in federal universities in South-West Nigeria. Four research questions and four hypotheses guided the study. The survey research design was adopted for the study. The academic staff of the three first generation federal universities in South-West Nigeria constituted the population size of 11,978. The stratified and simple random sampling techniques were used to draw a sample size of 1,385 staff (academic and non- academic) from the population comprising 13% of the total population for the study. The research instruments used for data collection for the study were interviews and a researcher structured questionnaire named Conflict and Staff Effectiveness Questionnaire (CBPIAQ). The research questions were answered using descriptive statistics of percentages, frequencies and means while the hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics of the t-test and Pearson Product Moment Correlation. All the findings were held significant at 0.05 probability level.

The findings of the study revealed that that collective bargaining has not been properly utilized to resolve the industrial disputes between the Federal Government and the Academic Staff Union of Universities. The serial infidelity in implementation of agreements has become a huge burden. Unilateral tinkering with a unanimous agreement between FG and ASUU has predominantly characterized FG-ASUU relationship, bedeviling the Nigerian university system with unending strikes. It reflects a critical industrial relations problem as witnessed in the incessant strike actions by ASUU as a consequence of government's failure to collectively bargain and honor agreements reached through negotiations. To resolve the conflict, therefore, policies aimed at governing the university system must be products of painstaking deliberations so that collective agreements are reached to guarantee workable as well as flexible solutions following acceptable international standards. Also, the machinery set up for collective bargaining, should be given some level of independence to work. Furthermore, all critical issues in the university system should be addressed in an atmosphere of mutual respect between the stakeholders and agreements reached between FGN and ASUU should be immediately implemented.

The study is related to the present study in the sense that both studies focus on the conflict between federal government of Nigeria and ASUU and the effective conflict resolution strategies to resolve the conflict. Also, both studies are related in the research design they adopted and in their instruments for data collection. However, the reviewed study created a gap by focusing on the extent to which collective bargaining process has influenced the implementation of agreements reached in resolving industrial disputes particularly between the Federal Government of Nigeria and Academic Staff Union of Nigerian Universities in federal universities in South-West Nigeria. In other words, the study under review emphasized on collective bargaining as a strategy to resolve ASUU-FGN conflict. It also created a gap in the geographical scope or area of the study as it used federal universities in South-West Nigeria. The current study filled the gap by emphasizing on Locke's social contract theory as a possible strategy in resolving the conflict between ASUU and Federal Government of Nigeria and by using federal universities in South East Nigeria.

Omodan and Dube (2019) carried out a research on mutual responsibility in bridging the dichotomous gaps between trade unions and management of tertiary institutions in Ekiti State Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to examine the mutual relationship between activities of trade unions and management of tertiary institutions in a bid to provide empirical solution to the lingering industrial conflicts between the staff unions in various tertiary institutions in Nigeria and the government. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The population of the study consisted of all the 4,174 members of academic and non-academic staff unions of three selected tertiary institutions including members of top management. The sample for the study consisted of 390 members of the unions who were selected using proportionate sampling techniques. Researcher structured questionnaire titled Trade Unionism and Management of Tertiary Institutions Questionnaire (TUMTIQ) and a second questionnaire titled Management of Tertiary Institutions Questionnaire (MTIQ) were used for data collection. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The research question was answered using percentage scores, frequency count and standard deviation while all hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) at 0.05 level of significance.

The findings from the study revealed a significant relationship between trade unions' dissatisfaction with conditions of service and management style and conflict in the tertiary institutions. In other words, disagreement between trade unions and the government stem from the failure of the government in their responsibility to ensure reasonable and suitable conditions of services and in employing good administrative style among other major causes of conflicts in tertiary institutions. Therefore, to resolve the conflict, the government must meet up with the responsibility of ensuring quality conditions of services for university staff as well as employ democratic administrative style to carry the university staff along in decision and policy making. The study reviewed is related and relevant to the current study because both studies center on providing resolution strategy to the lingering industrial conflicts between the staff unions of various tertiary

institutions in Nigeria and the government. However, the reviewed study created a gap in the areas of geographical scope, population, method of data collection and method of data analysis. While the reviewed study was conducted at Ekiti state with both academic and nonacademic staff as the population with questionnaire as instrument for data collection and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) as the method of data analysis, the present study filled the gap by using directors of FME, Abuja and only academic staff of Federal universities in South East Nigeria as the population, interview in addition to questionnaire for data collection and used Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test statistic as the method of data analysis.

Mbaji (2017) carried out a research study on Jean Jacques Rousseaus's social contract: Application in conflict resolution between the federal government of Nigeria and academic staff union of universities. The main purpose was to determine the consequences and causes of federal government versus ASUU conflict and the applicability of Rousseau's Social Contract theory in resolving the ASUU-Federal government conflict. Five research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised of 13 directors of Federal Ministry of education and 3908 members of academic staff union of Nigerian federal universities in South East Nigeria making it a total of 3921 subjects from which a sample size of 567 respondents were drawn using a multi stage-random sampling technique. A researcher developed questionnaire titled application of Rousseau's Social Contract in conflict resolution questionnaire. (ARSCCRQ) was used for data collection. The five research questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation while t-test statistic was used to test the three null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

The findings of the research shows that the consequences of the conflict between ASUU and FGN in Nigerian Universities among others include: closing down of the universities, disruption of the universities' academic calendar, lost of life and property, low productivity among staff, unjust dismissal of staff; also, the causes of the conflict between ASUU and FGN which are poor funding of university education, the issue of university autonomy and the issues of staff condition of services

can be resolved through the application of Rousseau's general will contract, direct democracy contract and self-enslavement contract respectively. The study under review and the current research are related in the sense that both deals with the application of social contract theory on the conflict between Federal government of Nigeria and ASUU, both focused on directors of FME, Abuja and lecturers in Federal Universities in South-East Nigeria as the population, descriptive survey design and Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test statistic as the method of data analysis. However, the study under review created a gap by focusing on application of Rousseau's general will contract, direct democracy contract and self-enslavement contract and using only questionnaire as instrument for data collection. The current study filled the gap by focusing on John Locke's social contract of mutual obligation between the people and the government, people's right of consent, people's right of property ownership, people's right of revolution/ rebellion against erring government and the possible application of these tenets in resolving the FGN-ASUU conflict and also by using interview in addition to questionnaire for data collection.

Study on Right of Consent and Conflict Resolution

Nolan-Haley (2022) carried out a study on Informed Consent in Mediation: its effect as a Guiding Principle for industrial conflict resolution: a case study of federal college of education, Zaria. The main aim of the study was to ascertain the possible roles of Informed Consent in Mediation in industrial dispute and resolution between academic staff union of colleges of education and the management/ government. Five research questions and 5 hypotheses were drawn to guide the study. The study adopted the experimental survey research design. The population of the study consisted of all staff and students of the Federal College of Education, Zaria (FCEZ) which is a total of 2680 subjects. With the use of probability sampling and simple random sampling (SRS) techniques, a sample size of 268 was drawn from the population which is 10% of the population. A structured questionnaire titled Informed Consent in Mediation for industrial conflict resolution questionnaire (ICMICRQ) and oral face to face interview were used to collect data for the study. The data was analyzed using the Chi-square One Way Test (Goodness-of-Fit) inferential statistical test.

The research findings revealed that Mediation shares a common goal of the court system: to achieve justice and fairness in the resolution of disputes. Mediation, however, is different from litigation because it is governed by the principle of consent. That is, conflicting parties must autonomously agree to engage in the process and to accept its outcome. Consent promotes self-determination and autonomy. Hence the absence of informed consent in mediation undermines this autonomous commitment and acceptance of outcome. The principle of informed consent requires that parties be educated about the mediation process before they consent to participate in it, that their continued participation in mediation be voluntary, and that they understand and consent to the outcomes reached in mediation. However, the study discovered that in government-Academic unions of colleges of education conflicts, the government most times used her position of authority to cajole or bamboozle the unions into consent. As a result, the unions hardly accept the outcomes of their mediations. Hence, their conflicts remain persistent as they keep reoccurring. The effects of the conflicts include loss of man-hour, poor academic performance amongst others.

Both the reviewed research and the current study are related in the sense that they are both concerned with conflict in the educational industry with academic staff of federal tertiary institutions as the population of the study. However, the study under review left a gap that stem from its geographical scope of colleges of education in Zaria, content scope of causes and effects of industrial disputes between the academic staff union of colleges of education and the government while failing to emphasize methods of resolving the dispute and its use of Chi-square One Way Test (Goodness-of-Fit) inferential statistical test as method of data analysis. Hence, the current study filled the gap by focusing on application of Locke's social contract theory in resolving the conflict between Federal Government and ASUU in federal universities in South East Nigeria using mean, standard deviation and t-test statistic for data analysis.

Chile and Ogbu (2021) carried out a study on Application of strategic communication and principle of consent in labour relationship between ASUU and the Federal Government of Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to investigate the use of strategic communication and the principle of

consent as a sound communication tools for effective collective bargaining or agreement in labour relations in Nigeria with focus on the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) and federal government of Nigeria. Three research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The population of the study consisted of all the 9,788 members of academic staff unions of federal universities in the North Central Region of Nigeria. The sample for the study consisted of 490 members of the unions who were randomly selected from four universities in the zone using proportionate sampling techniques. Researcher structured questionnaire and Interview schedules were used for data collection. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The research question was answered using percentage scores, frequency count and standard deviation while the two hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) at 0.05 level of significance.

The result of the study showed that effective application of strategic communication and principle of consent by employers (government) will to a high extent enhance respect for collective bargaining and agreement between employers and employee. It also revealed that government has always breached collective bargaining and agreement with ASUU. The findings of the study also showed that government does not respect labour laws even though this tantamount to abuse of workers' rights. More so, the government use intimidation and victimization as a means to subdue ASUU instead of using strategic communication. They try to dictate for ASUU and impose decisions and policy on the university staff, by so doing, the government neglects the principle of consent. The consequence of this has always been conflict and industrial strike by ASUU. The study reviewed is related and relevant to the current study because both studies center on providing resolution strategy to the lingering industrial conflicts between the staff unions of various tertiary institutions in Nigeria and the government, adopted same research design and employed similar instruments of data collection and analysis. However, the reviewed study created a gap in the areas of geographical and content scopes. While the study under review took place in North Central Nigeria, with focus on Application of strategic communication and principle of consent in collective bargaining and labour

relations between ASUU and the Federal Government of Nigeria and used Pearson Product Moment Correlation to analyze the hypotheses. The current study filled the gap as it took place in South-East Nigeria with focus on the application of Locke's social contract in resolving the conflict between the federal government of Nigeria and the academic staff union of universities and used t-test statistic to analyze the hypotheses.

Aja-Okorie (2017) carried out a research on impact of covert administrative style on Organizational Staff and management cooperation in Secondary Schools in Ohaozara Local Government Area of Ebonyi State. The aim of the study was to investigate how recognition and non recognition of workers opinion in decision and policy making affects team work and cooperation between teachers and their administrative heads. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of 672 secondary school teachers and administrators (444 teacher and 228 administrators) from all the eight public secondary schools within Ohaozara Local Government Area. A simple random sampling technique was used to draw a sample size of 220 teachers from the population for the study. Instrument for data collection was a researcher self structured questionnaire titled Impact of Covert Administrative Style on Organizational Staff and Administration Cooperation of Secondary Schools (IOCASOSAC)". Data collected were analyzed using statistical mean and t-test analysis.

The findings of the study showed that covert administrative style has negative impacts on teachers' commitment, coordination, cooperation and mental stress of teachers, which negatively impact on the effective administration of secondary schools in Ohaozara local government area of Ebonyi State. It also showed that conflict between teachers and school administrative personnel arise when teachers consent, opinions and suggestions are ignored in school policy making. Such an administrative style adversely affects teachers' school attendance, class coordination and good teacher-to teacher relationships in administration. It hinders teachers from covering their scheme of work. Furthermore, neglect of teacher's opinions in staff meetings negatively affect communication

among them, their shared duties, co-operation in the school, ability to follow the planned school calendar and make them to disrespect the principal and keep malice within themselves and with the principal. It can degenerate to serious conflict among teachers and making them to be aggressive, segregate and lose concentration in the class among others. Both researches are related in the sense that they are both concerned with conflict in the educational industry and they both applied mean and t-test for data analysis. However, the study in review is at variance with the current study because, the study in review focused on the impact of covert administrative style on Organizational Staff and Administration cooperation with teachers and administrators of Secondary Schools in Ohaozara Local Government Area of Ebonyi State as the population of the study. By this, the study under review left a gap in terms of the area of the study, population and scope of the study. This is the gap the current study filled by focusing on ways Locke's social contract theory can resolve the conflict between the federal government of Nigeria and academic staff union of universities in South-East Nigeria with directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of federal universities in South East as the population of the study.

Olaleye and Arogundade (2013) carried out a study on the principles of consent and other conflict management strategies of university administrators in South-West Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to find out, the types, causes of conflict and techniques of resolving conflicts by university administrators. Five research questions guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The target population consisted of all current heads of academic and non-academic departments, directors of academic programs and physical services, Deans of faculties and post graduate schools, registrars, Bursars, Deputy Vice-Chancellors, and Vice-Chancellors of one hundred and twenty two (122) universities in Nigeria. 36 owned by Federal Government, 36 owned by State Government and 50 privately owed. A sample of six universities selected through stratified random sampling was used for the study. This comprised two state universities, two federal universities and two private universities from which 200 professional administrators and 200 academic administrators making it a total of 400 respondents were drawn using simple random

sampling technique for the study. Questionnaire tagged Conflict management strategy of university administrators questionnaire (CMSUAQ) was used for data collection. Frequency count, mean score and percentages, were used in analyzing the data collected.

The findings of the study identified common types of conflict in the university to include: conflicts between Academic staff and the government, conflicts between Academic staff and professional administrators, conflict between Non-teaching staff and the Government, Conflict between Academic staff and students and between unions, conflict between students and the host community it also includes: interpersonal conflict among staff and the most common causes of conflict found in this study include communication gap or disregard to the principle of consent. Other major causes of conflict were non implementation of government circular on staff welfare and miscomprehension of duties between Academic and professional administrator. One of the most effective strategies for resolving conflicts as revealed by the study is dialogue between the two parties which involved finding out the opinions and interest of the other party which was ab initio neglected that resulted to the conflict and how to meet the interest and recognize various opinions in decision making.

The study is related to the present study in the sense that both studies focus on the conflicts that exist in Nigeria universities and the effective conflict resolution strategies for them. However, a gap exists in the study under review because of its use of Professional and Academic administrative heads in federal, state and private universities in South-West Nigeria as population of the study and its focus on dialogue and respect for the principle of consent as an effective strategy for resolving different kinds of conflicts in the universities. The present study filled the gap by focuses on Directors of FME, Abuja and only academic staff of Federal universities in South East Nigeria as the population of the study and Locke's social contract theory with its tenets of respect for mutual obligation, right of consent, right of property ownership and right to revolution as possible effective strategy to resolve the conflict between ASUU and Federal Government of Nigeria.

Study on Right of Property Ownership and Conflict Resolution

Ndema (2022) carried out a study on the effect of strategic labour unionism on workers welfare in Enugu state public service. The researcher sought to ascertain the extent to which labour unionism has guaranteed workers welfare and job security for workers in Enugu State; determine the extent to which workers unions have assisted to ensure timely promotion of workers in Enugu State; investigate the contributions of workers unions on regular provision of training programmes for workers in Enugu State; and ascertain the extent to which effective labour unionism has assured timely payment of pension and gratuities to retirees in Enugu State. The study adopted the survey research design. Five research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study comprised of 8604 public servants from the state ministries of labour, justice, education and health in Enugu state. Simple random sampling technique was adopted in selecting 864 public servants. The instrument for data collection was a researcher-structured questionnaire titled “Effect of strategic labour unionism on workers welfare questionnaire” (ESLUWWQ). Mean score and percentages, were used in analyzing the data collected while the t-test statistic was used to test the three null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significances.

The result of the study showed that effective unionism is lacking in Enugu State from 2015 till date consequent upon the harsh political environment under which unions operate in the state. Hence, Welfare of workers such as job security, timely promotion with commensurate financial benefits, regular training programmes, pension and gratuity benefits are hardly provided as and when due. All these have resulted to poverty, hunger, lack of interests to assigned responsibilities, etc among workers across government establishments in Enugu State. The researcher recommended among other things that labour unions in Enugu State should seek redress in industrial court with regards to any infringement on the rights of any worker in the state as this has yielded positive results in the past. The study under review and the current study are related in the sense that they both emphasized the relationship between employers and workers union. They are also related in the area of research design (survey research design) they adopted. However, the study under review left some gap in the areas of geographical and content scope in the sense that the reviewed study focused on

the effect of strategic labour unionism on workers welfare with public servants from the ministries of labour, justice, education and health in Enugu state as the population. The current study filled the gap by focusing on Locke's social contract theory to determine its application in resolving the conflicts between ASUU and Federal Government of Nigeria with directors of federal ministry of education, Abuja and academic staff of federal universities in south east Nigeria as the population.

Dunmade, Kadiri and Aliyu (2020) carried out a study on trade unionism and employees' welfare in the Nigerian medical association. The study focused on the effect of trade unionism on the workers' welfare of the Nigerian Medical Association (NMA) in Kwara State. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study comprised of all 2200 members of the Nigerian Medical Association, Kwara State chapter, Ilorin. The study employed simple random sampling technique in selecting 220 respondents for the study. Structured questionnaire was used for data collection. The data collected was analyzed using simple percentages, frequency tables and linear regression.

The findings of the study revealed that trade union's actions do have significant effect on employees' wages and salaries; and also that trade union's membership has significant effect on employees' working conditions. That is to say, trade unions have a very significant influence in ensuring workers welfare. The findings of the study also indicated that trade union's negotiation ability plays significant role in improving employees' job security among the medical staff of the Association. The study therefore recommends more encouragement for trade unionism in the Kwara State chapter of NMA. The reviewed study is relevant to the current study because both studies are similar in their focus on employers-employees relationship and the use of simple random sampling technique in drawing the study sample. However, the study under review left a gap in its geographical and content scopes, population, instrument for data collection and method of data analysis because it was carried out in Kwara state with focus on the effect of trade unionism on workers' welfare using members of the Nigerian Medical Association as the population, only questionnaire as instrument for data collection and simple percentages, frequency tables and linear

regression for data analyses. The current study filled the gap by focusing on application of Locke's social contract theory in resolving the incessant conflict between the academic staff union of universities and the federal government of Nigeria using directors of FME, Abuja and lecturers in Federal Universities in South-East Nigeria as the population, employed interview in addition to questionnaire for data collection and Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test statistic as the method of data analysis.

Similarly, Ekeoma and Sangoleye (2018) carried out a study on the causes of industrial conflict in the Nigerian University with University of Ilorin as a case study. The study aimed at ascertaining the predictors of industrial conflicts in Nigerian universities. Four research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 840 academic staff and 1164 non academic staff making it a total of 2004 subjects. With the use of simple random sampling technique, a sample size of 600 subjects comprising 280 academic staff and 320 non academic staff were selected for the study. A researcher developed questionnaire titled causes of industrial conflicts questionnaire (COICQ) was the instrument for data collection. Multiple regression analysis was applied in answering the research questions while the t-test statistic was used to test the null hypotheses.

The findings of the research showed that the possible causes of conflict in Nigeria universities are: poor working conditions and welfare of staff, poor funding of the institutions, poor leadership style, communication gap between the management and the staff unions among others. Both studies are related since both are centered on conflict in the Nigeria universities and they both adopted descriptive survey research design. However, while the study under review focused on the predictors of industrial conflicts in Nigerian universities, leaving a gap in the possible ways of resolving the conflict, the current study seeks to fill the gap by focusing on Locke's social contract theory with the view to determine its application in resolving the conflicts between ASUU and Federal Government of Nigeria.

Yusuf (2018) carried out a study on the causes and effects of industrial disputes by the academic staff union of colleges of education: a case study of federal college of education, Zaria from 1999-2014. The aim of the study was to ascertain the possible causes of industrial dispute between academic staff union of colleges of education and the management/ government. Five research questions and 5 hypotheses were drawn to guide the study. The study adopted the experimental survey research design. The population of the study consisted of all staff and students of the Federal College of Education, Zaria (FCEZ) which is a total of 2680 subjects. With the use of probability sampling and simple random sampling (SRS) techniques, a sample size of 268 was drawn from the population which is 10% of the population. A structured questionnaire titled causes and effects of industrial disputes questionnaire (CAEIODQ) and oral face to face interview were used to collect data for the study. The data was analyzed using the Chi-square One Way Test (Goodness-of-Fit) inferential statistical test.

The research findings revealed that the causes of dispute were non-payment of workers' entitlements, lack of conducive working environment, government's penchant to renege on agreements while the effects of the disputes include loss of man-hour, poor academic performance amongst others. Both the reviewed research and the current study are related in the sense that they are both concerned with conflict in the educational industry with academic staff of federal tertiary institutions as the population of the study and both employed similar instruments for data collect. However, the study under review left a gap that stem from its scope of colleges of education in Zaria, its focus on the causes and effects of industrial disputes between the academic staff union of colleges of education and the government while failing to emphasize methods of resolving the dispute and its use of Chi-square One Way Test (Goodness-of-Fit) inferential statistical test as methods of data analysis. Hence, the current study filled the above gaps by focusing on ways Locke's social contract theory can be applied in resolving the conflict between Federal Government and ASUU in federal universities in South East Nigeria with Directors of federal ministry of education, Abuja and

academic staff of federal universities in south east as the population and by using mean, standard deviation and t-test statistic for data analysis.

Tshuma, Ndlovu and Bhebhe (2016) conducted a research study on the causes of conflict among school personnel in Gwanda District Secondary Schools in Zimbabwe. The purpose of the study was to investigate causes of conflict in the urban and peri-urban secondary schools in Gwanda District of Zimbabwe. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 980 teachers and 155 administrative school heads and heads of departments bringing it to a total of 1135 subjects from which a sample of 400 was drawn using a simple random sampling technique. The instruments used for data collection were survey questionnaire and interview with the selected respondents. The data was presented using tables and percentages. The data were further analyzed with Simple percentage average and Chi-square distributions.

The findings show, that conflicts in Gwanda urban and peri-urban secondary schools occur among teachers in the same department; among teachers in different departments; between teachers and the school heads and among teachers, parents and students. The study established that conflict was influenced by both structural and personal factors among personnel in Gwanda urban and peri-urban secondary schools. The main structural causes of conflict were identified as sharing of resources, poor work conditions and administrative style used by leadership. The major personal factors that cause conflict in Gwanda urban and peri-urban secondary schools were differences in personalities, poor dissemination of information and favoritism at work by leadership.

This study is related and relevant to the current study in the area of causes of conflict in an educational system and organization. Also, both studies are related in their research design as they both employed descriptive survey design. However, the study under review differs from the current study in terms of area of the study, population and method of date analysis. While the study under review was carried out in Gwanda District in Zimbabwe as the area of the study, secondary school teachers as the population and Simple Percentage Average and Chi-square distributions as the

method of data analysis. The current study filled the gap as the study was carried out in Federal Ministry of Education (FME) Abuja and Federal Universities in south East Nigeria as the area of the study with Directors of FME and academic staff of federal universities as the population and employed mean, standard deviation and t-test statistic as the method of data analysis. Also, the study under review left a gap in the area of methods of conflict resolution between academic staff of universities and the government. Hence, the current study filled this gap as it emphasized Locke's social contract as a possible method of resolving conflicts between the federal government of Nigeria and ASUU.

Odey and Owan (2014) carried out a study on Empirical Analysis of Trade Unionism and the Enhancement of Workers' Welfare in Nigerian Maritime Sector. The study focused on the influence of trade unionism and the enhancement of workers' welfare in Nigeria, using maritime workers' union of Nigeria as a case study. The survey research design was adopted for the study. Three hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study comprised of 4110 maritime workers in Eastern Ports of Nigeria. Eastern Ports are made up of Calabar, Port Harcourt, Warri, and Onne. A sample size of 1000 respondents was drawn for the study using purposive sampling method. Questionnaires and interview schedule structured by the researchers were the instruments used for data collection. The data collected were analyzed using the one-way analysis of variance and Pearson product moment correlation statistics.

The findings of the study showed that the level of negotiation adopted by union members exerts significant influence on workers' welfare. Also, the union's ability to properly educate their members on their rights and availability of skillful and well educated union leaders can make a great difference to the effective management of labor demands. The study also revealed that the deprivation of workers from benefiting from their welfare package either by management or sometimes by ill-mannered union leaders was responsible for majority of the conflicts and strikes in work settings in our contemporary economy. In other words, the persistent faceoff or conflicts observed between employers and workers is due to the fact that some union leaders are not living up

to their responsibilities in terms of engaging in high level of responsible negotiation with management and failure to educate members to know their rights in the organizations. The reviewed study and the current study share some similarities and relationship in the areas of instrument of data collection as both used questionnaire and interview as instruments of data collection. Also both studies emphasized workers union and employers relationship in terms of agreement and conflict resolution. However, the reviewed study created a gap in the areas of geographical and content scopes, population of the study and method of data analysis as it focuses on the influence of trade unionism and the enhancement of workers' welfare in Nigeria, using maritime workers of Nigeria as population and one-way analysis of variance and Pearson product moment correlation statistics as method of data analysis. The current study filled the above gap by focusing on Locke's social contract theory for conflict resolution between the academic staff union of universities and the federal government of Nigeria using directors of FME, Abuja and lecturers in Federal Universities in South-East Nigeria as the population and Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test statistic as the method of data analysis.

Ige, Adeyeye and Aina (2011) carried out a research on the topic: An empirical study of the factors influencing Industrial Conflicts in the six geo-political zones of Nigeria (1980-2010). The study aimed at examining empirically the factors that influence industrial conflicts in Nigeria during the period 1980 to 2010. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study is 60,000 company workers in 18 companies in Nigeria. The sample for the study consisted of 400 company workers from six selected companies across the six geo-political zones of Nigeria which were selected through stratified random sampling technique. Secondary data were obtained from the Federal Ministry of Labor, Employment and Productivity, Lagos and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) Lagos. All the data for number of strikes, level of productivity and unemployment rate were obtained from the federal Ministry of Employment, Labor and Productivity, Lagos. While those on general level of prices were taken from various issues of Annual abstract of statistics, published by the

National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). The data for Union membership was obtained from Ananaba's Trade Union Movement in Nigeria and from the Federal Ministry of Labor's Annual Reports for various years. The review period lasted from 1980 through 2010. The study employed simultaneous equation model techniques (SEMT) and ordinary least square (OLS) techniques in analyzing the data collected.

Findings of the study showed that changes in wage rate, price expectation and union membership concentration are major determinants of industrial conflicts in Nigeria. Also the simultaneous equation model revealed that wages were significantly affected by strikes activity by labor unions. Strike activities were not affected by wages only during the period under study but also by prices of commodities. Thus a significant increase in wages and decrease in prices of commodities will lead to a substantial decrease in the incidence of conflicts both in the private sector and the public sector of the economy. The study under review relates to the current study in the sense that both studies have to do with work-place-related conflict and they have similar sample size. However, they differ in their methods of data analysis. While the study under review adopted simultaneous equation model techniques (SEMT) and ordinary least square (OLS) techniques in analyzing the data collected for the study, the current study adopted mean, standard deviation and t-test statistic for data analysis. Another gap created by the study under review is that the study under review used company workers in 18 companies in Nigeria and specifically focused on the factors that influence industrial conflicts in Nigeria during the period 1980-2010 but failed to proffer solutions to industrial conflicts. The present study filled the gap by emphasizing the application of Locke's social contract theory to the conflict resolution between ASUU and Federal Government of Nigeria with directors of FME, Abuja and lecturers in Federal Universities in South-East Nigeria as the population.

Study on Right of Revolution and Conflict Resolution

Sarpong, Kpabi, Abiew and Adomako (2022) carried out a research titled, strike actions in the health sector: does leadership play a role? A study of College of Health Sciences, University of

Ghana. The purpose of the study was to determine the extent to which leadership style contributes to striking actions in the Health Sector. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey approach. Five research questions guided the study. The population of the study comprised of 831 full time employed junior and senior staff of the College of Health Sciences, University of Ghana, Korle-Bu campus. A sample size of 149 respondents was selected using Yamane Taro's simplified formula for the study. A Structured Standardize Questionnaire was used for data collection from the respondents. Mean, standard deviation and frequency count were used to analyze the data collected.

The result of the study revealed that bureaucratic and autocratic leadership styles were among the causes of the strike action coupled with delays in salary increments, poor working conditions, unfairness in promotion and non-involvement of union leaders in decision-making. The study also revealed that the strike action of the college affects patient care, students' academic programmes and productivity as well as loss of employees' wages. The study recommended measures to curtail strike action such as improvement in the condition of service for employees, involvement of union leaders in decision-making, fairness in promotion procedure and most importantly, adoption of democratic, transformational and transactional leadership instead of bureaucratic and autocratic style would create industrial harmony in the school. The reviewed research and the current study are related in the sense that both studies are concerned with employer-employee disagreements in the education subsector. Also both studies employed questionnaire as their instrument for data collection and mean score and standard deviation for data analysis. However, the reviewed study created a gap in the areas of design, geographical and content scope, population and method of data collection and analysis in the sense that the study under review focused on the extent to which leadership style contributes to strike actions in the Health Sector with full time employed staff of the College of Health Sciences, University of Ghana, Korle-Bu campus as the population, adopted cross-sectional survey design, used only questionnaire instrument for data collection with mean score, standard deviation and frequency count for data analysis. The current study filled the above gap by focusing on Locke's social contract theory for conflict resolution

between the academic staff union of universities and the federal government of Nigeria using directors of FME, Abuja and lecturers in Federal Universities in South-East Nigeria as the population, adopted descriptive survey design and used interview in addition to questionnaire for data collection as well as used t-test statistic in addition to mean score and Standard Deviation as the method of data analysis.

Edward and Olaitan (2022) carried out a research on creating Harmonious Working Environment through Effective Industrial relations at workplace. The study focused on the need and ways to create harmonious working environment void of strike actions in Nigeria with emphasis on effective industrial relationship. The research adopted a survey design. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consisted of 18,480 workers in the Kogi state civil service and some selected private business ventures (Hotels, Banks and Manufacturing industries). The sample of the study comprised of 1020 respondents drawn from the population through simple random sampling technique. Structured questionnaire and oral interview were the instruments used for data collection. The data was analyzed using simple percentage and the Chi-square research techniques.

The result of the study revealed that harmonious working environment can be secured through effective industrial relations at workplace which is achievable using proper two way traffic effective communication by employers, always dialoging and bargaining with the workers on terms of their contracts; by management giving attention to the needs and living conditions of the workers and not suppressing their voices and by workers doing what they are employed to do and striving to attain the business objectives of their institutions. The study also revealed that the challenges confronting the workers unions have not allowed their activities to be effective in ensuring effective industrial relationship with their employers. Therefore, the study recommended that organizations should create enabling environment for union activities to thrive by assisting them where necessary so as to stabilize the organization. The study under review relates to the current study in the sense that both studies have to do with ways of managing or avoiding work-place-related conflicts and they

employed similar sampling technique and similar instrument for data collection that is simple random sampling technique; structured questionnaire and oral interview respectively. However, they differ in their methods of data analysis. While the study under review adopted simple percentage and the Chi-square research techniques in analyzing the data collected for the study, the current study adopted mean, standard deviation and t-test statistic for data analysis. Another gap created by the study under review is that the study under review used workers in the Kogi state civil service and some selected private business ventures (Hotels, Banks and Manufacturing industries) and specifically focused on creating harmonious working environment through effective industrial relations at workplace. The present study filled the gap by emphasizing the application of Locke's social contract theory to the conflict resolution between ASUU and Federal Government of Nigeria with directors of FME, Abuja and lecturers in Federal Universities in South-East Nigeria as the population.

Nwankwo, Ezeanolue, Nnorom, and Mbonu (2021) carried out a study on Principals' administrative style: predictor for teachers' cooperation, job performance and secondary school effectiveness in Ehime Mbano Local Government Area of Imo State. The aim of the study was to explore how principals' administrative styles can affect teachers, cooperation, tendency to rebel, their job performance and over all secondary school effectiveness in Ehime Mbano local government area of Imo state. The study adopted the survey research design. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study comprised of 204 teachers and principals in Ehime Mbano local government area of Imo state. Simple random sampling technique was adopted in selecting 16 Principals and 136 secondary school teachers in Ehime Mbano giving a total of 152 respondents. The instrument for data collection was a researcher-structured questionnaire titled "Principals Administrative Styles and Teachers cooperation and Job Performance and Secondary Schools Effectiveness" (PASTCJPSSE). Mean score and percentages, were used in analyzing the data collected while the t-test statistic was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significances.

The findings of the study revealed that open and democratic leadership style by the principal is important for teachers' cooperation with the principal and effectiveness at work. In other words, communication with teachers and staff enhance effectiveness to schools. Constant and smooth communication energizes both teachers and learners in the school. If the Principal fails to keep teachers posted with the current information needed for the effectiveness of secondary schools, they may be deformed especially in quality lesson delivery and their tendency to disrespect and to rebel against the principal will be high. This according to the study is because, good communication enhances and stimulates enthusiasms; raise the interest and motivation of those concerned; removes fear and anxiety on the part of teachers and brings unity and friendliness between principals and teachers which leads to effectiveness of teachers in their job performance. The study also revealed that Principals who involves teachers in decision making motivates them for performance effectiveness. Hence, staff meeting is an important aspect of school administration which promotes teaching and learning in secondary schools. Hence, to achieve teachers cooperation, reduce teachers' rebellious tendency and enhance their job performance and to ensure the overall school effectiveness, Principals should adopt good communication pattern, involve teachers and staff in decision making, become less autocratic and bureaucratic and imbibe democratic and open leadership style,

The reviewed research is related to the current study in the sense that both studies are concerned with causes and resolution of disagreement in the work place, especially within the education subsector. Also both studies adopted the descriptive survey research design. Also both employed questionnaire for data collection. However, a gap exists in the reviewed study in the areas of geographical and content scope, population and method of data collection and analysis. The study under review focuses on how principals' administrative styles can affect teachers' cooperation, tendency to rebel, their job performance and over all secondary school effectiveness in Ehime Mbano local government area of Imo state with secondary school principals and teachers as the population; used questionnaire instrument for data collection and mean score and t-test statistic for data analysis. The current study filled the above gap by focusing on Locke's social contract theory

for conflict resolution between the academic staff union of universities and the federal government of Nigeria using directors of FME, Abuja and lecturers in Federal Universities in South-East Nigeria as the population and used interview in addition to questionnaire for data collection as well as used Standard Deviation in addition to mean score and t-test statistic as the method of data analysis.

In another instance, Ekwoaba and Danesi (2020) carried out a study on the effects of academic staff union of universities revolt on employees' job performance in university of Lagos. The purpose of the study was to examine how the union's industrial strike actions affect the job performance of academic employees in the University of Lagos. Two research questions and a null hypothesis guided the study. A cross-sectional research design was employed for the study. The population of the study comprises of 1065 subjects drawn from all the departments of the university. A sample size of 199 was derived from the population using the krejcie and Morgan's formula. A structured questionnaire titled academic staff union of universities revolts and employees' job performance questionnaire (ASUUREJPQ) was employed for data collection. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions while inferential statistics of t-test was used to test the null hypothesis.

The findings of the study showed that the effect of industrial action on the performance of University academic employees includes difficulties in planning the universities' academic and non-academic activities and programs; interruptions of the school calendar resulting to poor inculcation of the requisite skills to the learners which makes them unemployable and globally incompetent, a situation that increases unemployment and hinders national development. The study is relevant to the present study in the sense that both studies deal with the issues of conflict between federal government of Nigeria and ASUU and both adopt mean and standard deviation for data analysis. However, the reviewed study left a gap as it focuses on how the industrial actions of Academic Staff Union of universities affect the job performance of academic employees in University of Lagos with staff of Unilag as the population and used krejcie and Morgan's formula as its sampling technique as well as using questionnaire as the instrument for data collection. This is the gap the present study

filled by employing simple random sampling techniques and focuses on Locke's social contract theory with the view to determine its application in conflict resolution with directors of Federal ministry of education and academic staff of federal universities in south east as the population of the study. It also used interview in addition to questionnaire as the instrument for data collection.

Wahab (2018) carried out a research study on the topic: An investigation of the causes of workers revolt and its effect on students' academic performance: a case study of Federal University of Lagos Akoka. The purpose of the study was to probe into the causes and effects of industrial strikes as a form of workers revolt against Management in Nigeria universities. Four research questions and four null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted experimental survey research design. The population of the study consisted of all staff and students of the Federal University of Lagos which is a total of 7640 out of which a sample of 560 subjects were selected through simple random sampling technique. A researcher structured questionnaire titled causes and effects of industrial strikes questionnaire (CAEOISQ) was used for data collection. Multiple regression analysis was applied in answering the research questions.

The findings of the study showed that factors that cause university staff to revolt against the university management body in the Nigerian universities include: dissatisfaction with wages, poor working and social conditions of staff, fatigue and frustration at work plus insincerity of the Federal Government in honoring agreements reached between her and staff unions, poor funding of the universities, government's continued appointments of highly inexperienced politicians as education Ministers and Ministers of labor and Employment and the imposition of IPPIS on university staff. The study also revealed that the effects of strikes include: brain drain, frequent disruption of academic calendar, Irregular learning and poor quality of teaching necessitated by poor services from aggrieved lecturers which leads to falling standard of learning and turning out of half-baked graduates into the labor market. Also, during industrial strikes students are idle and frustrated hence, many of them resort to deviant behavior like robbery, arson, rape, touting and nuisance to the society. The study under review and the ongoing research are related since they are both concerned

with conflict between staff union of universities and the federal government. However, the reviewed study focused on just the University of Lagos and the causes and effects of industrial strikes in Nigerian universities as its geographical and content scope while using Multiple Regression as method of data analysis. These are the gaps the current study filled by focusing specifically on Locke's social contract theory with the view to determine its application in resolving the conflict between Federal Government and ASUU in federal universities in South East Nigeria.

Summary of Literature Reviewed

The literature review focused on three main sub-headings: conceptual framework, theoretical framework and review of empirical studies. Under conceptual framework, literature materials reviewed provided much insight on major concepts of the study such as Nigeria university education system, academic staff union of universities (ASUU), the concept of conflict, the bases of the conflict between FGN and ASUU, conflict resolution, industrial conflict resolution strategies and concept of social contract. University education was reviewed as the tertiary educational institution in Nigeria that provides learners with the highest level of education through lecturing/ teaching, learning, research, internship and practicum for high level intellectual and technical functioning. ASUU was considered as a national trade union created for the purpose of fighting for the interest and welfare of academic staff of universities in Nigeria with all academic staff of the Nigerian universities as its members and conflict can be defined as the disagreement between two or more parties over certain issues. It was reviewed that the bases of conflict between ASUU and FGN are erosion of university autonomy, poor funding of universities and poor conditions of services of university staff. Conflict resolution was viewed as any attempt aimed at management or total termination of a conflict to minimize its negative impacts on the organizational objectives. Industrial conflict resolution strategies reviewed include dialogue, mediation, conciliation, arbitration, adjudication and negotiation. Locke's Social contract was conceptualized as an undertaking of two or more parties to form a unit of association whereby one party consents to the leadership of the other party for the sake of social well being for all.

Under theoretical framework, three theories were reviewed. They are: John Locke social contract theory, the pluralistic theory of industrial conflict and Marxist theory of industrial conflict. However, the study anchored on John Locke social contract theory. John Locke social contract theory critically exposes mutual obligation, people's right of property ownership, people's right of consent and people's right of rebellion as the bases of contract by which conflicts can be resolved or avoided. The pluralistic theory explains that conflict is a rational and inevitable phenomenon in any industrial relationship due to conflicting interests, hence there must be a system of collective bargaining set up to avoid conflicts and to resolve them when they arise. Hence, rules of industrial relation and conflict resolution are a function of collective bargaining. The Marxist theory revealed that industrial conflict emanates from class struggle and conflict of interest between the bourgeois and the proletariats or the capitalists and employees and that it can only be resolved by revolution or rebellion of the employees by which capitalism and all agents of social inequalities are eliminated.

Under the review of empirical studies, twenty-two (22) studies were reviewed. The studies reviewed focused on mutual obligation, right of consent, right of property ownership and right of revolution. From the empirical studies reviewed, no known study was carried out on application of John Locke's social contract theory on conflict resolution between the academic staff union of universities and the federal government of Nigeria in federal universities in south-east Nigeria. Thus, this formed part of the gap the researcher filled.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHOD

This chapter describes the research method that was employed in carrying out the study. It comprises of design of the study, area of the study, population of the study, sample and sampling technique, instrument for data collection, validation of the instrument, reliability of the instrument, method of data collection and method of data analysis.

Design of the Study

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The descriptive survey research design has been described as the type of research design that employs reliable techniques to collect data from a well-defined population or systematically selected segments of the population for the purpose of determining the attributes of or facts about the entire population (Nwogu, 2015). The survey design is best suited for this study because the study sort to collect, describe, analyze and interpret data collected from a given sample of the population of academic staff of Federal Universities in South East Nigeria directors of Federal Ministry of Education and officials of federal ministry of labour and employment to determine the applicability of Locke's social contract theory in resolving the perennial conflict between the academic staff union of universities and the federal government of Nigeria.

Area of the Study

The study was carried out in the Federal Ministry of Education (FME) Abuja, Federal Ministry of Labour and Employment (FMLE), Abuja and all the federal universities in South-East zone of Nigeria. The Federal Ministry of Education is a part of Federal Ministries in Nigeria that directs education in Nigeria. It is located at Block 5A (8th floor), Federal Secretariat complex, Shehu Shagari Way, Central Area Abuja. Abuja is the federal capital territory of Nigeria. The Federal Ministry of Education, Abuja was chosen for this study because the Federal Ministry of Education is the apex body in charge of formulating national policy on education, educational planning and

financing of education throughout the country and educational policy making and funding are among the major issue of contention between the government and ASUU.

The Federal Ministry of Labour and Employment is the Federal Ministry concerned with the relationship between workers and employers. It is headed by the Minister of Labour and Employment appointed by the president. The minister is assisted by a Permanent Secretary, who is a career civil servant. The ministry's head office is located at Block 44 (the 2nd floor), Federal secretariat Complex Shehu Shagari Way, Central Area, Abuja. The ministry of Labour and employment, Abuja was chosen for this study because the ministry formulates policies on trade union organizations as well as handles labour disputes and complaints, assist in worker's education and keeps records on trade unions and their activities. These functions brought the ministry to the front line as a representative of the federal government in the course of her conflict and negotiations with ASUU. Hence, the ministry has played a prominent role in the course of the ASUU-FGN conflict and therefore a stake holder on the matter.

South-East is one of the six geo-political zones in Nigeria. South-East comprises of five states namely: Abia State, Anambra State, Ebonyi State, Enugu state and Imo state. South-East is bounded by Delta in the west, Rivers and Bayelsa States in the south, Cross River and Akwa Ibom States in the east and Kogi and Benue States in the north. Igbo is the native language spoken by the people of South-East. The South-East zone was chosen for this study because of the presence of many educational institutions in the area, especially Universities hence, most of the individuals of this area are to a large extent educated, a situation that earned the five states in the zone the title of educationally advantaged states. Also most people in the area are university undergraduates, graduates, civil servants or university staff who depends on government salaries for economic security. Based on this, any situation that affects education adversely will have a direct and proportionate effect on the lives of majority of the people economically, socially, mentally and otherwise. In other words, the persistent conflict between ASUU and FGN which has severally led to the closure of the schools as the staff goes on strike resulting to total fall in the standard of the

university education in the country has dealt a heavy blow on the people of this area due to their large dependence on education. During such strikes, most parents in the area are cut off from their source of livelihood especially with the government policy of “no-work, no pay”, a condition that has led to lots of family crises in the area such as starvation and the death of many due to inability to afford medical treatment. More so, during the strikes, students are kept idle for long period of time hence, some of them resort to crime and other social vices, as the saying goes, “An idle mind is the devil’s workshop”. The above problems therefore informed the choice of the South-East region for this study.

Population of the Study

The population of this study comprised 4,354 subjects (15 Directors of Federal Ministry of Education, Abuja, 12 Directors of Federal Ministry of Labour and Employment, Abuja and 4,327 academic staff of Federal Universities in South-East). The population of the academic staff of the universities is distributed as follows: university of Nigeria Nsukka (UNN) 1,098, Federal University of technology Owerri (FUTO) 825, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka (UNIZIK) 924, Michael Okpala University of Agriculture, Umudike (MOUAU) 788 and Federal University Ndufu Alike Ikwo, Abakeliki (FUNAI) 692. Source: Human Resource Management Department, Ministry of Education and Ministry of Labour and Employment Abuja, 2022 and staff personnel service department of federal universities in South-East Nigeria 2021/2022) (See Appendix, C Page 109).

Directors of Federal Ministry of Education, Directors of Federal Ministry of Labour and Employment and academic staff of federal universities were chosen as the population of the study because they are directly involved in the FGN-ASUU conflicts, they are also directly involved in every negotiation in attempts to resolve the conflict. As a result, they were in better position to give credible information on ways Locke’s social contract theory can resolve the incessant FGN-ASUU conflict.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample for this study consists of 448 respondents (15 directors of Federal Ministry of Education and 433 lecturers from the federal universities in South-East). All the 15 Directors of Federal Ministry of Education were used for the study while 433 respondents were drawn from the population of 4,327 academic staff of federal universities in South-East. 448 represent 10.3% of the population of academic staff of federal universities in South-East. The rationale for selecting 10.3% of the population is in line with Umar and Usman (2015) who states that “if the population of a study is in few hundreds, a 40% or more sample will do; if many hundreds, a 20% sample will do; if a few thousands, a 10% will do; and if many thousands, a 5% or less will do”. Thus, since the population of the study (4354) runs into few thousands, a 10.3% sample is considered appropriate for this study.

Three universities: FUTO, UNN and UNIZIK were drawn from the five South-East universities: FUTO, MOUAU, UNN, NAU and FUNAI using simple random sampling technique. The names of the universities were written on pieces of papers, folded, placed in a container and shuffled; then the researcher drew the three universities named above without replacement (balloting without replacement). The sample of 433 was shared among the three universities as follows: FUTO-144, MOUAU-144 and UNN-145. Similarly, simple random Sampling technique was adopted to sample three faculties from each of the three universities sampled for the study: for FUTO, School of Agriculture and Agriculture Technology, School of Basic Medical Science and School of Engineering Sciences were sampled with 48 respondents each; For UNIZIK, faculty of Arts, faculty of Management Sciences and faculty of Social Sciences were sampled with 48 respondents each and for UNN, faculty of Linguistics and Nigerian Languages with 48 respondents, faculty of Education with 49 respondents and faculty of Biological Sciences with 48 respondents sampled. These faculties were selected using simple random technique because the subjects across all the faculties possess similar characteristics as academic staff.

Instrument for Data Collection

A structured questionnaire titled: Locke’s Social Contract and Conflict Resolution Questionnaire (LSCCRQ) developed by the researcher from the reviewed literature and interview

schedule were used for data collection. The questionnaire consisted of sections A and B. Section A comprised information regarding the demographic data of the respondents. Section B contains (30) items built on four clusters namely; A, B, C and D. Cluster A, comprises 9 items on the extent to which mutual obligation can resolve the conflict between ASUU and FGN; Cluster B comprises 5 items on the extent to which people's right of consent can resolve the conflict between ASUU and FGN; Cluster C comprises 10 items on the extent to which people's right of property ownership can resolve the conflict between ASUU and FGN and Cluster D comprises 6 items on the extent to which people's right of revolution can resolve the conflict between ASUU and FGN. The instrument is based on a four-point rating scale with the following response modes for clusters A, B, C and D; Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) with scores of VHE = 4 points, HE = 3 points, LE = 2 points and VLE = 1 point. (See Appendix B). In addition to the questionnaire, interview schedule was used to collect data on the opinions of four (4) directors of FME, four (4) directors of FMLE and ten (10) lecturers randomly selected. 3 lecturers each from FUTO and MOUAU and 4 lecturers from UNN where granted interview immediately their questionnaires were retrieved from them.

Validation of the Instrument

The instruments were given to three experts for face validation. Two of the validates are from Philosophy of Education unit of Educational Foundations Department while one of the validates came from Measurement and Evaluation unit of Science Education Department, all from the Faculty of Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. The validates were requested to examine the items of the instruments in terms of; relevance to the study and adequacy in collecting relevant data to address the purpose of the study. The validates were also required to examine the level and appropriateness of the language used in structuring the items of the instruments. The experts examined the instruments' schedules and clusters to ensure that they align with the topic, research questions and hypotheses. The experts independently made comments, criticisms and suggestions that helped the

researcher to modify and produce the final instruments that were used for data collection for the study.

Reliability of the Instrument

In order to ensure the reliability of the instrument, 20 copies of the questionnaire were trial-tested on randomly selected respondents consisting of 5 Heads of department of the Imo State Ministry of Health and 15 lecturers from the University of Port Harcourt which is outside the study area. To ascertain the internal consistency of the instrument, Cronbach Alpha statistical method was used to determine the reliability coefficient which yielded: Cluster A, 0.83, Cluster B, 0.80, Cluster C, 0.79 and Cluster D, 0.71. These gave an overall reliability of 0.78. The result indicates that the instrument is reliable. (See Appendix D, Page)

Method of Data Collection

The direct delivery and retrieval method was employed. In other words, the researcher personally delivered the 448 copies of the questionnaire to the research subjects with the help of three trained research assistants. The three research assistants were briefed by the researcher on how copies of the questionnaire should be administered in order to ensure safe handling and maximum retrieval of the filled questionnaire. The reason for the use of research assistants was to ensure that the intended subjects were promptly reached to respond to the questionnaire almost within the same period of time. Similarly, the eight directors and ten lecturers were interviewed immediately their questionnaires were retrieved except for the directors of the ministry of labour and employment who were just granted interview because they were omitted during the questionnaire distribution earlier. The interviews were carried out by the researcher with a tape recorder and with a research assistant taking notes while the tape recorder was switched on. The researcher asked probing questions within the scope of the research. At the end of the interviews, the researcher returned to his residence and compiled the records from the research assistant and the tape recorder for further analyses. The process lasted about a month and 12 days due to difficulties encountered in securing meetings with the directors.

Method of Data Analysis

To provide answers to the research questions, the data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. The decision benchmark was 2.50. This means that mean scores from 2.50 were regarded as positive outcomes while mean scores below 2.50 were rejected. The t-test statistic was used to test the four null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The interview schedule data was analyzed using thematic analysis method. Here the researcher closely examined the data to identify common themes (or responses), ideas and pattern of meanings that came up repeatedly. The responses were structured as follows: VHE= Very High Extent, HE= High Extent, LE= Low Extent, VLE= Very Low Extent.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

This chapter presents the analysis of data collected. The results are presented in tabular form in line with the research questions and the hypotheses that guided the study as well as the interview schedule.

Research Question 1: To what extent can mutual obligation resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN?

Table 1: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviations of Respondents on the Extent to Which Mutual Obligation Can Resolve the Conflicts between ASUU and FGN

S/ N	Item Statements	Directors (N = 13)			Academic Staff (N = 412)			Overall		
		\bar{X}	SD	DL	\bar{X}	SD	DL	\bar{X}	SD	DL
1	Establishment of comprehensive agreements between ASUU and FGN with well spelt out terms to address their conflicting issues.	3.30	0.48	HE	3.40	0.49	HE	3.39	0.48	HE
2	Parties to agreement (ASUU and FGN) should not renege on such agreements.	2.07	0.75	LE	3.65	0.47	VHE	3.60	0.55	VHE
3	The agreements must indicate the repercussion for reneging on the terms of agreements by any of the parties.	1.46	0.51	VLE	3.65	0.47	VHE	3.58	0.60	VHE
4	The government should live up to the obligation of providing the 90% funds for the universities by increasing budgetary allocation to education to a minimum of 26% UN prescription.	2.30	0.75	LE	3.44	0.49	HE	3.40	0.54	HE
5	ASUU should live up to the 10% universities funding obligation as prescribed by the government by sourcing for funds from alternative sources.	3.76	0.43	VHE	3.74	0.43	VHE	3.74	0.43	VHE
6	The government should make it easier for universities to access the Education Trust Funds (ETF) as a	1.84	0.68	LE	3.34	0.47	HE	3.30	0.54	HE

means of increasing university funding.

7	ASUU should through their publications liaise with the government to reorient the masses towards the responsibility of assisting the government in funding the university education.	3.69	0.48	VHE	3.65	0.47	VHE	3.65	0.47	VHE
8	FGN should prioritize educational development and show strong commitments to its sustainability.	3.69	0.48	VHE	3.74	0.43	VHE	3.74	0.43	VHE
9	Government officials should encourage stable academic calendar by avoiding political grandstanding, heckling and harassments in matters concerning the development and sustenance of university education.	1.76	0.72	LE	3.59	0.49	VHE	3.54	0.58	VHE
Cluster Mean		2.65	0.58	HE	3.57	0.46	VHE	3.54	0.51	VHE

\bar{x} = Mean, SD= Standard Deviation, VHE= Very High Extent, HE= High Extent, LE= Low Extent, VLE= Very Low Extent, DL= Decision Level

Results in Table 1 above shows the mean ratings and standard deviations of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent mutual obligation can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU. In response to items 1, 5, 7 and 8, both the directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities responded to the items with the mean scores of 3.30, 3.40; 3.76, 3.74; 3.69, 3.65 and 3.69 and 3.74 respectively. This falls within the mean range of 2.50-3.49 and 3.50-4.00 set as criterion for high extent and very high extent. However, views of the respondents vary in items 2, 3, 4, 6 and 9. On one hand, the directors of federal ministry of education to a low extent responded to the items with the mean scores of 2.07, 1.49, 2.30, 1.84 and 1.76 respectively. On the other hand, the academic staff of universities to a high extent and to a very high extent responded to the items with the mean scores of 3.65, 3.65, 3.44, 3.35 and 3.59 correspondingly. Generally, the table showed a cluster mean scores of 2.65 with a corresponding standard deviation of 0.58 (for directors of federal ministry of education) and 3.57 with standard deviation of 0.46 (academic staff of universities) together with an overall mean score of 3.54 with a corresponding standard deviation of 0.51. The above overall mean score is an

empirical evidence that mutual obligation as postulated by John Locke in his social contract theory can be used to resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU to a very high extent.

Hypothesis One

H0₁: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent mutual obligation can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU.

Table 2: t-test Analysis of the Significant Difference between the Mean Ratings of Directors Of Federal Ministry Of Education And Academic Staff Of Universities On the Extent Mutual Obligation Can Resolve The Conflicts Between FGN and ASUU

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	t-value	Df	Sig.	Dec.
Directors	13	2.65	0.58	0.67	423	0.06	NS
Academic Staff	412	3.57	0.46				

Key: NS = Not Significant, $df = (n_1 - 1) + (n_2 - 1) = (425 - 1) + (425 - 1) = 423$

The results in Table 2 shows the t-test analysis of the significant difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent to which mutual obligation can be applied to resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU. Result shows that a t-value of 0.67 with a degree of freedom of 423 and a significant value of 0.06 were obtained. Since the significant value of 0.06 is greater than 0.05 set as level of significance for testing the hypothesis, this means that the result is not significant. The null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent mutual obligation can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU is by implication, not rejected. Inference drawn therefore is that the difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent mutual obligation can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU is not statistically significant. This means that both respondents share similar opinion or view on the extent to which mutual obligation can be used to resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU.

Research Question 2: To what extent can the people's right of consent resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN?

Table 3: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviations of Respondents on the extent the people's right of consent can be applied in resolving the conflicts between ASUU and FGN

S/N	Item Statements	Directors (N = 13)			Academic Staff (N = 412)			Overall		
		\bar{X}	SD	DL	\bar{X}	SD	DL	\bar{X}	SD	DL
10	Government should in the spirit of patriotism partner with ASUU in making policies affecting university education.	1.76	0.43	LE	3.35	0.47	HE	3.30	0.54	HE
11	Government and her agencies should recognize and respect Acts and laws governing individual universities.	2.07	0.75	LE	3.20	0.40	HE	3.17	0.46	HE
12	Government should enact policies to allow universities the freedom of procedural self-governance even in recruitment of staff and students' admission.	1.84	0.68	LE	3.50	0.50	VHE	3.44	0.58	HE
13	The university Senate should be allowed to determine the content of their university programs/ courses.	3.38	0.50	HE	3.45	0.49	HE	3.45	0.49	HE
14	The government and her agencies should avoid covert interference with the university senate in their assessment and promotion of their academic staff.	3.38	0.65	HE	3.84	0.36	VHE	3.83	0.37	VHE
Cluster Mean		2.48	0.60	LE	3.46	0.44	HE	3.43	0.48	HE

\bar{x} = Mean, SD= Standard Deviation, VHE= Very High Extent, HE= High Extent, LE= Low Extent, DL= Decision Level

Results in Table 3 illustrates the mean ratings and standard deviations of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent the people's right of consent can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN. Going by the results as presented on the table, it is obvious that views of the respondents vary in items 11, 12 and 13. For instance, the directors of federal ministry of education to a low extent responded on the items that government should in the

spirit of patriotism partner with ASUU in making policies affecting university education, recognize and respect Acts and laws governing individual universities and enact policies to allow universities the freedom of procedural self-governance even in recruitment of staff and students' admission with the mean scores of 1.76, 2.07 and 1.84 respectively. The academic staff of universities on the same items responded with the mean scores of 3.35, 3.20 and 3.50. This falls within the mean range of 2.50-3.49 and 3.50-4.00 set as criterion for high extent and very high extent. Though, both respondents share similar opinion in items 12 and 13 which stated that the university Senate should be allowed to determine the content of their university programs/ courses and that the government and her agencies should avoid covert interference with the university senate in their assessment and promotion of their academic staff with the mean scores of 3.38, 3.45; 3.38 and 3.84 respectively. This falls within the mean range of 2.50-3.49 and 3.50-4.00 set as criterion for high extent and very high extent. Generally, the table showed a cluster mean scores of 2.48 with a matching standard deviation of 0.60 (for directors of federal ministry of education) and 3.46 with standard deviation of 0.44 (academic staff of universities) together with an overall mean score of 3.43 with a parallel standard deviation of 0.48. This implies that the people's right of consent as envisaged by John Locke in his social contract theory can be used to resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN to a high extent.

Hypothesis Two

H0₂: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent the people's right of consent can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU.

Table 4: t-test Analysis of the Significant Difference between the Mean Ratings of Directors Of Federal Ministry Of Education And Academic Staff Of Universities On the extent the People's Right Of Consent Can Resolve The Conflicts Between FGN and ASUU.

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	t-value	Df	Sig.	Dec.
Directors	13	2.48	0.60	11.7	423	0.02	S

Academic Staff 412 3.46 0.44

Key: S = Significant, $df = (n_1 - 1) + (n_2 - 1) = (425 - 1) + (425 - 1) = 423$

The results in Table 4 shows the t-test analysis of the significant difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent to which the people’s right of consent can be used to resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU. The t-test analysis shows that a t-value of 11.7 with a degree of freedom of 423 and a significant value of 0.02 were obtained. Given that the significant value of 0.02 is less than 0.05 set as level of significance for testing the hypothesis, the result is hence, significant. By implication, the null hypothesis is rejected. Inference drawn therefore is that the difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent the people’s right of consent can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU is statistically significant. This means that both respondents share contrary views as regards to the extent the people’s right of consent can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU.

Research Question 3: To what extent can the people’s right to property ownership resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN?

Table 5: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviations of Respondents on the Extent to which the People’s Right To Property Ownership Can Resolve The Conflicts Between ASUU and FGN

S/N	Item Statements	Directors (N = 13)			Academic Staff (N = 412)			Overall		
		\bar{X}	SD	DL	\bar{X}	SD	DL	\bar{X}	SD	DL
15	The government should treat the staff conditions of services as right rather than privilege.	2.84	0.68	HE	3.44	0.49	HE	3.43	0.51	HE
16	The government should raise the salary scale for the university academic staff as a measure to curtail brain drain.	2.92	0.86	HE	3.45	0.49	HE	3.43	0.51	HE
17	Government should avoid delayed payment of academic staff entitlements as that will thwart and dampen their morale and zeal.	3.00	0.70	HE	3.43	0.49	HE	3.42	0.50	HE

18	The government must ensure a reasonable staff-student ratio to avoid over laboring the academic staff.	2.92	0.64	HE	3.01	0.54	HE	3.01	0.55	HE
19	The government must make provisions for comfortable office accommodations for the academic staff of universities	3.46	0.66	HE	3.60	0.49	VHE	3.59	0.49	VHE
20	The government must make provisions for comfortable residential accommodation for academic staff of universities	3.30	0.85	HE	3.34	0.73	HE	3.34	0.73	HE
21	The government must make provisions for soft loan scheme to help young lecturers to procure vehicle to ease their transportation.	2.38	0.50	LE	3.04	0.38	HE	3.02	0.40	HE
22	The government must make provisions for affordable and quality health care facilities for the academic staff of universities.	2.58	0.52	HE	3.41	0.65	HE	2.99	0.59	HE
23	The government must ensure the provision of staff development programs for the academic staff of universities	2.61	0.86	HE	2.99	0.83	HE	2.98	0.83	HE
24	Government must institute a formidable retirement benefit structure for the academic staff of universities.	3.00	0.57	HE	3.19	0.39	HE	3.19	0.40	HE
Cluster Mean		2.91	0.68	HE	3.29	0.54	HE	3.24	0.55	HE

\bar{x} = Mean, SD= Standard Deviation, VHE= Very High Extent, HE= High Extent, LE= Low Extent, DL= Decision Level

Results in Table 5 shows the mean ratings and standard deviations of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent to which the people's right to property ownership can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN. Based on the results as presented on the table, it is obvious that both respondents to a high extent and to a very high extent responded to all the items with the exception of item 21 with the following mean scores of 2.84, 3.45; 2.92, 3.45; 3.00, 3.43; 2.92, 3.01; 3.46, 3.60; 3.30, 3.34; 2.99, 3.41; 2.61, 2.99; 3.00 and 3.19 respectively. The above mean scores fall within the mean range of 2.50-3.49 and 3.50-4.00 set as criterion for high extent and very high extent. However, views of the respondents vary in item 21. On

one hand, the directors of federal ministry of education to a low extent responded on the above item with the mean score of 2.38. On the other hand, the academic staff of universities to a high extent responded with the mean score of 3.04. By and large, the table showed a cluster mean scores of 2.91 with a corresponding standard deviation of 0.68 (for directors of federal ministry of education) and 3.29 with standard deviation of 0.54 (academic staff of universities) together with an overall mean score of 3.24 with a corresponding standard deviation of 0.55. The above overall mean score falls within the mean range of 2.50-3.49 set as criterion for high extent. This directs to the fact that the people's right to property ownership as envisaged by John Locke in his social contract theory can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN to a high extent.

Hypothesis Three

H0₃: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent the people's right to property can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU.

Table 6: t-test Analysis of the Significant Difference between the Mean Ratings of Directors Of Federal Ministry Of Education And Academic Staff Of Universities On the Extent The People's Right To Own Property Can Resolve The Conflicts Between FGN and ASUU.

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	t-value	Df	Sig.	Dec.
Directors	13	2.91	0.68	4.25	423	0.29	S
Academic Staff	412	3.29	0.54				

Key: S = Significant, $df = (n_1 - 1) + (n_2 - 1) = (425-1) + (425-1) = 423$

Results of the t-test analysis as presented in Table 6 above shows the level of the significant difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent the people's right to property can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU. Results of the t-test analysis confirmed that a t-value of 4.25 with a degree of freedom of 423 along with a significant value of 0.29 were obtained. Given that the significant value of 0.29 is greater than 0.05 set as level of significance for testing the hypothesis, the result by implication is

therefore significant. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected. Deduction from results of the t-test analysis is that the variation between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent the people's right to property can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU is statistically significant. Equally, this directs to the fact that respondents share contrary views as regards to the extent people's right to property can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU.

Research Question 4: To what extent can the people's right of revolution resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN?

Table 7: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviations of Respondents on the Extent to which the People's Right Of Revolution Can Resolve The Conflicts Between ASUU and FGN

S/N	Item Statements	Directors (N = 13)			Academic Staff (N = 412)			Overall		
		\bar{X}	SD	DL	\bar{X}	SD	DL	\bar{X}	SD	DL
25	The government should avoid criminalizing ASUU strike since that is their only means of getting reasonable attention from the government.	1.92	0.64	LE	3.50	0.50	VHE	3.45	0.57	HE
26	Government must through the operations of NUC and Federal ministry of Education ensure quick response to demands of ASUU as they arise as a measure to curtail the incidence of ASUU strike.	3.07	0.64	HE	3.45	0.49	HE	3.44	0.50	HE
27	The government must ensure the protection of lives and properties (both intellectual and material) of academic staff of universities.	3.38	0.50	HE	3.84	0.36	VHE	3.83	0.37	VHE
28	ASUU should device other better means of attracting the attention of the government rather than going on prolonged strikes considering the adverse effects of such on the nation as a whole.	3.53	0.51	VHE	2.01	0.70	LE	2.05	0.74	HE
29	The government must avoid every form of victimization of academic	2.00	0.57	LE	3.15	0.65	HE	3.12	0.68	HE

staff because of their active involvement in unionism.

30	The government must avoid selective application of university rules and regulations on academic staff.	2.07	0.64	LE	3.50	0.50	VHE	3.35	0.56	HE
Cluster Mean		2.66	0.58	HE	3.24	0.53	HE	3.20	0.57	HE

\bar{X} = Mean, SD= Standard Deviation, VHE= Very High Extent, HE= High Extent, LE= Low Extent, DL= Decision Level

Results in Table 7 demonstrates the mean ratings and standard deviations of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent the people’s right of revolution can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN. As presented on the table, it is noticeable that views of the respondents vary in items 25, 28, 29 and 30. For instance, the directors of federal ministry of education to a low extent responded on items 25, 29 and 30, while academic staff of universities strongly to a high extent responded on the same items with the mean scores of 1.92, 3.50; 2.00, 3.15; 2.07 and 3.50 respectively. Equally, the respondents have contrast judgments on item 28 which stated that ASUU should device other better means of attracting the attention of the government rather than going on prolonged strikes considering the adverse effects of such on the nation as a whole. On this item, while the directors of federal ministry of education to a high extent responded, the academic staff of universities to a low extent responded with the mean scores of 3.53 and 2.00 respectively. Nonetheless, both respondents share similar opinion in items 26 and 27 with the mean scores of 3.07, 3.45; 3.45; 3.38 and 3.84 respectively. The above mean scores fall within the mean range of 2.50-3.49 and 3.50-4.00 set as criterion for high extent and very high extent. Generally, the table showed a cluster mean scores of 2.66 with a matching standard deviation of 0.58 (for directors of federal ministry of education) and 3.24 with standard deviation of 0.53 (academic staff of universities) together with an overall mean score of 3.20 with a parallel standard deviation of 0.57. This implies that the people’s right of revolution as postulated by John Locke in his social contract theory can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN to a high extent.

Hypothesis Four

H0₄: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent the people’s right of revolution can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU.

Table 8: t-test Analysis of the Significant Difference between the Mean Ratings of Directors Of Federal Ministry Of Education And Academic Staff Of Universities On the Extent The People’s Right Of Revolution Can Resolve The Conflicts Between FGN and ASUU

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	SD	t-value	Df	Sig.	Dec.
Directors	13	2.66	0.58	11.01	423	0.30	S
Academic Staff	412	3.24	0.53				

Key: S = Significant, $df = (n_1 - 1) + (n_2 - 1) = (425 - 1) + (425 - 1) = 423$

The results in Table 8 shows the t-test analysis of the significant difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent to which the people’s right of revolution can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU. Result shows that a t-value of 11.01 with a degree of freedom of 423 and a significant value of 0.30 were obtained. Although the significant value of 0.30 is greater than 0.05 set as level of significance for testing the hypothesis, the t-value of 11.01 is significant this means that the result is significant. The null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent the people’s right of revolution can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU is by implication, rejected. Inference drawn therefore is that the difference between the respondents is statistically significant. This means that the respondents share contrary opinion on the extent the people’s right of revolution can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU.

To analyze the interview questions, the researcher adopted thematic analysis which is a method of analyzing qualitative data. Here the researcher closely examined the data to identify common themes (or responses), ideas and pattern of meaning that came up repeatedly. The responses are structured as follows: VHE= Very High Extent, HE= High Extent, LE= Low Extent, VLE= Very Low Extent.

Table 9: Interview schedule showing Number of lecturers and directors interviewed

S/N	INTERVIEW QUESTIONS	Number of Lecturers interviewed	Number of Directors interviewed
1	To what extent do you think mutual obligation can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN?	10	8
2	To what extent do you think can the people's right of consent resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN?	10	8
3	To what extent do you think that the people's right to property ownership can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN?	10	8
4	To what extent do you think that the people's right of revolution can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN?	10	8

Table 10: Interview responses from the Lecturers

Responses	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
VLE	2	1	2	1
LE	1	1	2	2
HE	4	2	4	2
VHE	3	6	2	5
Total	10	10	10	10

Bar Chart 1 Thematic analysis of interview responses by lecturers

Table 10 and Bar chart 1 above shows the outcome of the analysis of the interview responses by the lecturers. Each of the bars represents a particular response pattern. The blue bar represents very low extent (VLE), the orange bar represents low extent (LE) and the gray bar represents high extent (HE) while the yellow bar represents very high extent (VHE). Here, in interview questions 1, 2, 3 and 4 the response that occurred most is the very high extent. In other words, most lecturers believed that

mutual obligation, people’s right of consent, people’s right to property ownership and the people’s right of revolution can to a very high extent resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN. They believed that while Locke's social contract theory can provide a framework for understanding the rights and responsibilities of both parties, practical solutions would likely involve a comprehensive approach that considers the specific circumstances and interests of the ASUU, FGN, students, and other stakeholders. This response is consistent with the questionnaire responses of both the lecturers and the directors of the ministry of Education as shown on table 1 to 8 above.

Table 11: Interview responses from the directors

Responses	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
VHE	1	1	1	1
HE	1	2	1	1
LE	2	3	4	3
VLE	4	2	2	3
Total	8	8	8	8

Bar Chart 2. Thematic analysis of interview responses by Directors

Table 11 and Bar chart 2 above shows the outcome of the analysis of the interview responses by the directors. Each of the bars represents a particular response pattern. Here, the blue bar represents very high extent (VHE), the orange bar represents High extent (HE) and the gray bar represents low extent (LE) while the yellow bar represents very low extent (VLE). In interview questions 1, 2, 3 and 4 the Low extent and the very low extent responses occurred most. In other words, most directors believed that mutual obligation, people’s right of consent, people’s right to property ownership and the people’s right of revolution can to a very low extent resolve the conflicts between ASUU and

FGN. They believed that although individuals in a society should willingly enter into a social contract with the government to protect their natural rights, such as right to life, liberty, and the right to own property, the people are expected to totally submit to the will of the government. This response disagrees with the responses of both lecturers and directors in the questionnaire results as presented in table 1 to 8 above. It is quite surprising that the directors contradicted their questionnaire responses. Could it be that the directors gave their honest opinion in the questionnaire because the questionnaire gave them the liberty of anonymous responses in which they responded as true Nigerians and probably parents who have actually seen and felt the overall adverse consequences of the ASUU-federal government conflict but responded strictly officially to the interview that took cognizance of their names and official position?

Summary of Findings

From the data analysis and interpretation of results on the research questions and the null hypotheses that guided the study, a number of findings were made. The results revealed that:

1. Mutual obligation as postulated by John Locke in his social contract theory can be used to resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU to a very high extent.
2. The difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent mutual obligation can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU is not statistically significant.
3. The people's right of consent as envisaged by John Locke in his social contract theory can be used to resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN to a high extent.
4. There exists a significant difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent the people's right of consent can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU. This shows that that the opinions of the lecturers and that of the directors are at variance.
5. The people's right to property ownership as envisaged by John Locke in his social contract theory can be used to resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN to a high extent.
6. There was a significant difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent the people's right to property can

resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU. This directs to the fact that the respondents share contrary opinions as regards to the extent the people's right to property can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU.

7. The people's right of revolution as postulated by John Locke in his social contract theory can be used to resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN to a high extent.
8. The difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent the people's right of revolution can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU is statistically significant. This shows that the opinions of the lecturers and that of the directors are at variance.
9. Locke's social contract theory can provide a framework for understanding the rights and responsibilities of both parties. However, practical solutions would likely involve a comprehensive approach that considers the specific circumstances and interests of the ASUU, FGN, students, and other stakeholders.
10. Although individuals in a society should willingly enter into a social contract with the government to protect their natural rights, such as right to life, liberty, and the right to own property, the people are expected to totally submit to the will of the government.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION, RECOMMENDATIONS, SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This chapter is concerned with the discussion of the findings, summary, educational implications, recommendations, conclusion, limitations of the study and suggestions for further studies.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study are discussed below.

The Extent Mutual Obligation Can Resolve The Conflicts Between FGN and ASUU.

The result of the study with regards to the extent mutual obligation can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU showed that mutual obligation as envisaged by John Locke in his social contract theory can be used to resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU to a very high extent. This implies that both the FME directors and ASUU members have accepted the need to keep to mutual obligations as regards to the conflicts between FGN and ASUU. This agreed with the recommendations of Carsten (2021) who averred that to eschew or resolve industrial conflicts, the negotiation parties must avoid selfishness and grand standing but to try and make some sacrifices and some compromises to reach mutual agreement. Also, an earlier study by Ehoru and Konya (2020) revealed that there is significant relationship between collective bargaining / mutual agreement and industrial harmony in tertiary institutions hence, if the management of tertiary institutions should show more commitment and respect for collective bargaining and mutual agreement it will go a very long way fostering industrial harmony in the educational sector.

Based on the findings of the study, there should be establishment of comprehensive agreements between ASUU and FGN with well spelt out terms to address their conflicting issues. It was established that ASUU should live up to the 10% universities funding obligation as prescribed by the government by sourcing for funds from alternative sources. Equally, Government officials should encourage stable academic calendar by avoiding political grandstanding, heckling and harassments in matters concerning the development and sustenance of university education. This

result is surprising and as well, appears to be sarcasm based on the empirical evidences and literature reviewed. Literature evidences showed that FGN has always opposed ASUU's demands and most terms of their bargains making mutual agreement difficult and when they eventually agree, such agreements are reneged upon by the government. For instance, the earlier study conducted by Mbaji (2017) confirms that there is lack of serious commitment by the government towards fulfilling their agreements with ASUU on matters concerning the development and sustenance of university education and this situation has put the Nigerian universities in a serious jeopardy. From this assertion, it is obvious that the findings of the study are quite different from the literature reviewed. Could it be that the directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities faked their responses regarding this issue?

The result of the t-test analysis of hypothesis one found that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent to which mutual obligation can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU. By implication, the null hypothesis is not rejected. Inference drawn therefore is that the difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent to which mutual obligation can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU is not statistically significant. This means that both respondents share similar opinion or view on the extent to which mutual obligation can be used to resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU.

Extent to which the People's Right of Consent Can Resolve the Conflicts between ASUU and FGN

The result of the study with respect to the extent the people's right of consent can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN showed that the people's right of consent as envisaged by John Locke in his social contract theory can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN to a high extent. This result is consistent with the tenet of Locke (1890) on people's right of consent that decision making is not to be left to the government alone because they can make mistakes or allow

their human selfishness and emotions to becloud their sense of judgment and as such, make wrong decisions that can be detrimental to the public. Decisions therefore are to be reached through deliberations rather than the arbitrariness of the rulers otherwise the civil society will become unbearable for man. This implies that the government must consult or seek the opinions/ consent of the academic staff of universities in making and implementing any law, policy or code of conduct affecting the university education to end their conflict. This also agreed with the findings of Olaleye and Arogundade (2013) that to avoid or end a work place conflict, parties must bridge communication gaps and respect the principle of consent.

Based on the findings of the study, it is evident that views of the directors of federal ministry of education vary to a certain extent from those of the academic staff of universities. For instance, the directors of federal ministry of education to a low extent responded on the items that government should in the spirit of patriotism partner with ASUU in making policies affecting university education, recognize and respect Acts and laws governing individual universities and enact policies to allow universities the freedom of procedural self-governance even in recruitment of staff and students and admission of students. The academic staff of universities on the same items responded differently indicating high extent and very high extent. This result is an eye opener that most unfulfilled agreement between the FGN and ASUU that led to the incessant ASUU strike is as a result of shabby treatment of the matter by the government. This result is not surprising considering the earlier assertion of Chile and Ogbu (2021) who stated that the government has for long and by all means reiterated its right to control all affairs of the universities since they fund university staff salaries, infrastructure and most activities of the universities, hence the government does not seek the consent of academic staff while enacting laws and policies affecting university education and continuously breached collective bargaining and agreement with ASUU on this matter.

The result from the test of hypothesis two showed that the difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent the people's right of consent can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU is statistically

significant. By implication, the null hypothesis is rejected. However, given that the overall mean rating is within the range of 2.50 to 3.49, is an implication that the people's right of consent as envisaged by John Locke in his social contract theory can be used to resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN to a high extent. This means that both respondents share almost similar opinion as regards to the extent to which people's right of consent can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU.

The Extent to which People's Right to Property Ownership Can Resolve the Conflicts between ASUU and FGN

The result of the study which dwelt on the extent to which the people's right to property ownership can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN showed that the people's right to property ownership as envisaged by John Locke in his social contract theory can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN to a high extent. This result is in line with the tenet of Locke (1890) on people's right to property ownership as he argues that people's right to property ownership which includes the right to entitlement accruable to labour is an inalienable right. Hence, to enjoy a man's labour, he must be duly rewarded for it for the reward encourages man to work harder and to acquire personal property, wealth and estate and anyone who denies a worker of this right puts themselves in a state of conflict. The result of the study also agreed with the findings of Ekeoma and Sangoleye (2018) that poor working conditions and welfare of staff and undemocratic leadership style cause conflict between the management and the staff unions.

Based on the findings of the study, it is marked that both directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities had similar positive responses. For instance, they all responded that the government should treat the staff conditions of services as right rather than privilege, raise the salary scale for the university academic staff as a measure to curtail brain drain, avoid delayed payment of academic staff entitlements as that will thwart and dampen their morale and zeal, make provisions for comfortable office accommodations and residence for the academic staff of universities to a high extent and very high extent. This result is interesting because if

properly implemented, it will serve as a lasting solution to the incessant struggle between the FGN and ASUU. Unfortunately, the reverse is the case because this result in actual practice remains only a theoretical postulation that has remained an illusion. This is because the result of the study disagreed with literatures reviewed as Okebukola (2010) reported that Nigerian university staff are suffering from serious poor conditions of services which include: low salary which most times delay in coming, delayed or denial of due promotion, poor standard of living especially pertaining accommodation, transportation and health management, poor retirement benefits structure, over labored work force and so on.

The result from the test of hypothesis three showed that the variation between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities on the extent the people's right to property ownership can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU is statistically significant. This result is based on the fact that both respondents share contrary views as regards to the extent people's right to property ownership can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected.

The Extent the People's Right of Revolution Can Resolve the Conflicts between ASUU and FGN

The finding of the study which sought to find the extent the people's right of revolution can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN found that the people's right of revolution as envisaged by John Locke in his social contract theory can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN to a high extent. This result is consistent with the tenet of Locke (1890) on people's right of revolution. As explained by the theorist, if the sovereign repeatedly abuses his power or consistently fail on the duty of guaranteeing the security of life, property and the liberty of the people, the people should oppose or rebel against him without fear of punishment or any form of victimization. In other words, if the employer repeatedly abuses the right of the employee, the employee has the right to revolt against the employer by going on industrial strike. This is supported by the findings of Sarpong, Kpabi, Abiew and Adomako (2022) which revealed that bureaucratic and autocratic

leadership styles and insecurity of workers welfare and property were among the major causes of the strike actions recorded in tertiary institutions.

Based on the findings of the study, it is evident that the views of the directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities vary to a certain extent. For instance, the directors of federal ministry of education to a low extent responded on the items that the government should avoid criminalizing ASUU strike since that is their only means of getting reasonable attention from the government, must avoid every form of victimization of academic staff because of their active involvement in unionism and as well, avoid selective application of university rules and regulations on academic staff. The academic staff of universities on the same items responded differently indicating high extent and very high extent. This result is not surprising because from the literature reviewed, it is obvious that ASUU and FGN always had conflicting opinions, understanding and ideology regarding some issues. For instance, based on the constitutional power vested on the federal government to oversee the management of university education, the federal government sees the university and its staff as an organ of the state's bureaucracy which should be totally submissive to the interest of the government. The expression of this ideology by the government in her decisions and policies has been a major cause of the conflict between the federal government and ASUU. This is because, as observed by Albert (2015) ASUU sees the university as an autonomous entity, a status that ought to be respected by the government. Hence, ASUU poses as a critical watchdog and the mouth piece for the university community striving to curtail the administrative excesses of the government over the university affairs. These conflicting interests and ideologies have created an ugly circumstance of power tussle between the two parties and that has made them sworn enemies rather than partners in progress which they ought to be.

Furthermore, based on the immediate state of the act the federal government of Nigeria seems to lack the right approach to resolve their conflict with ASUU all these years. This is obvious considering their inability to deal with and to resolve the issues pertaining to university autonomy and academic freedom, poor conditions of services, poor funding of the university education and

others that have constituted the major causes of ASUU strikes all these years and instead of seeking amicable ground for settlement, the government resort to the use of force, ground standing and victimization of ASUU members. How can a government impose unfavorable conditions of services on university academic staff and expect them to keep quiet? As explained by Tide (2020), the federal government imposition of the Integrated Personnel and Payroll Information System (IPPIS) on universities and all the federal government owned institutions while ignoring the UTAS suggested by ASUU was one example of undemocratic leadership style, hence it became a major reason for the last ASUU strike action. ASUU saw this centralized payroll system as an infringement on the autonomy of the university and hence rejected it. To that effect, ASUU called for a two weeks warning strike but the federal government refused to shift ground. Because of the failure of the government to remove the IPPIS and other terms of agreement they reached with ASUU to call off the 2020 strike, ASUU went on strike on the 14th February, 2022. The most painful side of the scenario is that instead of fulfilling these agreements so to resolve the strike, the government declared no-work, no-pay on the striking ASUU. As though that was not enough, the minister of labour and employment went ahead and formally registered two new university academic unions: Congress of Nigerian University Academics (CONUA) and National Association of Medical and Dental Academics (NAMDA) just to break ASUU. These acts rather made the strike to linger for eight months among other ugly consequences. The implication is that if the government has lived up to expectation and shun administrative recklessness on university management, ASUU would not have resorted to strikes in the first place. To curtail or end the FGN-ASUU conflicts therefore, the government should live up to the expectations of providing reasonable conditions of services of academic staff of universities, respect university autonomy and academic freedom and ensure that decisions pertaining to university education are reached through deliberations with ASUU rather than executive arbitrariness. Otherwise, ASUU reserves the right to go on strike.

The result from the test of hypothesis four showed that the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of directors of federal ministry of

education and academic staff of universities on the extent the people's right of revolution can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU is by implication, rejected. This is because the inference drawn is that the difference between the respondents is statistically significant.

The findings of the interview showed that most lecturers believed that mutual obligation, people's right of consent, people's right to property ownership and the people's right of revolution can to a very high extent resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN while directors believed the contrary. The interview response of lecturers is consistent with their questionnaire responses whereas the Directors contradicted their questionnaire responses. This inconsistency is quite surprising. Could it be that the directors gave their honest opinion in the questionnaire because the questionnaire gave them the liberty of anonymous responses in which they responded as true Nigerians and probably parents who have actually seen and felt the overall adverse consequences of the ASUU-federal government conflict but responded strictly officially to the interview that took cognizance of their names and official position? This result is worrisome in that the government through its officials should encourage stable academic calendar by avoiding political grandstanding, heckling and harassments in matters concerning the development and sustenance of university education.

Implications of the Findings

The implications of the findings of this study are examined below.

The result of the study with regards to the extent mutual obligation can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU shows that mutual obligation as envisaged by John Locke in his social contract theory can be used to resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU to a very high extent. This implies that both the FGN and ASUU have acknowledged the need to mutually keep to their obligations as regards to conflicts resolution between FGN and ASUU. This result is indeed a welcome development in that neither the government nor ASUU should renege on their terms of agreement in resolving their conflicts, government should live up to the obligation of providing the 90% funds for the universities by increasing budgetary allocation to education to a minimum of 26% while ASUU should live up to the 10% universities funding obligation as prescribed by the

government by sourcing for funds from alternative sources. Also government should through its officials encourage stable academic calendar by avoiding political grandstanding, heckling and harassments in matters concerning the development and sustenance of university education.

The findings of the study also disclosed that the people's right of consent as envisaged by John Locke in his social contract theory can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN to a high extent. This implies that the government must partner with ASUU in formulating and implementing laws, policies or code of conduct pertaining to the administration and management of university education in Nigeria. Also, Government and her agencies should recognize and respect university autonomy and academic freedom.

The study also found that the people's right to property ownership as envisaged by John Locke in his social contract theory can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN to a high extent. By implication, if the government improves on and ensure reasonable conditions of services for the academic staff of universities especially in the areas of higher and regular salary payment, retirement benefits, timely promotions, quality accommodation, affordable quality health care and staff development programs, this will serve as a lasting solution to the incessant conflict between the FGN and ASUU.

Findings from the study also disclosed that the people's right of revolution as envisaged by John Locke in his social contract theory can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN to a high extent. This result is not surprising. Going by the literature reviewed. It is obvious that ASUU and FGN always had conflicting views, understanding and ideology regarding some issues pertaining to university education for which the government uses force trying to suppress ASUU and their views. Attempts by ASUU to resist such suppressive approach by the government have always ended in clash. The implication is that if government ensures quick response to the demands of ASUU as they arise, guarantees protection of lives and properties (both intellectual and material) of academic staff of universities and avoid arbitrariness and administrative recklessness, ASUU will have no reason to

rebel against the government by going on strike, in other words the conflict between FGN and ASUU will be permanently resolved.

The result also shows that the difference between the respondents on the extent mutual obligation can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU is not statistically significant. By implication the null hypothesis is not rejected. Whereas there is a statistically significant difference in the responses of the respondents on the extent to which People's right of consent, people's right to property ownership and the people's right of revolution can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU, by implication the corresponding null hypotheses are rejected.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommends that;

- Both ASUU and FGN should at all cost avoid renegeing on their agreements reached in resolving the issues pertaining to university funding, university autonomy and staff conditions of service. This is necessary to avoid all forms of hostility and intolerance between the government and the academic staff of universities.
- The government should enact policies that restrict political interference of government agencies and parastatals in the affairs of the university system most especially in the areas of appointment of key officers, recruitment of staff and students' admission, determination of content of the university programs/ courses and assessment and promotion of academic staff of universities.
- The Government should in the spirit of patriotism partner with ASUU in making policies affecting university education. This is to avoid impositions of government decisions on academic staff of universities which might be resisted by ASUU leading and resulting to hostility.
- The government should treat the staff conditions of services as right rather than privilege. They should as a matter of urgency, increase the salary scale for the university academic staff and improve on other conditions of services as a measure to curtail brain drain in the system.

- The government should avoid every form of victimization of academic staff because of their active involvement in unionism. They should avoid criminalizing ASUU strike since that is their only means of getting reasonable attention from the government and checking administrative excesses of the government.
- Government should through the operations of NUC and Federal ministry of Education ensure quick response to demands of ASUU as they arise as a measure to curtail the incidence of ASUU strike.

Limitations of the Study

Some of the limitations of this study include:

1. The instrument for data collection was developed by the researcher, it was not standardized, and this may affect the reliability of the instrument when used on different respondents.
2. Some characteristics of the directors of federal ministry of education and academic staff of universities such as their socio-economic status, experience and qualification were not included in the study. These might have accounted for the differences in their responses to a certain extent.
3. Some of the respondents refused to answer the questionnaire on the grounds that they were busy and had no time to give their responses. Some actually collected the instrument but travelled thereafter and could not respond to them prior to the time data were compiled and analyzed. Consequently, out of the 448 copies of the questionnaire administered, only 425 copies were retrieved. This makes the study to suffer attrition of 23 respondents. Therefore, care must be taken before drawing sharp conclusions based on the outcome of this study.

In spite of the limitations pointed out above, the study has however been able to establish that social contract theory as postulated by John Locke can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN to a high extent.

Suggestions for Further Studies

Based on the findings and the limitations of the study, the researcher suggests that further research can be carried out in the following areas:

- Application of John Locke theory of right of revolution in resolving the incessant conflicts between ASUU and FGN in federal universities in North East, Nigeria.
- Application of John Locke social contract theory as a conflict management strategy among university administrators in South-West Nigeria.
- Application of John Locke social contract theory in conflict resolution between the federal government of Nigeria and non academic staff of the Nigerian universities
- Application of Thomas Hobbes social contract in resolving internal conflicts in federal universities in South West Nigeria.

Summary of the Study

This study focused on Locke's social contract with the view to determine its application in resolving the incessant conflict between the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) and the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU). Concepts such as university education, federal government of Nigeria, academic staff union of universities (ASUU), conflict, conflict resolution and John Locke's social contract were reviewed. Three theories were reviewed under theoretical framework which include; John Locke social contract theory, the pluralistic theory of industrial conflict and Marxist theory of industrial conflict. Under the review of empirical studies, twenty-two (22) studies were reviewed. The studies reviewed focused on mutual obligation, right of consent, right of property ownership and right of revolution and conflict resolution.

Four research questions and four null hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study comprised all 4,354 subjects (15 directors of federal ministry of education, Abuja, 12 directors of federal ministry of labour, Abuja and 4,327 academic staff of federal universities in South-East). The sample for this study consists of 448 respondents (15 directors of Federal Ministry of Education and 433 lecturers from the federal universities in South-East) drawn using simple random sampling technique. A structured questionnaire titled: Locke's Social Contract and Conflict Resolution

Questionnaire (LSCCRQ) and interview schedule developed by the researcher from the reviewed literature were used for data collection. The questionnaire is made up of 30 items. The research instruments were validated by three experts from Faculty of Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. The reliability of the instruments was determined using Cronbach Alpha. The direct delivery and retrieval method was employed in distributing the instrument with the aid of 3 research assistants. The four research questions were analyzed using mean and Standard Deviation, while the t-test statistics was used to test the four null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance and the interview schedule data was analyzed using thematic analysis method.

An overview of the overall results showed that mutual obligation as postulated by John Locke in his social contract theory can be used to resolve the incessant conflicts between FGN and ASUU to a very high extent. People's right of consent, people's right to property ownership and people's right of revolution as postulated by John Locke in his social contract theory can be used to resolve the incessant conflicts between FGN and ASUU to a high extent. The result also shows that the difference between the respondents on the extent mutual obligation can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU is not statistically significant. By implication the null hypothesis is not rejected. Whereas there is a statistically significant difference in the responses of the respondents on the extent to which People's right of consent, people's right to property ownership and the people's right of revolution can resolve the conflicts between FGN and ASUU, by implication the corresponding null hypotheses are rejected.

Equally, the major findings of the study were thoroughly discussed, their educational implications stressed and recommendations made. Limitations of the study were acknowledged and suggestions for further studies were also emphasized.

Conclusion

It is evident from the findings of the study that mutual obligation, people's right of consent, people's right to property ownership and people's right of revolution as postulated by John Locke in

his social contract theory can be used to resolve the incessant conflicts between FGN and ASUU to a high extent. That is to say that if both the government and ASUU should live up to their obligations by not renegeing on the terms of agreement they reached in the process of resolving their conflicts and by living up to their mutual obligations towards university education funding of 90% and 10% for government and ASUU respectively, their conflict will be resolved. Also, if the federal government of Nigeria can swallow her pride and do away with political grandstanding, heckling and harassments and all forms of administrative recklessness and begin to partner with ASUU in formulating and implementing laws, policies or code of conduct pertaining to the administration and management of university education in Nigeria as well as showing respect and recognition of university autonomy and academic freedom. The study also revealed that if the government improves on and ensure reasonable conditions of services for the academic staff of universities especially in the areas of higher and regular salary payment, retirement benefits, timely promotions, quality accommodation, affordable quality health care and staff development programs, this will serve as a lasting solution to the incessant conflict between the FGN and ASUU. Furthermore, if government ensures quick response to demands of ASUU as they arise, guarantees protection of lives and properties (both intellectual and material) of academic staff of universities and avoid arbitrariness and administrative recklessness or the use of suppressive approach on ASUU members, ASUU will have no reason to rebel against the government by going on strike, in other words the conflict between FGN and ASUU will be permanently resolved.

Based on these findings, one can rightly concluded that John Locke's social contract theory is acceptable and to high extent a relevant approach in resolving the incessant conflict between the federal government of Nigeria and the Academic staff union of universities. Thus, in formulating and implementation of policies or strategies for the resolution of FGN-ASUU conflicts in Nigerian universities irrespective of the geographical zones of the university, John Locks idea of social contract should be considered and adopted as a model or guiding principle.

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APPENDIX A

A Request for Completion of Research Instrument (Questionnaire)

Department of Educational Foundations
Faculty of Education
University of Nigeria
Nsukka.

Dear Sir/Madam,

REQUEST FOR COMPLETION OF RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

I am a postgraduate student of Philosophy of Education in the above-named department and institution. I am conducting a research titled “Application of John Locke’s social contract in resolving incessant conflict between federal government of Nigeria and academic staff union of universities (ASUU)”. I humbly solicit your kind assistance in supplying information on the attached questionnaire in order to enable me continue with the research work. The information being sought is only for the purpose of this research work and will be treated with utmost confidence.

Thanks in anticipation of your assistance.

Yours Sincerely,

Njoku Maurice Ejike
PG/Ph.D/16/83179

APPENDIX B
Locke's social contract and conflict resolution questionnaire (LSCCRQ)

Section A: Demographic Information of the Respondent.

Please kindly fill the spaces provided, as they apply to you.

1. Name of Institution
2. Director Federal Ministry of Education [] University Lecturer []

Section B: Information on Relevance of John Locke's social contract in resolving ongoing conflict between federal government of Nigeria and academic staff union of universities (ASUU) in South-East Nigeria.

Kindly tick (✓) in the column that most appropriately expresses your opinion on Application of John Locke's social contract theory on conflict resolution between federal government of Nigeria and Academic staff union of Federal Universities in South-East Nigeria.

Key:

VHE - Very High Extent

HE- High Extent

LE- Low Extent

VLE- Very Low Extent

Cluster A

Extent to which mutual obligation can resolve the conflict between ASUU and FGN.

S/N	Item Statement	VHE	HE	LE	VLE
1	Establishment of comprehensive agreements between ASUU and FGN with well spelt out terms to address their conflicting issues.				
2	Parties to an agreement (ASUU and FGN) should not renege on such agreements.				
3	The agreements must indicate the repercussion for renegeing on the terms of agreements by any of the parties.				
4	The government should live up to the obligation of providing the 90% funds for the universities by increasing budgetary allocation to education to a minimum of 26% UN prescription.				
5	ASUU should live up to the 10% universities funding obligation as prescribed by the government by sourcing for funds from alternative sources.				
6	Government should make it easier for universities to access the Education Trust Funds (ETF) as a means of increasing university funding.				

7	ASUU should through their publications liaise with the government to reorient the masses towards the responsibility of assisting the government in funding the university education.				
8	FGN should prioritize educational development and show strong commitments to its sustainability.				
9	Government officials should encourage stable academic calendar by avoiding political grandstanding, heckling and harassments in matters concerning the development and sustenance of university education.				

Cluster B

Extent to which the people's right of consent can resolve the conflict between ASUU and FGN.

S/N	Item Statement	VHE	HE	LE	VLE
10	Government should in the spirit of patriotism partner with ASUU in making policies affecting university education.				
11	Government and her agencies should recognize and respect Acts and laws governing individual universities.				
12	Government should enact policies to allow universities the freedom of procedural self-governance even in recruitment of staff and students' admission.				
13	The university Senate should be allowed to determine the content of their university programs/ courses.				
14	The Government and her agencies should avoid covert interference with the university senate in their assessment and promotion of their academic staff.				

Cluster C

Extent to which the people's right of property ownership can resolve the conflict between ASUU and FGN.

S/N	Item Statement	VHE	HE	LE	VLE
15	Government should treat staff conditions of services as right rather than privilege.				
16	Government should raise the salary scale for the university academic staff as a measure to curtail brain drain.				
17	Government should avoid delayed payment of academic staff entitlements as that will thwart and dampen their morale and zeal.				
18	Government must ensure a reasonable staff-student ratio to avoid over laboring the academic staff.				
19	Government must make provisions for comfortable office accommodations for the academic staff of universities				
20	Government must make provisions for comfortable residential accommodation for academic staff of universities				
21	Government must make provisions for soft loan scheme to help young lecturers to procure vehicle to ease their transportation.				
22	Government must make provisions for affordable and quality health care facilities for the academic staff of universities.				
23	Government must ensure the provision of staff development programs for the academic staff of universities				
24	Government must institute a formidable retirement benefit structure for the academic staff of universities.				

Cluster D**Extent to which the people's right of revolution can resolve the conflict between ASUU and FGN.**

S/N	Item Statement	VHE	HE	LE	VLE
25	Government should avoid criminalizing ASUU strike since that is their only means of getting reasonable attention from the government.				
26	Government must through the operations of NUC and Federal ministry of Education ensure quick response to demands of ASUU as they arise as a measure to curtail the incidence of ASUU strike.				
27	Government must ensure the protection of lives and properties (both intellectual and material) of academic staff of universities.				
28	ASUU should device other better means of attracting the attention of the government rather than going on prolonged strikes considering the adverse effects of such on the nation as a whole.				
29	Government must avoid every form of victimization of academic staff because of their active involvement in unionism.				
30	Government must avoid selective application of university rules and regulations on academic staff.				

APPENDIX C

Table distribution of Directors of Federal Ministry of Education and academic staff of Federal Universities in South East Nigeria

S/N	Name of institution	POPULATION
1	directors of federal ministry of education	15
2	university of Nigeria Nsukka (UNN)	1098
3	Federal University of technology Owerri (FUTO)	825
4	Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka (UNIZIK)	924
5	Michael Okpala University of Agriculture, Umudike (MOUAAU) 788	788
6	Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike Ikwo, Abakeliki (AEFUNAI)	692
	Total Population	4,342

Source: Human Resource Management Department, Ministry of Education Abuja, 2022 and staff personnel service department of federal universities in South-East Nigeria 2021/2022)

APPENDIX D

Table distribution of Directors of Federal Ministry of Education, Directors of Federal Ministry of Labor and Employment and academic staff of federal universities in South East Nigeria

S/N	INTERVIEW QUESTIONS	Number of Lecturers interviewed	Number of Directors interviewed
1	To what extent do you think mutual obligation can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN?	10	8
2	To what extent do you think can the people’s right of consent resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN?	10	8
3	To what extent do you think that the people’s right to property ownership can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN?	10	8
4	To what extent do you think that the people’s right of revolution can resolve the conflicts between ASUU and FGN?	10	8

APPENDIX E

Interview responses from the Lecturers

Responses	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
VLE	2	1	2	1
LE	1	1	2	2
HE	4	2	4	2
VHE	3	6	2	5
Total	10	10	10	10

APPENDIX F

Graphical Illustration of interview responses from the Lecturers

APPENDIX G

Interview responses from the directors

Responses	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
VHE	1	1	1	1
HE	1	2	1	1
LE	2	3	4	3
VLE	4	2	2	3
Total	8	8	8	8

APPENDIX H
Graphical Illustration of interview responses from the Directors

APPENDIX I
Reliability Coefficient

Reliability Coefficient for Cluster A: The extent to which mutual obligation can resolve the conflict between ASUU and FGN.

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	20	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	20	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.829	9

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Item1	3.5000	.51299	20

Item2	3.4500	.51042	20
Item3	3.2500	.63867	20
Item4	3.5000	.51299	20
Item5	3.4500	.51042	20
Item6	3.5000	.51299	20
Item7	3.6500	.48936	20
Item8	3.4500	.51042	20
Item9	3.5000	.51299	20

Reliability Coefficient for Cluster B: The extent to which people’s right of consent can resolve the conflict between ASUU and FGN.

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	20	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	20	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha ^a	N of Items
.795	5

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Item11	3.6500	.48936	20
Item12	3.6000	.50262	20
Item13	3.7500	.44426	20
Item14	3.6000	.50262	20

Reliability Coefficient for Cluster C: The extent to which people’s right of property ownership can resolve the conflict between ASUU and FGN.

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	20	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	20	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.787	10

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Item15	3.4000	.68056	20
Item16	3.3000	.65695	20
Item17	3.6000	.59824	20
Item18	3.3000	.65695	20
Item19	3.3000	.65695	20
Item20	3.6000	.59824	20
Item21	3.3000	.65695	20
Item22	3.1500	.67082	20
Item23	3.5500	.60481	20
Item24	3.3500	.48936	20

Reliability Coefficient for Cluster D: The extent to which people's right of revolution can resolve the conflict between ASUU and FGN.

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	20	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	20	100.0

a. List wise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha ^a	N of Items
.712	6

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Item25	3.4500	.51042	20
Item26	3.2000	.41039	20
Item27	3.4000	.59824	20
Item28	3.4500	.51042	20
Item29	3.8500	.36635	20
Item30	3.4500	.51042	20

OVERALL RELIABILITY

Case Processing Summary

	N	%
Cases Valid	20	100.0
Excluded ^a	0	.0
Total	20	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha ^a	N of Items
.781	30

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Item1	3.5000	.51299	20
Item2	3.4500	.51042	20
Item3	3.2500	.63867	20

Item4	3.5000	.51299	20
Item5	3.4500	.51042	20
Item6	3.5000	.51299	20
Item7	3.6500	.48936	20
Item8	3.6000	.50262	20
Item9	3.4500	.51042	20
Item10	3.5000	.51299	20
Item11	3.6500	.48936	20
Item12	3.6000	.50262	20
Item13	3.7500	.44426	20
Item14	3.3500	.48936	20
Item15	3.6500	.48936	20
Item16	3.7500	.44426	20
Item17	3.6000	.50262	20
Item18	3.4000	.68056	20
Item19	3.3000	.65695	20
Item20	3.6000	.59824	20
Item21	3.3000	.65695	20
Item22	3.1500	.67082	20
Item23	3.5500	.60481	20
Item24	3.3500	.48936	20
Item25	3.4500	.51042	20
Item26	3.2000	.41039	20
Item27	3.4000	.59824	20
Item28	3.4500	.51042	20
Item29	3.8500	.36635	20
Item30	3.4500	.51042	20

Appendix J

Analysis of Co-efficient

Research Question 1

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Establishment of Academic Staff	412	3.4005	.49059

comprehensive agreements between ASUU and FGN with well spelt out terms to address their conflicting issues.	Directors of Fed. M	13	3.3077	.48038
	Total	425	3.3976	.48999
Parties to agreement (ASUU and FGN) should not renege on such agreements.	Academic Staff	412	3.6529	.47662
	Directors of Fed. M	13	2.0769	.75955
	Total	425	3.6047	.55710
The agreements must indicate the repercussion for renegeing on the terms of agreements by any of the parties.	Academic Staff	412	3.6529	.47662
	Directors of Fed. M	13	1.4615	.51887
	Total	425	3.5859	.60873
The government should live up to the obligation of providing the 90% funds for the universities by increasing budgetary allocation to education to a minimum of 26% UN prescription.	Academic Staff	412	3.4442	.49748
	Directors of Fed. M	13	2.3077	.75107
	Total	425	3.4094	.54245
ASUU should live up to the 10% universities funding obligation as prescribed by the government by sourcing for funds from alternative sources.	Academic Staff	412	3.7476	.43493
	Directors of Fed. M	13	3.7692	.43853
	Total	425	3.7482	.43454
The government should make it easier for universities to access the Education Trust Funds (ETF) as a means of increasing university funding.	Academic Staff	412	3.3471	.47662
	Directors of Fed. M	13	1.8462	.68874
	Total	425	3.3012	.54826
ASUU should through their publications liaise with the government to reorient the masses towards the responsibility of assisting the government in funding the university education.	Academic Staff	412	3.6529	.47662
	Directors of Fed. M	13	3.6923	.48038
	Total	425	3.6541	.47622
FGN should prioritize	Academic Staff	412	3.7476	.43493

educational development and show strong commitments to its sustainability.	Directors of Fed. M	13	3.6923	.48038
	Total	425	3.7459	.43588
Government officials should encourage stable academic calendar by avoiding political grandstanding, heckling and harassments in matters concerning the development and sustenance of university education.	Academic Staff	412	3.5995	.49059
	Directors of Fed. M	13	1.7692	.72501
	Total	425	3.5435	.58970

Research Question 2

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Government should in the spirit of patriotism partner with ASUU in making policies affecting university education.	Academic Staff	412	3.3519	.47816
	Directors of Fed. M	13	1.7692	.43853
	Total	425	3.3035	.54911
Government and her agencies should recognize and respect Acts and laws governing individual universities.	Academic Staff	412	3.2063	.40515
	Directors of Fed. M	13	2.0769	.75955
	Total	425	3.1718	.46190
Government should enact policies to allow universities the freedom of procedural self-governance even in recruitment of staff and students' admission.	Academic Staff	412	3.5000	.50061
	Directors of Fed. M	13	1.8462	.68874
	Total	425	3.4494	.58107
The university Senate should be allowed to determine the content of their university programs/ courses.	Academic Staff	412	3.4539	.49847
	Directors of Fed. M	13	3.3846	.50637
	Total	425	3.4518	.49825
The government and her agencies should avoid	Academic Staff	412	3.8471	.36034
	Directors of Fed. M	13	3.3846	.65044

covert interference with the university senate in their assessment and promotion of their academic staff.	Total	425	3.8329	.37973
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Research Question 3

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
The government should treat the staff conditions of services as right rather than privilege.	Academic Staff	412	3.4515	.49824
	Directors of Fed. M	13	2.8462	.68874
	Total	425	3.4329	.51473
The government should raise the salary scale for the university academic staff as a measure to curtail brain drain.	Academic Staff	412	3.4539	.49847
	Directors of Fed. M	13	2.9231	.86232
	Total	425	3.4376	.51988
Government should avoid delayed payment of academic staff entitlements as that will thwart and dampen their morale and zeal.	Academic Staff	412	3.4393	.49691
	Directors of Fed. M	13	3.0000	.70711
	Total	425	3.4259	.50915
The government must ensure a reasonable staff-student ratio to avoid over laboring the academic staff.	Academic Staff	412	3.0097	.54919
	Directors of Fed. M	13	2.9231	.64051
	Total	425	3.0071	.55154
The government must make provisions for comfortable office accommodations for the academic staff of universities	Academic Staff	412	3.6019	.49009
	Directors of Fed. M	13	3.4615	.66023
	Total	425	3.5976	.49573
The government must make provisions for comfortable residential	Academic Staff	412	3.3471	.73057
	Directors of Fed. M	13	3.3077	.85485

accommodation for academic staff of universities	Total	425	3.3459	.73355
The government must make provisions for soft loan scheme to help young lecturers to procure vehicle to ease their transportation.	Academic Staff	412	3.0461	.38878
	Directors of Fed. M	13	2.3846	.50637
	Total	425	3.0259	.40839
The government must make provisions for affordable and quality health care facilities for the academic staff of universities.	Academic Staff	412	3.4150	.65444
	Directors of Fed. M	13	2.5846	.52637
	Total	425	2.9998	.59041
The government must ensure the provision of staff development programs for the academic staff of universities	Academic Staff	412	2.9927	.83561
	Directors of Fed. M	13	2.6154	.86972
	Total	425	2.9812	.83814
Government must institute a formidable retirement benefit structure for the academic staff of universities.	Academic Staff	412	3.1990	.39976
	Directors of Fed. M	13	3.0000	.57735
	Total	425	3.1929	.40684

Research Question 4

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
The government should avoid criminalizing ASUU strike since that is their only means of getting reasonable attention from the government.	Academic Staff	412	3.5000	.50061
	Directors of Fed. M	13	1.9231	.64051
	Total	425	3.4518	.57310
Government must through the operations of NUC	Academic Staff	412	3.4539	.49847
	Directors of Fed. M	13	3.0769	.64051

and Federal ministry of Education ensure quick response to demands of ASUU as they arise as a measure to curtail the incidence of ASUU strike.	Total	425	3.4424	.50665
The government must ensure the protection of lives and properties (both intellectual and material) of academic staff of universities.	Academic Staff	412	3.8471	.36034
	Directors of Fed. M	13	3.3846	.50637
	Total	425	3.8329	.37347
ASUU should device other better means of attracting the attention of the government rather than going on prolonged strikes considering the adverse effects of such on the nation as a whole.	Academic Staff	412	2.0024	.70279
	Directors of Fed. M	13	3.5385	.51887
	Total	425	2.0494	.74600
The government must avoid every form of victimization of academic staff because of their active involvement in unionism.	Academic Staff	412	3.1578	.65577
	Directors of Fed. M	13	2.0000	.57735
	Total	425	3.1224	.68273
The government must avoid selective application of university rules and regulations on academic staff.	Academic Staff	412	3.5000	.50061
	Directors of Fed. M	13	2.0769	.64051
	Total	425	3.4565	.56101

Hypothesis 1

Independent Samples Test

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper

Establishment of comprehensive agreements between ASUU and FGN with well spelt out terms to address their conflicting issues.	E q u a l v a r i a n c e s a s s u m e d E q u a l v a r i a n c e s n o t a s s u m e d	3.613	.058	.672	423	.502	.09279	.13812	-.17868	.36427
				.685	12.802	.505	.09279	.13541	-.20020	.38579

Parties to agreement (ASUU and FGN) should not renege on such agreements.	E q u a l v a r i a n c e s a s s u m e d E q u a l v a r i a n c e s n o t a s s u m e d	6.131	.014	11.490	423	.000	1.57599	.13716	1.30639	1.84559
				7.435	12.300	.000	1.57599	.21197	1.11540	2.03658

The agreements must indicate the repercussion for reneging on the terms of agreements by any of the parties.	E q u a l v a r i a n c e s a s s u m e d	1.169	.280	16.279	423	.000	2.19137	.13461	1.92678	2.45597
	E q u a l v a r i a n c e s n o t a s s u m e d			15.029	12.647	.000	2.19137	.14581	1.87547	2.50728

<p>The government should live up to the obligation of providing the 90% funds for the universities by increasing budgetary allocation to education to a minimum of 26% UN prescription.</p>	E q u a l v a r i a n c e s s u m e d	41.245	.000	7.967	423	.000	1.13648	.14266	.85608	1.41688
	E q u a l v a r i a n c e s s u m e d			5.418	12.334	.000	1.13648	.20975	.68086	1.59211

The government should make it easier for universities to access the Education Trust Funds (ETF) as a means of increasing university funding.	E q u a l v a r i a n c e s s u m e d	2.227	.136	11.011	423	.000	1.50093	.13632	1.23299	1.76888
	E q u a l v a r i a n c e s n o t a s s u m e d			7.799	12.365	.000	1.50093	.19246	1.08297	1.91890

ASUU should through their publications liaise with the government to reorient the masses towards the responsibility of assisting the government in funding the university education.	E q u a l v a r i a n c e s a s s u m e d E q u a l v a r i a n c e s n o t a s s u m e d	.431	.512	-.293	423	.769	-.03940	.13429	-.30336	.22457
				-.291	12.757	.776	-.03940	.13529	-.33223	.25344

<p>FGN should prioritize educational development and show strong commitments to its sustainability.</p>	<p>E q u a l v a r i a n c e s a s s u m e d E q u a l v a r i a n c e s n o t a s s u m e d</p>	<p>.647</p>	<p>.422</p>	<p>.450</p>	<p>423</p>	<p>.653</p>	<p>.05527</p>	<p>.12290</p>	<p>-.18630</p>	<p>.29683</p>
				<p>.410</p>	<p>12.629</p>	<p>.689</p>	<p>.05527</p>	<p>.13495</p>	<p>-.23714</p>	<p>.34767</p>

Government officials should encourage stable academic calendar by avoiding political grandstanding, heckling and harassments in matters concerning the development and sustenance of university education.	Equal variances assumed	11.684	.001	13.027	423	.000	1.83028	.14050	1.55412	2.10644
	Equal variances not assumed			9.037	12.349	.000	1.83028	.20253	1.39039	2.27018

Hypothesis 2

Independent Samples Test

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	t-test for Equality of Means
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		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Government should in the spirit of patriotism partner with ASUU in making policies affecting university education.	Equal variances assumed	6.120	.014	11.777	423	.000	1.58271	.13439	1.31856	1.84686
	Equal variances not assumed			12.776						12.917
Government and her agencies should recognize and respect Acts and laws governing individual universities.	Equal variances assumed	11.862	.001	9.561	423	.000	1.12939	.11813	.89720	1.36158
	Equal variances not assumed			5.337						12.216
Government should enact policies to allow universities the freedom of procedural self-governance even in recruitment of staff and students' admission.	Equal variances assumed	1.055	.305	11.582	423	.000	1.65385	.14279	1.37318	1.93452
	Equal variances not assumed			8.587						12.403
The university Senate should be allowed to determine the content of their university programs/ courses.	Equal variances assumed	2.584	.109	.493	423	.622	.06927	.14048	-.20686	.34539
	Equal variances not assumed			.486						12.745

The government and her agencies should avoid covert interference with the university senate in their assessment and promotion of their academic staff.	Equal variances assumed	19.135	.000	4.417	423	.000	.46247	.10471	.25666	.66828
	Equal variances not assumed			2.551	12.234	.025	.46247	.18127	.06835	.85660

Hypothesis 3

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
The government should treat the staff conditions of services as right rather than privilege.	Equal variances assumed	1.101	.295	4.258	423	.000	.60530	.14215	.32589	.88472
	Equal variances not assumed			3.143	12.399	.008	.60530	.19259	.18717	1.02343
The government should raise the salary scale for the university academic staff as a measure to curtail brain drain.	Equal variances assumed	75.628	.000	3.678	423	.000	.53081	.14433	.24711	.81450
	Equal variances not assumed			2.208	12.254	.047	.53081	.24042	.00818	1.05344
Government should avoid delayed payment	Equal variances assumed	1.091	.297	3.094	423	.002	.43932	.14200	.16022	.71842

of academic staff entitlements as that will thwart and dampen their morale and zeal.	Equal variances not assumed			2.223	12.377	.046	.43932	.19764	.01015	.86849
The government must ensure a reasonable staff-student ratio to avoid over laboring the academic staff.	Equal variances assumed	.853	.356	.557	423	.578	.08663	.15549	-.21900	.39226
	Equal variances not assumed			.482	12.563	.638	.08663	.17969	-.30295	.47622
The government must make provisions for comfortable office accommodations for the academic staff of universities	Equal variances assumed	10.885	.001	1.005	423	.315	.14040	.13964	-.13407	.41488
	Equal variances not assumed			.760	12.421	.461	.14040	.18470	-.26051	.54132
The government must make provisions for comfortable residential accommodation for academic staff of universities	Equal variances assumed	1.011	.315	.190	423	.849	.03940	.20687	-.36723	.44602
	Equal variances not assumed			.164	12.559	.872	.03940	.23981	-.48054	.55933
The government must make provisions for soft loan scheme to help young lecturers to procure vehicle to ease their transportation.	Equal variances assumed	9.033	.003	5.981	423	.000	.66150	.11059	.44412	.87888
	Equal variances not assumed			4.667	12.450	.000	.66150	.14174	.35391	.96910
The government must make provisions for	Equal variances assumed	2.474	.117	5.622	423	.000	1.03043	.18330	.67015	1.3907 2

affordable and quality health care facilities for the academic staff of universities.	Equal variances not assumed			7.151	13.297	.000	1.03043	.14410	.71984	1.34103
The government must ensure the provision of staff development programs for the academic staff of universities	Equal variances assumed	.210	.647	1.601	423	.110	.37733	.23566	-.08588	.84055
	Equal variances not assumed			1.542	12.709	.148	.37733	.24470	-.15255	.90722
Government must institute a formidable retirement benefit structure for the academic staff of universities.	Equal variances assumed	.025	.875	1.741	423	.082	.19903	.11433	-.02569	.42375
	Equal variances not assumed			1.234	12.366	.240	.19903	.16133	-.15134	.54940

Hypothesis 4

Independent Samples Test

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	t-test for Equality of Means								
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
The government should avoid criminalizing ASUU strike since that is their only means of getting reasonable attention from the government.	Equal variances assumed	11.376	.030	11.083	423	.000	1.57692	.14229	1.29725	1.85660
	Equal variances not assumed			8.792	12.467	.000	1.57692	.17935	1.18777	1.96608

Government must Equal through the variances operations of assumed NUC and Federal Equal ministry of variances not Education ensure assumed quick response to demands of ASUU as they arise as a measure to curtail the incidence of ASUU strike.		7.548	.020	2.660	423	.008	.37696	.14171	.09842	.65550
				2.102	12.463	.057	.37696	.17934	-.01217	.76610
The government Equal must ensure the variances protection of assumed lives and Equal properties (both variances not intellectual and assumed material) of academic staff of universities.		9.461	.002	4.494	423	.000	.46247	.10290	.26022	.66473
				3.267	12.386	.006	.46247	.14156	.15510	.76984
ASUU should Equal device other variances better means of assumed attracting the Equal attention of the variances not government assumed rather than going on prolonged strikes considering the adverse effects of such on the nation as a whole.		.000	.982	-7.809	423	.000	-1.53603	.19669	-1.92264	-1.14943
				-10.377	13.428	.000	-1.53603	.14802	-1.85477	-1.21730
The government Equal must avoid every variances form of assumed		3.269	.071	6.288	423	.000	1.15777	.18414	.79583	1.51970

victimization of academic staff because of their active involvement in unionism.	Equal variances not assumed			7.087	12.996	.000	1.15777	.16335	.80485	1.51068
The government must avoid selective application of university rules and regulations on academic staff.	Equal variances assumed	11.376	.001	10.002	423	.000	1.42308	.14229	1.14340	1.70275
	Equal variances not assumed			7.935	12.467	.000	1.42308	.17935	1.03392	1.81223